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Department of Mathematics

On ARZ-algebra Structure to Apply an Encryption Scheme

A Thesis

Submitted to the council of the Faculty of Education for girls- University
of Kufa in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of
Doctor of Science in Mathematics Science

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1444 A.H

بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

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Dedication

I would like to dedicate this work...

To Prophet Muhammad (PBUH), Fatima Alzahraa and the
Twelfth Imams

Zainab

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Zainab

Abstract

Algebra is considered a significant milestone in Mathematics. Students often find this topic complicated, but actually, it is one of the most interesting topics of Mathematics and regular practice of the topics of algebra can help students develop their logical and reasoning skills.

The proposed method includes ARZ-algebra, fuzzy ARZ-algebra, ARZ-binary block code, and application of ARZ-algebra in RC6 algorithm.

An ARZ-algebra investigates some of its properties. The notions of atom, subalgebra, ideal, ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra, quotient ARZ-Algebras and homomorphism, several theorems, properties are stated and proved.

Fuzzy ARZ-ideal, subalgebra, ideal, homeomorphs, Cartesian product of ARZ-algebra, several theorems, properties are stated and proved. The fuzzy relations on ARZ -algebras are also studied.

An ARZ-binary block code is created based on ARZ-algebra which is a generalization of BCC-algebra. An ARZ-valued function is defined to form this code. On various cases of ARZ-algebra, namely commutative and implicative, not commutative and implicative, not commutative and not implicative and commutative and not implicative, the ARZ-codes are existed. Also, the ARZ-code V is a subset of the universal binary block code. Conversely, the ARZ-code can be used to recover the ARZ-algebra. These results are proved mathematically. Some examples are presented to explain these results. The creation of ARZ-code considers as a new insight for communications.

Digital information has spread over the world; this digital information requires protection from sly activities when sent from one device to another

over the wireless network, so we used the encryption algorithms to save this information. Rivest Cipher 6 (RC6) is block cipher algorithm which used in ARZ-algebra to the encryption biometric information. RC6 is improvements over RC5. It's satisfied the requirements of AES algorithm. It satisfies confusion and diffusion. Dataset used are ORL, CMU, MMI, HZFD, Casia iris, fingerprint and face94.

To estimate accuracy of encryption and decryption data, the researcher used some tests such that PSNR, SNR, MSE, and RMSE.

The researcher used MATLAB R2020a Program and laptop Hp, Intel core i5 and RAM 4GB.

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CMU	The Database Group at Carnegie Mellon University
GIF	Graphics Interchange Format
HZ	Hussein and Zainab
JPG	Joint photographic expert group
Min	Minimum
MSE	Mean Square Error
ORL	Olivetti Research laboratory
PSNR	Pick Signal-to-Noise Ratio
RC6	Receive Cipher 6
RGB	Red, Green and Blue
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
TIF	Tagged Image File Format

List of Principal Symbols

Symbol	Description
\forall	For all
$<$	Less than
\leq	Less than or equal in the fuzzy cases
$>$	Greater than
\geq	Greater than or equal in the fuzzy cases
\subseteq	Subset
μ, β	Fuzzy subset
R_β	Strongest fuzzy relation
$X \times Y$	Cartesian product of X and Y.
$\mu \times \beta$	Cartesian product of fuzzy subset μ and β
$*, \circ, \odot$	Binary operations
\cup	Union
\cap	Intersection
$\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i$	Intersection fuzzy of ARZ-algebras
$\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i$	Union fuzzy of ARZ-algebras
f, φ	Functions
μ_t	Level set of μ
$0, 0'$	The constant

\emptyset	Empty set
$f(\mu)$	Image of fuzzy subset μ under f
$f^{-1}(\mu)$	Pre-image of fuzzy subset μ under f
$\ker f$	Kernel of homomorphism f
max	Maximal
min	Minimum
sup	Supremum
\wedge	Index
X/I	Quotient ARZ-algebra
$[X]_I$	Equivalence class
\sim	Relation
■	End of proof
inf	Infremum
Λ	Index
\in	Belong
\notin	Not Belong

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Introduction

Introduction

I. General Background

Algebra can be defined as a branch of arithmetic where numbers are represented with the help of letters combined with different rules of arithmetic with terms like constants, variables, coefficients, etc.

The ARZ-algebra, its application in binary coding, cryptography are applied in this work. In 2012, W.A. Dudek introduced new of abstract algebras: is called BCC-algebras as a generalization of the concept of set-theoretic difference and propositional calculus and studied some important properties in [11]. The concept of fuzzy subset and various operations on it were first introduced by L.A. Zadeh in [45], then fuzzy subsets have been applied to diverse field. The study of fuzzy subsets and their application to mathematical contexts has reached to what is now commonly called fuzzy mathematics. Fuzzy algebra is an important branch of fuzzy mathematics. Since these ideas have been applied to other algebraic structures such as semi-groups, rings, ideals, modules and vector spaces. O.G. Xi, [44] applied this concept to BCK-algebra and BCC-algebra, and he introduced the notion of fuzzy sub-algebras (ideals) of the BCK-algebras with respect to minimum.

A block code is a type of error correcting code. It adds redundancy to a plaintext, so that the receiver can decode a plaintext with minimal errors, provided that the information rate would not exceed the channel capacity. The main characterization of a block code is by a fixed length channel code (unlike source coding schemes such as Huffman coding, and unlike channel coding methods like convolutional encoding) [27]. On the other hand, BCK-algebras were first introduced in 1966 by Y. Imai and K. Iseki, [19] as a generalization of the concept of set-theoretic difference

and propositional calculi. The class of BCK-algebras is a proper subclass of the class of BCI-algebras and there exist several generalizations of BCK-algebras, as a generalized BCK-algebras [17], dual BCK-algebras [30] and BE-algebras. ARZ-valued function are defined and investigated some related properties. The ARZ-block code is created based on an ARZ-valued function [1]. Every finite ARZ-algebra determines ARZ-block code and the converse is true [29].

Wireless networks are used in communication systems, where they enable more than two users to communicate without physical connections. Computer data are sent from the device to another across an insecure channel. This channel may be exposed to attack lead to theft the data or modified. For this reason, require protection of the data transmitted through insecure channels [38].

Biometric authentication systems have acquired more importance because of the main role of the information security and privacy. Biometric recognition is one of the most important techniques for security privacy due to its biometric traits such as fingerprints, iris, faces, palm, etc. Biometrics is the study of identification based on physical or behavioral characteristics and widely adopted in providing better authentication [15].

Cryptography converts messages into an unreadable form through the use of encryption algorithms. The cryptography is concerned with several objectives are confidentiality, integrity, availability, and authentication [39]. Cryptography is used to guarantee the secrecy and the authenticity of information by different techniques and algorithms.

II. Literature Survey

There are several referred works and gorgeous ideas related to the submission work of this thesis. Data confidentiality grows equally important along with technological advancement. Encryption technique is an essential aspect of information security. The security of encryption technique relies on its key.

In 1976, Is'eki K., introduce BCK-algebra is an important class of logical algebras introduced by K. Is'eki and was extensively investigated by several researchers. The class of all BCK-algebras is a quasivariety. K. Is'eki posed an interesting problem whether the class of BCK-algebras is a variety [20].

In 1999, Wiesław D. and Young J. , suggest a job is concerned with the fuzzification of ideals in BCC-algebras. We show that every fuzzy BCC-ideal of a BCC-algebra is a fuzzy BCK-ideal, and show that the converse is not true by providing an example. We also prove that in a BCC-algebra every fuzzy BCK-ideal is a fuzzy BCC-subalgebra; and in a BCK-algebra the notion of a fuzzy BCK-ideal and a fuzzy BCC-ideal coincide [8].

In 2012, WIESLAW D. AND JANUS T., describe weak BCC-algebras (also called BZ-algebras) in which the condition $(xy)z = (xz)y$ is satisfied only in the case when elements x, y belong to the same branch. We also characterize branchwise commutative and branchwise implicative weak BCC-algebras satisfying this condition. We also describe connections between various types of implicative weak BCC-algebras [12].

In 2018, Mohammed B., introduce RC6 is a symmetric block cipher that possesses remarkable features, e.g., simple structure, Feistel structure and supporting for different block size, key length and number of rounds. However, some recent studies show that this cipher is subject to several

cryptanalyses such as statistical attack, linear cryptanalysis, correlation attack and brute force attack. This paper proposes an enhancement version dubbed Chaotic Key Based RC6 (CKBRC6) that makes use of the Logistic map to generate round keys [5].

In 2020, Zahraa F. and Esraa H., proposed encryption image by using RC6 algorithm and generated key by using hybrid chaotic map (tent and logistic map). the key expansion by using RC6 expansion algorithm. Used some measures to explain powerful of encryption; these measures given a very good indicator of the strength of encryption and the difficulty of breaking [47].

In 2021, Subandi A. and etc., introduced RC6 is a simple modern cryptographic algorithm but can provide sufficient security for data encryption and decryption, RC6 is a parameterized algorithm with RC6-w / r / b, where the suggested w values are 16, 32 and 64 and r values (rotation of encryption processing) are 20, while b is the user-specified key length. It determine the effectiveness of RC6 with the lowest parameters of the suggested RC6 8/5 / b, and we call it with RC6-Lite [40].

III. Problem Statement

1. Sending data to many users in wireless networks may clarify the attackers.
2. Weakness of mathematics in some encryption method.
3. weakness of the key.
4. Difficult return ARZ-code algebra.

IV. Thesis Objective

The aims of this thesis are:

1. Confidentiality is prevents unauthorized access to sensitive data sent between two nodes over insecure channel through encrypt of data by block cipher RC6 method.
2. The highest security provided by some algebra mathematical concepts where it need satisfy many conditions.
3. Authentication is used to make sure that you really communicate with the user you want to. To achieve authenticity, shared keys or public keys, are used ARZ- algebra shared key.
4. Binary block code used to return ARZ-code algebra, where relies on ARZ-function.

V. Thesis Structure

The remaining chapters of the thesis are organized as in the following points:

- ❖ Chapter One: **“Basic Concepts and Notations”**. This chapter ,we will review some definitions and theorems, BBC-algebra, BCK-algebra ,cryptography and quality metrics.
- ❖ Chapter Two: **“On ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebra”** . This chapter presents the ARZ-algebra, ideal, ARZ-ideal, quotient, homeomorphs, and fundamental theorems.
- ❖ Chapter Three: **“ On Fuzzy ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebra”**. This chapter explains fuzzy ARZ-algebra, fuzzy ideal, fuzzy ARZ-ideal, homeomorphs, and cartesian product of fuzzy ideal.
- ❖ Chapter Four: **“ The ARZ-algebra and its Application in Binary Coding and Cryptography ”**. This chapter explains ARZ-code, ARZ-valued function, RC6 encryption and RC6 decryption algorithm.
- ❖ Chapter Five: **“Performance Analysis”**. This chapter presents the performance and security analysis of the proposed method.
- ❖ Chapter Six: **“Conclusions and Future Works”**. This chapter states the conclusion and future work.

Chapter One

Basic Concepts and Notations

Chapter One

Basic Concepts and Notations

1.1 Introduction

This chapter consists of two sections. The first section is entitled basic mathematical. It includes BCK-algebra and BCC-algebra with fuzzy of them and introduces some properties and theorem about that. The second section is Cryptography, and Biometric. Cryptography is a science of studying information security by providing several protocols, algorithms, and strategies to protect sensitive data from unauthorized access. Biometric data as secret information is suggested to enable strong cryptographically-secure authentication of human users [4].

1.2 Basic Mathematical

This section explains two parts as follows:

Part one: BCK-algebra

Definition 1.2.1 [22].

Let X be a nonempty set with binary operation $*$ and constant 0 . Then is called a **BCK-algebra** if it satisfies the following conditions: for any $x, y, z \in X$

- (i) $((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0$,
- (ii) $(x * (x * y)) * y = 0$,
- (iii) $x * x = 0$,
- (iv) $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0 \Rightarrow x = y$,
- (v) $0 * x = 0$.

Remark 1.2.1 [22].

In $(X;*,0)$ a **BCK-algebra**, we can define a binary relation (\leq) by $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0, x, y \in X$.

Definition 1.2.2. [16].

Let X be a set with a binary operation $*$ and constant 0 , then $(X;*,0)$ is called a **BCK-algebra** if and only if it satisfies that, for any $x, y, z \in X$

- 1) $(x * y) * (x * z) \leq z * y$,
- 2) $x * (x * y) \leq y$,
- 3) $x \leq x$,
- 4) $x \leq y$ and $y \leq x$ imply $x = y$,
- 5) $0 \leq x$,
- 6) $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Definition 1.2.3 [22].

Let $(X;*,0)$ be a BCK-algebra and S be a nonempty subset of X , then S is called a **subalgebra of X** if for any $x, y \in S$, $x * y \in S$.

Proposition 1.2. 1.[22].

Let $(X;*,0)$ be a BCK-algebra and S be a subalgebra of X , then the following hold:

- 1) $0 \in S$,
- 2) $(S;*,0)$ is also a BCK-algebra
- 3) $\{0\}$ is a subalgebra of X

Proposition 1.2.2. [22].

If we are given a nonzero element of a BCK-algebra $(X;*,0)$, then $(\{0, a\};*,0)$ is a subalgebra of X for any $a \in X$.

Definition 1.2.4. [22].

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra and I be a nonempty subset of X . Then I is called an **ideal of X** if it satisfies:

- (1) $0 \in I$,
- (2) $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x \in I$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proposition 1.2.3. [22].

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra then any BCK-ideal of X is a BCK-subalgebra but the converse is not true.

Definition 1.2.5.[3]

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra. A fuzzy set μ in X is called a fuzzy subalgebra of X , if for any $x, y \in X$, $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$

Definition.1.2.6.[3]

A fuzzy set μ in a BCK-algebra X is called a **fuzzy BCK-ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: , for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (A) $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$,
- (B) $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$.

Definition 1.2.7. ([22]).

A fuzzy subset μ of a set X has **sup property** if for any subset T of X , there exist $t_0 \in T$ such that $\mu(t_0) = \sup_{t \in T} \mu(t)$.

Definition 1.2.8. [22].

Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *', 0')$ be two BCK-algebras. A mapping $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ is called a **homomorphism** from X into Y , if for all $x, y \in X$, $f(x * y) = f(x) *' f(y)$.

Definition 1.2.9. [22].

Let f be a mapping from the set X to set Y . If μ is a fuzzy subset of X , then the fuzzy subset β of Y is defined by:

$$f(\mu)(y) = \beta(y) = \begin{cases} \sup_{x \in f^{-1}(y)} \mu(x), & f^{-1}(y) = \{x \in X \mid f(x) = y\} \neq \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

is said to be **the image of μ under f** .

Similarly, if β is a fuzzy subset of Y , then the fuzzy subset $\mu = \beta \odot f$ in X . (i.e. the fuzzy subset is defined by $\mu(x) = \beta(f(x)), \forall x \in X$) is called **the pre-image of β under f**).

Theorem 1.2.1. [22].

Let $f: (X, *, 0) \rightarrow (Y, *, 0')$ be a homomorphism of a BCK-algebra X into a BCK-algebra Y , then:

(F₁) If β is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of Y , then $f^{-1}(\beta)$ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X .

(F₂) If μ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X , then $f(\mu)$ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of Y , where with sup property.

(F₃) If β is fuzzy ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(\beta)$ is fuzzy ideal of X .

(F₄) If I is fuzzy ideal of X , then $f(I)$ is fuzzy ideal of Y . where f is onto and with sup property.

Part two: BCC-algebra

Definition 1.2.10. [28, 7].

A **BCC-algebra** $(X; *, 0)$ is a nonempty set X together with a constant 0 and $*$ a binary operation, if it satisfies the following conditions: for any $x, y, z \in X$, then

(i) $((x * y) * (z * y)) * (x * z) = 0,$

(vi) $0 * x = 0,$

(vii) $x * 0 = x,$

(viii) $x * x = 0,$

(ix) $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0 \Rightarrow x = y.$

A binary relation can be defined (\leq) by putting
 $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Proposition 1.2.4. [28, 7].

In the BCC-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, the following properties holds: for all

$x, y, z \in X$,

- 1) $z * z = 0$,
- 2) $z * (x * z) = 0$,
- 3) $x = (x * 0) * 0$,
- 4) $((y * z) * z) * y = 0$,
- 5) $0 * x = 0 * y$ then $x = y$.

Proposition 1.2.5. [28, 7].

In BCC-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, the following properties holds: for all

$x, y, z \in X$,

- 7) $(x * y) * (z * y) \leq x * z$,
- 8) $x \leq y$ then $x * z \leq y * z$,
- 9) $x \leq y$ then $z * y \leq z * x$,
- 10) $z * x \leq z * y$ then $x \leq y$, (left cancellation law).

Definition 1.2.11. [6].

A nonempty subset S of a BCC-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called **subalgebra of X** if $x * y \in S$, whenever $x, y \in S$.

Definition 1.2.12. [7].

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCC-algebra. I is called an **ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y \in X$,

- (3) $0 \in I$,
- (4) $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x \in I$.

Definition 1.2.13. [9].

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCC-algebra. I is called a **BCC-ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $0 \in I$,
- (2) $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x * z \in I$.

Proposition 1.2.6. [28, 7].

In a BCC-algebra $(X; *, 0)$,

- 1- Every BCC-ideal of BCC-algebra is an ideal.
- 2- Every BCC-ideal of BCC-algebra is a subalgebra.
- 3- Every ideal of X is subalgebra

Definition 1.2.13. [9].

Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *', 0')$ be BCC-algebras. A **homomorphism** is a mapping $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ satisfying:

$$f(x * y) = f(x) *' f(y), \text{ for all } x, y \in X. \quad \text{Let } I \subseteq X \text{ and } J \subseteq Y .$$

The image of I of X under f is $f(I) = \{f(x) \mid x \in I\}$ and **the inverse image of J of Y** is $f^{-1}(J) = \{x \in X \mid f(x) \in J\}$. The set $\{x \in X \mid f(x) = 0\}$ is called **the kernel of f** denoted by $\ker f$.

Proposition 1.2.7. [9].

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a homomorphism of a BCC-algebra X into a BCC-algebra Y . Then:

- (1) $f(0) = 0'$.
- (2) If 0 is the identity in X , then $f(0)$ is the identity in Y .
- (3) $x \leq y$ then $f(x) \leq f(y)$.

Theorem 1.2.2. [9].

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a homomorphism of a BCC-algebra X into a BCC-algebra Y . Then:

- (1) If I is a BCC-ideal of X , then $f(I)$ is a BCC-ideal of Y . Where f is onto.
- (2) If J is a BCC-ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is a BCC-ideal of X .
- (3) $\ker f$ is a BCC-ideal of X .
- (4) $\text{Im}(f)$ is a subalgebra of Y .

Definition 1.2.14. [44].

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a nonempty set, a fuzzy subset μ of X is a mapping $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$.

Definition 1.2.15. [44].

Let X be a nonempty set and μ be a fuzzy subset of $(X; *, 0)$, for $t \in [0,1]$, the set $\mu_t = \{x \in X \mid \mu(x) \geq t\}$ is called a **level subset of μ** .

Definition 1.2.16. [34].

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a mapping nonempty sets X and Y respectively. If μ is a fuzzy subset of X , then the fuzzy subset β of Y defined by:

$$f(\mu)(y) = \begin{cases} \sup\{\mu(x) : x \in f^{-1}(y)\} & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) = \{x \in X, f(x) = y\} \neq \phi \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

is said to be the image of μ under f .

Similarly if β is a fuzzy subset of Y , then the fuzzy subset $\mu = (\beta \circ f)$ in X (i.e the fuzzy subset defined by

$\mu(x) = \beta(f(x))$ for all $x \in X$) is called the pre-image of β under f

Definition 1.2.17. [34].

A fuzzy subset μ of a set X has sup property if for any subset T of X , there exist $t_0 \in T$ such that $\mu(t_0) = \sup\{\mu(t)/t \in T\}$.

Definition 1.2.18 [10]

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a *BCC*-algebra. Then a fuzzy set μ in X is called a **fuzzy subalgebra** of X , if for any $x, y \in X$,

$$\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$$

Definition.1.2.19.[10]

A fuzzy set μ in X is called a **fuzzy BCC-ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: , for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(A) \quad \mu(0) \geq \mu(x),$$

$$(B) \quad \mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\}.$$

Definition 1.2.20. [18].

Let $\{I_i; i \in \Lambda\}$ be a collection of fuzzy subsets of a *BCC*-algebra

$(X; *, 0)$.

Define the fuzzy subset of X (**intersection**) by:

$$(\cap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i)(x) = \inf\{I_i(x); i \in \Lambda\}. \text{ for all } x \in X.$$

Define the fuzzy subset of X (**union**) by: $(\cup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i)(x) = \sup\{I_i(x); i \in \Lambda\}$, for all $x \in X$.

Proposition 1.2.8. [18].

A fuzzy subset μ of *BCC*-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a fuzzy *BCC*-subalgebra of X if and only if, for any $t \in [0, 1]$, μ_t is a *BCC*-subalgebra of X .

Proposition 1.2.9. [18].

A fuzzy subset μ of *BCC*-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a fuzzy *BCC*-ideal of X if and only if for any $t \in [0, 1]$, μ_t is a *BCC*-ideal of X .

Proposition 1.2.10. [18].

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a *BCC*-algebra and μ be a fuzzy subset of X , then any fuzzy *BCC*-ideal of X is a fuzzy *BCC*-subalgebra of X , but the converse is not true.

Definition 1.2.21. [34, 35].

A fuzzy relation R on any set S is a fuzzy subset $R: S \times S \rightarrow [0,1]$.

Definition 1.2.22. [34, 35].

If R is a fuzzy relation on sets S and β is a fuzzy subset of S , then R is a fuzzy relation on β if $R(x, y) \leq \min \{\beta(x), \beta(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in S$.

Definition 1.2.23. [34, 35].

Let μ and β be fuzzy subsets of a set S . The Cartesian product of μ and β is defined by $(\mu \times \beta)(x, y) = \min \{\mu(x), \beta(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in S$.

Lemma 1.2.1. [34, 35].

Let μ and β be fuzzy subsets of a set S . Then,

- (1) $(\mu \times \beta)$ is a fuzzy relation on S ,
- (2) $(\mu \times \beta)_t = \mu_t \times \beta_t$, for all $t \in [0,1]$.

Definition 1.2.23. [34, 35].

If β is a fuzzy subset of a set S , the strongest fuzzy relation on S , that is, a fuzzy relation on β is R_β given by $R_\beta(x, y) = \min \{\beta(x), \beta(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in S$.

Lemma 1.2.2. [34, 35].

For a given fuzzy subset β of a set S , let R_β be the strongest fuzzy relation on S , then for $t \in [0,1]$, we have $(R_\beta)_t = \beta_t \times \beta_t$.

1.3 Encryption technique

This section explain block cipher, encryption algorithm, biometric, and quality metrics.

1.3.1 Block Cipher

A block cipher is a set of plain text letters is encrypted together to create a set of cipher text. A block cipher is one in which a block of plaintext is treated as a whole and used to produce cipher text block of equal length.

There are many block cipher algorithms like (DES, AES, Blowfish, RC5, CAST-128, RC6.... etc.).

There are two types of Cryptography. They are symmetric and asymmetric. Symmetric Cryptography uses the single key for encryption and decryption. Symmetric cipher is easier to implement in low computation devices. Asymmetric cryptography, it used for encryption and decryption two different keys. The key used for encryption is public key. Receiver has the private decryption key to obtain the original message [39].

Definition 1.3.1.[40] (Lexicographic order)

A lexicographic order \leq_{lex} is a totally ordered set (V, \leq_{lex}) of a binary block code V . This means that

$$w_1 \geq_{lex} w_2 \geq_{lex} \dots \geq_{lex} w_n$$

1.3.2 RC6 Algorithm

A block cipher is operating on fixed-length of bits called a block, it is important in the design of cryptographic protocols and implement encryption of data. RC6 is block cipher and an evolutionary improvement of RC5, designed to meet the requirements of the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES). RC6 has a key expansion algorithm, an encryption algorithm, and a decryption algorithm. The RC6- $w/r/b$, where w is the word size, r is the non-negative number of rounds, and b is the byte size of the encryption key. RC6 is based on seven primitive operations as shown in table (1.1). Size of the block 128 bits, the key bytes are then loaded into an array L of size c word, form $(2r+4)$ words are stored in key array S , the base of natural logarithms $e = 2.718281828459\dots$ and the golden ratio $\phi = 1.618033988749\dots$. Figure (1.1) shows RC6 encryption algorithm. Successful block cipher designs often integrate the concepts of confusion and diffusion.

Confusion: obscure relationship between ciphertext and key such as substitution. Diffusion is a bit change spread from one block to other blocks, where a small change in the plaintext leads to major changes in the ciphertext such as transposition (permutation). To increasing of change between rounds, used a quadratic equation. To achieve the security goals used equation (1.1) twice in each round [36]:

$$F(x) \equiv x(2x + 1) \bmod 2^w. \quad (1.1)$$

Figure 1-1: RC6 Encryption Algorithm [36].

The primitive operations of the RC6 algorithm are:

- 1- Integer addition modulo 2^w is $(a + b)$
- 2- Integer subtraction modulo 2^w is $(a - b)$
- 3- Bitwise exclusive-or (XOR) of w -bit words is $(a \oplus b)$
- 4- Integer multiplication modulo 2^w is $(a \times b)$
- 5- Rotate the w -bit (a) word a to the left by $(b = \log_2 w)$ is
 $a \lll b$
- 6- Rotate the w -bit (a) word a to the right by $(b = \log_2 w)$ is
 $a \ggg b$

7- Parallel assignment of values on the right to registers on the left is
Enc: $(A, B, C, D) = (B, C, D, A)$ and Dec: $(A, B, C, D) = (D, A, B, C)$

1.3.3 Biometric Science

Biometric is one challenge in computer science, which is used to grant security system and proved identification and authentication during matching input pattern with the database [23]. Focus on a facial recognition system which a technology capable of identifying or verifying a person from a digital image [25].

A biometric system is basically a recognition system that captures a biometric character from an individual, extracts a set of discriminative features from the trait captured, compares the extracted feature set against a template set (or sets) stored in the system's database. Then, the final decision is taken based on the results of this comparison. Thereby, users do not need to remember or carry anything with them, avoiding the loss, sharing or forgetting of personal information [37]. As depicted in figure (1.2) the overall structure of any biometric system consists of four main stages, that work in a sequential manner to obtain the result from the system [2].

Figure 1-2: A general structure of a biometric system [2].

The Biometric characteristic should satisfy the following requirements [32]:

- **Robustness:** the biometric characteristic has to be highly unchangeable over a period of time.
- **Distinctiveness:** a biometric characteristic should not be identical in two individuals.
- **Availability:** every person should be possessed the biometric characteristic.
- **Accessibility:** it refers to users, possess ability to use a specific biometrical feature (characteristic) in their everyday routine.
- **Circumvention:** represents to what degree it is easy to fool the system by the usage of fraudulent techniques.

There are two types of biometric highlights physiological and behavioral. Physiological measure a specific part of the structure or shape of a portion of a subject's body. The types of physiological biometrics include (e.g., fingerprint, retina, iris, and DNA) [41]. Behavioral biometrics are more concerned with how to do something, rather than just a static measurement of a specific body part. (e.g., signature and keystroke) [24]. But this is only a partial list of characteristics that each individual has, as new measures (such as gait, ear shape, head resonance, optical skin reflectance, and body odor) are developed all of the time [26] as shown in Figure (1.3) [46].

Figure 1-3: Types of the biometric features [46].

1.3.3.1 Iris

Iris is one of the most accurate biometrics that plays a fundamental part in the identification and verification of people. Literature reveals that the iris structure remains consistent over the whole life of an individual, except for some minor changes occurring in the early life stages [31]. Moreover, the critical thing of the human eyes is its stability and uniqueness in structure. The human eyes represent international organic identity, PIN or security word. The human iris is the colored portion of the eye having a diameter of (10 mm - 13 mm) and has many distinguished features that make it unique to each person. Complex tissue structure is readily available on the outer human body [33]. Despite the small size, the difference between the different individuals is enormous [14]. Even the same person has a difference between the right and the left iris.

1.3.3.2 Face

Recognize faces nearly from birth, though the mechanisms by which we do so are now well understood enough that computers may be taught to do so under particular conditions. Before a subject can access a laptop

computer, certain models employ facial recognition as a form of authentication. The process of recognizing a person based on their face must be carried out in the midst of numerous, frequently contradicting circumstances that modify facial appearance and make the task challenging. As a result, it's critical to investigate the causes of facial variety in more depth. There are two sorts of variation that might be considered. Extrinsic or intrinsic variables might cause a change in the appearance of a face. Many applications have only one or two steps to complete a task, but with a face recognition system, there are a few differences since it has a number of stages, each of which has a dramatic effect on the final recognition rate [21].

1.3.3.3 Fingerprint

Automatic fingerprint recognition technology has now rapidly grown beyond forensic applications and into civilian applications. Thanks to good recognition performance and to the growing market of low-cost Personal Computers and acquisition devices, fingerprint-based biometric systems are becoming very popular and are being deployed in a wide range of applications: the fingers of a human hand in addition to the skin structure on the sole and the toes of the foot have a unique property of being completely individual, which allows them be used for human identification. Fingerprints have been used for identification purposes long time ago due to the well understanding of their biological properties and skin structure. A fingerprint is concisely defined as a smooth pattern of alternating ridges and valleys constructed on the fingertip. While, fingerprint ridges and furrows are treated as parallel in most fingerprint regions, a plenty of other altering features such as scars, cuts bruises, cracks, and calluses can also be found as a part of the fingerprint structure. These features can also be invested as discriminating factors [13].

1.4 Quality Metrics

The aim of image encryption techniques is to encrypted the secret message, thus the quality of the image will be changed from slight modification to very distortion. In order to evaluate whether the level of encryption is acceptable or not, the Pick Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) , and the Mean Square Error (MSE) metrics have been used.

MSE and PSNR are the most common metrics and widely used for image quality evaluation [42]. The MSE measures the difference between two images, while PSNR measures the similarity between these two images (how two images are close to together) in decibels (dB). These two metrics computed very easy and fast, according to Equations (1.2) and (1.3) respectively as follows [43]:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{mn} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (X(i,j) - Y(i,j))^2 \quad (1.2)$$

$$PSNR_{dB} = 10 \log_{10} \frac{(L)^2}{MSE} \quad (1.3)$$

Signal-to-noise ratio expressed in dB as shown in equation (1.4)

$$SNR_{dB} = 10 \log_{10} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (X(i,j))^2}{\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (X(i,j) - Y(i,j))^2} \quad (1.4)$$

Root mean square error as shown in equation (1.5)

$$RMSE = \sqrt{MSE} \quad (1.5)$$

Where m and n are row and column indices, i and j are the image coordinates, $X(i,j)$ denotes the cover image and $Y(i,j)$ denotes the stego image. L The maximum value of a pixel for 8-bit images: $L = 255$.

Chapter Two

On ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebra

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On ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebra

2.1 Introduction

This chapter includes five sections. The first section is about ARZ-algebra. The second section is about ARZ-ideal algebra. The third section is quotient of ARZ-algebra. The fourth section is on homomorphism. The fifth section deals with fundamental theorems.

2.2 On ARZ-algebras

This section introduces new notion which is called ARZ-algebras and defines its subalgebra and give several characteristics.

Definition 2.2.1.

A BCC-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called **ARZ-algebra of X** , if its satisfying the following axioms: for all $x, y \in X$,

(v) *If $x * y = 0$ and $y * x \neq 0$, then $y * x = x$, where $x \neq 0$.*

In $(X; *, 0)$ we can define a binary relation (\leq) by:

$$x \leq y \text{ if and only if } x * y = 0$$

Definition 2.2.2

A ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is said to be commutative, if it satisfies for all $x, y \in X$,

$$x * (x * y) = y * (y * x), \text{ i.e., } x \wedge y = y \wedge x.$$

Definition 2.2.3

A ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is said to be implicative if it satisfies for all $x, y \in X$ if it satisfies that $x = x * (y * x)$.

Example 2.2.1.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2\}$ in which $*$ is defined by the following table:

$*$	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1
2	2	2	0

Solve: $\forall x, y, z \in X$

Condition (i) to prove $((x * y) * (z * y)) * (x * z) = 0$:

If $x = 0$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 0$ then

$$((0 * 0) * (0 * 0)) * (0 * 0) = 0$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 1$ then

$$((0 * 0) * (1 * 0)) * (0 * 1) = (0 * 1) * (0 * 1) = 0$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 2$ then

$$((0 * 0) * (2 * 0)) * (0 * 2) = (0 * 2) * (0 * 2) = 0$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 1$ & $z = 0$ then

$$((0 * 1) * (0 * 1)) * (0 * 0) = (0 * 0) * (0 * 0) = 0$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 1$ & $z = 1$ then

$$((0 * 1) * (1 * 1)) * (0 * 1) = (0 * 0) * (0 * 1) = 0$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 1$ & $z = 2$ then

$$((0 * 1) * (2 * 1)) * (0 * 2) = (0 * 2) * (0 * 2) = 0$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 2$ & $z = 0$ then

$$((0 * 2) * (0 * 2)) * (0 * 0) = (0 * 0) * (0 * 0) = 0$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 2$ & $z = 1$ then

$$((0 * 2) * (1 * 2)) * (0 * 1) = (0 * 1) * (0 * 1) = 0$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 2$ & $z = 2$ then

$$((0 * 2) * (2 * 2)) * (0 * 2) = (0 * 0) * (0 * 2) = 0$$

If $x = 1 \& y = 0 \& z = 0$ then

$$((1 * 0) * (0 * 0)) * (1 * 0) = (1 * 0) * (1 * 0) = 0$$

If $x = 1 \& y = 0 \& z = 1$ then

$$((1 * 0) * (1 * 0)) * (1 * 1) = (1 * 1) * (1 * 1) = 0$$

If $x = 1 \& y = 0 \& z = 2$ then

$$((1 * 0) * (2 * 0)) * (1 * 2) = (1 * 2) * (1 * 2) = (1 * 1) = 0$$

If $x = 1 \& y = 1 \& z = 0$ then

$$((1 * 1) * (0 * 1)) * (1 * 0) = (0 * 0) * (1 * 0) = (0 * 1) = 0$$

If $x = 1 \& y = 1 \& z = 1$ then

$$((1 * 1) * (1 * 1)) * (1 * 1) = (0 * 0) * (1 * 1) = 0$$

If $x = 1 \& y = 1 \& z = 2$ then

$$((1 * 1) * (2 * 1)) * (1 * 2) = (0 * 2) * (1 * 2) = (0 * 1) = 0$$

If $x = 1 \& y = 2 \& z = 0$ then

$$((1 * 2) * (0 * 2)) * (1 * 0) = (1 * 0) * (1 * 0) = (1 * 1) = 0$$

If $x = 1 \& y = 2 \& z = 1$ then

$$((1 * 2) * (1 * 2)) * (1 * 1) = (1 * 1) * (1 * 1) = (0 * 0) = 0$$

If $x = 1 \& y = 2 \& z = 2$ then

$$((1 * 2) * (2 * 2)) * (1 * 2) = (1 * 0) * (1 * 2) = (1 * 1) = 0$$

If $x = 2 \& y = 0 \& z = 0$ then

$$((2 * 0) * (0 * 0)) * (2 * 0) = (2 * 0) * (2 * 0) = (2 * 2) = 0$$

If $x = 2 \& y = 0 \& z = 1$ then

$$((2 * 0) * (1 * 0)) * (2 * 1) = (2 * 1) * (2 * 1) = (2 * 2) = 0$$

If $x = 2 \& y = 0 \& z = 2$ then

$$((2 * 0) * (2 * 0)) * (2 * 2) = (2 * 2) * (2 * 2) = (0 * 0) = 0$$

If $x = 2 \& y = 1 \& z = 0$ then

$$((2 * 1) * (0 * 1)) * (2 * 0) = (2 * 0) * (2 * 0) = (2 * 2) = 0$$

If $x = 2 \& y = 1 \& z = 1$ then

$$((2 * 1) * (1 * 1)) * (2 * 1) = (2 * 0) * (2 * 1) = (2 * 2) = 0$$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 1$ & $z = 2$ then

$$((2 * 1) * (2 * 1)) * (2 * 2) = (2 * 2) * (2 * 2) = (0 * 0) = 0$$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 2$ & $z = 0$ then

$$((2 * 2) * (0 * 2)) * (2 * 0) = (0 * 0) * (2 * 0) = (0 * 2) = 0$$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 2$ & $z = 1$ then

$$((2 * 2) * (1 * 2)) * (2 * 1) = (0 * 1) * (2 * 1) = (0 * 2) = 0$$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 2$ & $z = 2$ then

$$((2 * 2) * (2 * 2)) * (2 * 2) = (0 * 0) * (2 * 2) = (0 * 0) = 0$$

This shows that $(X ; * , 0)$ satisfies condition *i* .

Condition(ii) to prove $0 * x = 0$:

$$\text{If } x = 0 \Rightarrow (0 * 0) = 0$$

$$\text{If } x = 1 \Rightarrow (0 * 1) = 0$$

$$\text{If } x = 2 \Rightarrow (0 * 2) = 0$$

This shows that $(X ; * , 0)$ satisfies condition *ii* .

Condition(iii) to prove $x * 0 = x$:

$$\text{If } x = 0 \Rightarrow (0 * 0) = 0$$

$$\text{If } x = 1 \Rightarrow (1 * 0) = 1$$

$$\text{If } x = 2 \Rightarrow (2 * 0) = 2$$

This shows that $(X ; * , 0)$ satisfies condition *iii* .

Condition(iv) to prove $x * x = 0$:

$$\text{If } x = 0 \Rightarrow (0 * 0) = 0$$

$$\text{If } x = 1 \Rightarrow (1 * 1) = 0$$

$$\text{If } x = 2 \Rightarrow (2 * 2) = 0$$

This shows that $(X ; * , 0)$ satisfies condition *iv* .

Condition(iv) to prove $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0 \Rightarrow x = y$:

If $x = 0$ & $y = 0$ then

$$0 * 0 = 0 \ \& \ 0 * 0 = 0 \Rightarrow x = y$$

If $x = 0 \ \& \ y = 1$ then

$$0 * 1 = 0 \ \& \ 1 * 0 \neq 0 \Rightarrow x \neq y$$

If $x = 0 \ \& \ y = 2$ then

$$0 * 2 = 0 \ \& \ 2 * 0 \neq 0 \Rightarrow x \neq y$$

If $x = 1 \ \& \ y = 0$ then

$$1 * 0 \neq 0 \ \& \ 0 * 1 = 0 \Rightarrow x \neq y$$

If $x = 1 \ \& \ y = 1$ then

$$1 * 1 = 0 \ \& \ 1 * 1 = 0 \Rightarrow x \neq y$$

If $x = 1 \ \& \ y = 2$ then

$$1 * 2 \neq 0 \ \& \ 2 * 1 \neq 0 \Rightarrow x \neq y$$

If $x = 2 \ \& \ y = 0$ then

$$2 * 0 \neq 0 \ \& \ 0 * 2 = 0 \Rightarrow x \neq y$$

If $x = 2 \ \& \ y = 1$ then

$$2 * 1 \neq 0 \ \& \ 1 * 2 \neq 0 \Rightarrow x \neq y$$

If $x = 2 \ \& \ y = 2$ then

$$2 * 2 = 0 \ \& \ 2 * 2 = 0 \Rightarrow x = y$$

This shows that $(X; *, 0)$ satisfies condition v .

Condition (vi) to prove

$x * y = 0$ and $y * x \neq 0 \Rightarrow y * x = x$, where $x \neq 0$

If $x = 1 \ \& \ y = 0$ then

$$1 * 0 \neq 0 \ \& \ 0 * 1 = 0 \Rightarrow y * x \neq x$$

If $x = 1 \ \& \ y = 1$ then

$$1 * 1 = 0 \ \& \ 1 * 1 = 0 \Rightarrow y * x \neq x$$

If $x = 1 \ \& \ y = 2$ then

$$1 * 2 \neq 0 \ \& \ 2 * 1 = 2 \Rightarrow y * x \neq x$$

If $x = 2 \ \& \ y = 0$ then

$$2 * 0 \neq 0 \ \& \ 0 * 2 = 0 \Rightarrow y * x \neq x$$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 1$ then

$$2 * 1 \neq 0 \text{ \& } 1 * 2 = 1 \implies y * x \neq x$$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 2$ then

$$2 * 2 = 0 \text{ \& } 2 * 2 = 0 \implies y * x \neq x$$

This shows that $(X; *, 0)$ satisfies condition vi and so it is a ARZ-algebra

Commutative: to prove

$$\underline{x * (x * y) = y * (y * x), \text{ i.e., } x \wedge y = y \wedge x.}$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 0$ then

$$\begin{aligned} 0 * (0 * 0) = 0 \text{ \& } 0 * (0 * 0) = 0 \implies 0 * (0 * 0) &= 0 * (0 * 0) \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 1$

$$\begin{aligned} 0 * (0 * 1) = 0 \text{ \& } 1 * (1 * 0) = 0 \implies 0 * (0 * 1) &= 1 * (1 * 0) \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 2$ then

$$\begin{aligned} 0 * (0 * 2) = 0 \text{ \& } 2 * (2 * 0) = 0 \implies 0 * (0 * 2) &= 2 * (2 * 0) \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 0$ then

$$\begin{aligned} 1 * (1 * 0) = 0 \text{ \& } 0 * (0 * 1) = 0 \implies 1 * (1 * 0) &= 0 * (0 * 1) \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 1$ then

$$\begin{aligned} 1 * (1 * 1) = 0 \text{ \& } 1 * (1 * 1) = 0 \implies 1 * (1 * 1) &= 1 * (1 * 1) \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 2$ then

$$\begin{aligned} 1 * (1 * 2) = 0 \text{ \& } 2 * (2 * 1) = 0 \implies 1 * (1 * 2) &= 2 * (2 * 1) \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 0$ then

$$\begin{aligned} 2 * (2 * 0) = 0 \text{ \& } 0 * (0 * 2) = 0 \implies 2 * (2 * 0) &= 0 * (0 * 2) \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 1$ then

$$2 * (2 * 1) = 0 \text{ \& } 1 * (1 * 2) = 0 \implies 2 * (2 * 1) = 1 * (1 * 2) \\ = 0$$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 2$ then

$$2 * (2 * 2) = 0 \text{ \& } 2 * (2 * 2) = 0 \implies 2 * (2 * 2) = 2 * (2 * 2) \\ = 0$$

This shows that $(X;*,0)$ is a Commutative ARZ-algebra .

Implicative: to prove $x = x * (y * x)$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 0$ then

$$0 * (0 * 0) = 0 * 0 = 0 = x$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 1$ then

$$0 * (1 * 0) = 0 * 1 = 0 = x$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 2$ then

$$0 * (2 * 0) = 0 * 2 = 0 = x$$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 0$ then

$$1 * (0 * 1) = 1 * 0 = 1 = x$$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 1$ then

$$1 * (1 * 1) = 1 * 0 = 1 = x$$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 2$ then

$$1 * (2 * 1) = 1 * 2 = 1 = x$$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 0$ then

$$2 * (0 * 2) = 2 * 0 = 2 = x$$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 1$ then

$$2 * (1 * 2) = 2 * 1 = 2 = x$$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 2$ then

$$2 * (2 * 2) = 2 * 0 = 2 = x$$

This shows that $(X;*,0)$ is a Implicative ARZ-algebra .

Example 2.2.2.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $*$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	1
2	2	2	0	3
3	3	3	0	0

It is easy to show that $(X ; * , 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra.

Example 2.2.3

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $*$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	2	0	1
1	1	0	2	1
2	2	1	1	3
3	3	3	3	0

It is easy to show that $(X ; * , 0)$ is not an ARZ-algebra , since

If $x = 1$ & $y = 2$ & $z = 2$, then

$$((1 * 2) * (2 * 2)) * (1 * 2) = (2 * 1) * (1 * 2) = (2 * 2) = 2 \neq 0$$

Proposition 2.2.1.

In ARZ-algebra $(X ; * , 0)$, the relation defined by (\leq) satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- 1) *If $x \leq y$ then $x * z \leq y * z$,*
- 2) *If $x \leq y$ then $z * y \leq z * x$,*
- 3) *$(x * y) * z \leq x * z$,*

$$4) \quad (x * y) * (z * y) \leq x * z .$$

Proof:

1) If $x \leq y$, then $(x * z) * (y * z) \leq (x * y)$ thus

$$(x * z) * (y * z) \leq 0 \text{ and By (ii) implies that } (x * z) \leq (y * z) .$$

2) If $x \leq y$, then $(z * y) * (x * y) \leq (z * x)$ thus

$$(z * y) * 0 \leq (z * x)$$

thus $(z * y) \leq (z * x)$. ■

Proposition 2.2.2.

In any ARZ-algebra $(X ; * , 0)$, the following properties holds: for all

$x, y, z \in X$;

$$1) \quad (x * y) * x = 0 ,$$

$$2) \quad \text{If } x * y = 0 \text{ implies that } 0 * x = 0 * y ,$$

$$3) \quad \text{If } x * 0 = y * 0 \text{ implies that } x = y .$$

Proof.

1) Put $z = 0$ in (i) , $((x * y) * (0 * y)) * (x * 0) = 0$, implies that

$$((x * y) * 0) * x = 0, \text{ and by (iii) follows that } (x * y) * x = 0. \blacksquare$$

Definition 2.2.4.

A nonempty subset S of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called **subalgebra of X** if $x * y \in S$, whenever $x, y \in S$.

Example 2.2.4.

Let $S = \{0, 1, 2\}$ in which $*$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0
2	2	1	0

Condition: To prove $\forall x, y, \in S$, then $(x * y) \in S$:

If $x = 0$ & $y = 0$, then $(0 * 0) = 0$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 1$, then $(0 * 1) = 0$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 2$, then $(0 * 2) = 0$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 0$, then $(1 * 0) = 1$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 1$, then $(1 * 1) = 0$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 2$, then $(1 * 2) = 0$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 0$, then $(2 * 0) = 2$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 1$, then $(2 * 1) = 1$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 2$, then $(2 * 2) = 0$

This shows that $(S ; * , 0)$ is a subalgebra of ARZ-algebra .

Proposition 2.2.3.

Let $\{S_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of subalgebras of an ARZ-algebra $(X ; * , 0)$. Then $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$ is a subalgebra of X .

Proof.

Let $x, y \in X$ such that $x \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$ and $y \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$. This implies that $x \in S_i$ and $y \in S_i$, for all $i \in \Lambda$. Since S_i is a subalgebra of X , then $x * y \in S_i$, for all $i \in \Lambda$. This implies $x * y \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$. Therefore, $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$ is a subalgebra of X . ■

Remark 2.2.1.

The union of two subalgebras is not necessary to be subalgebra as shown in the following example.

Example 2.2.5.

Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ and let $*$ be a binary operation defined by the table:

$*$	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1	1
2	2	1	0	2	2
3	3	3	3	0	3
4	4	4	4	4	0

It is clear that $(X;*,0)$ is an ARZ-algebra and $F_1 = \{1,3\}$ and $F_2 = \{2,4\}$ are subalgebra, but $F_1 \cup F_2 = \{1,2,3,4\}$ is not subalgebra, since

$1 \in F_1 \cup F_2$ and $2 \in F_1 \cup F_2$, but $1 * 2 = 0 \notin F_1 \cup F_2$.

Proposition 2.2.4.

Let $\{S_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of subalgebras of an ARZ-algebra $(X;*,0)$. Then $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$ is a subalgebra of X , where $J_n \subseteq J_{n+1}$, for all $i \in \Lambda$.

Proof.

Let $x, y \in X$ such that $x, y \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$. This implies that $x \in S_i$ and $y \in S_j$, for some $i, j \in \Lambda$. Furthermore, let $S_j \subseteq S_i$ implies that $x \in S_i$ and $y \in S_i$, for some $i, j \in \Lambda$. Since S_i is a subalgebra of X , it follows that then $x * y \in S_i$, for some $i \in \Lambda$. Therefore, $x * y \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$, proving that $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$ is a subalgebra of X . ■

2.3 The ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebras

In this section, the ARZ-ideals concept of ARZ-algebra is defined some mathematical facts related to ARZ-ideal are discussed and proved several characteristics.

Definition 2.3.1.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-algebra. A subset I of X is called an **ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y \in X$,

- (1) $0 \in I$,
 (2) If $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ then $x \in I$.

Example 2.3.1.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ and $(*)$ be abinary operation defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	2
2	2	0	0	2
3	3	3	3	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra. It is easy to show that $I_1 = \{0, 1, 2\}$, $I_2 = \{0, 3\}$ and $I_3 = \{0, 1, 3\}$ are ideals of X .

Definition 2.3.2.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-algebra. I is called an **ARZ-ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $0 \in I$,
 (2) $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x * z \in I$.

Example 2.3.2.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $*$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1
2	2	1	0	1
3	3	3	3	0

Solve: $\forall x, y, z \in X$

Condition: to prove $((x * y) * z) \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x * z \in I$,

If $I_1 = \{0, 1, 2\}$:

If $x = 0$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 0$ then

$$((0 * 0) * 0) \in I \text{ and } 0 \in I \text{ imply } 0 * 0 = 0$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 1$ then

$$((0 * 0) * 1) \in I \text{ and } 0 \in I \text{ imply } 0 * 1 = 0$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 2$ then

$$((0 * 0) * 2) \in I \text{ and } 0 \in I \text{ imply } 0 * 2 = 0$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 1$ & $z = 0$ then

$$((0 * 1) * 0) \in I \text{ and } 1 \in I \text{ imply } 0 * 0 = 0$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 1$ & $z = 1$ then

$$((0 * 1) * 1) \in I \text{ and } 1 \in I \text{ imply } 0 * 1 = 0$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 1$ & $z = 2$ then

$$((0 * 1) * 2) \in I \text{ and } 1 \in I \text{ imply } 0 * 2 = 0$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 2$ & $z = 0$ then

$$((0 * 2) * 0) \in I \text{ and } 2 \in I \text{ imply } 0 * 0 = 0$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 2$ & $z = 1$ then

$$((0 * 2) * 1) \in I \text{ and } 2 \in I \text{ imply } 0 * 1 = 0$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 2$ & $z = 2$ then

$$((0 * 2) * 2) \in I \text{ and } 2 \in I \text{ imply } 0 * 2 = 0$$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 0$ then

$((1 * 0) * 0) \in I$ and $0 \in I$ imply $1 * 0 = 1$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 1$ then

$((1 * 0) * 1) \in I$ and $0 \in I$ imply $1 * 1 = 0$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 2$ then

$((1 * 0) * 2) \in I$ and $0 \in I$ imply $1 * 2 = 0$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 1$ & $z = 0$ then

$((1 * 1) * 0) \in I$ and $1 \in I$ imply $1 * 0 = 1$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 1$ & $z = 1$ then

$((1 * 1) * 1) \in I$ and $1 \in I$ imply $1 * 1 = 0$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 1$ & $z = 2$ then

$((1 * 1) * 2) \in I$ and $1 \in I$ imply $1 * 2 = 0$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 2$ & $z = 0$ then

$((1 * 2) * 0) \in I$ and $2 \in I$ imply $1 * 0 = 1$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 2$ & $z = 1$ then

$((1 * 2) * 1) \in I$ and $2 \in I$ imply $1 * 1 = 0$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 2$ & $z = 2$ then

$((1 * 2) * 2) \in I$ and $2 \in I$ imply $1 * 2 = 0$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 0$ then

$((2 * 0) * 0) \in I$ and $0 \in I$ imply $2 * 0 = 2$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 1$ then

$((2 * 0) * 1) \in I$ and $0 \in I$ imply $2 * 1 = 1$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 2$ then

$((2 * 0) * 2) \in I$ and $0 \in I$ imply $2 * 2 = 0$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 1$ & $z = 0$ then

$((2 * 1) * 0) \in I$ and $1 \in I$ imply $2 * 0 = 2$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 1$ & $z = 1$ then

$((2 * 1) * 1) \in I$ and $1 \in I$ imply $2 * 1 = 1$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 1$ & $z = 2$ then

$$((2 * 1) * 2) \in I \text{ and } 1 \in I \text{ imply } 2 * 2 = 0$$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 2$ & $z = 0$ then

$$((2 * 2) * 0) \in I \text{ and } 2 \in I \text{ imply } 2 * 0 = 2$$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 2$ & $z = 1$ then

$$((2 * 2) * 1) \in I \text{ and } 2 \in I \text{ imply } 2 * 1 = 1$$

If $x = 2$ & $y = 2$ & $z = 2$ then

$$((2 * 2) * 2) \in I \text{ and } 2 \in I \text{ imply } 2 * 2 = 0$$

This shows that $(X; *, 0)$ satisfies condition ARZ-ideal .

Proposition 2.3.1.

Every ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra is a subalgebra.

Proof.

Let I be an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra X , for all $x, y \in X$ and let $x, y \in I$, then $(x * 0) * y \in I$ and $0 \in I$. Hence by (iii), $x * y \in I$ Therefore I is an subalgebra. ■

Proposition 2.3.2

Every ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra is an ideal.

Proof.

If we put $z = 0$ in $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $y \in I$, we get $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$. ■

Proposition 2.3.3.

Every ideal of ARZ-algebra is a subalgebra.

Proof:

By definition ideal then subalgebra.

Proposition 2.3.4.

If I is an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$ and J is an ARZ-ideal of I , then J is an ARZ-ideal of X .

Proof.

Since J is an ARZ-ideal of I , then $0 \in J$.

Let $x, y, z \in X$ such that $((x * y) * z) \in J$ and $y \in J$. It follows that that

$((x * y) * z) \in I$ and $y \in I$. By assumption, I is an ARZ-ideal of X ,

so $x * z \in I$ and $y \in J$. From J is an ARZ-ideal of I , so $x * z \in J$.

Therefore, J is an ARZ-ideal of X . ■

Proposition 2.3.5.

If I is an ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$ and J is an ideal of I , then J is an ideal of X .

Proof.

Since J is an ideal of I , then $0 \in J$.

Let $x, y \in X$ such that $x * y \in J$ and $y \in J$. It follows that that $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$. By assumption, I is an ideal of X , so $x \in I$ and $y \in J$. From J is an ideal of I , so $x \in J$.

Therefore, J is an ideal of X . ■

Proposition 2.3.6.

If I is a subalgebra of ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$ and J is a subalgebra of I , then J is a subalgebra of X .

Proof.

Assume that J is a subalgebra of I .

Let $x, y \in X$ such that $x \in J$ and $y \in J$. It follows that $x \in I$ and $y \in I$. By assumption, I is a subalgebra of X , so $x * y \in I$. From J is a subalgebra of I , so $x * y \in J$.

Therefore, J is a subalgebra of X . ■

Proposition 2.3.7.

Let $\{I_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of ARZ-ideals of an ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$, then $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ is an ARZ-ideal of X .

Proof.

Let $\{I_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of ARZ-ideals of X .

It is obvious that $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i \subseteq X$. Since $0 \in I_i$, for all $i \in \Lambda$, it follows that $0 \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$.

Let $(x * y) * z \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ and $y \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$. We get that $(x * y) * z \in I_i$ and $y \in I_i$, for all $i \in \Lambda$, then $x * z \in I_i$, for all $i \in \Lambda$, because I_i is an ARZ-ideal of X .

So $x * z \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$. ■

Proposition 2.3.8.

Let $\{I_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of ideals of an ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$, then $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ is an ideal of X .

Proof.

Let $\{I_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of ideals of X .

It is obvious that $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i \subseteq X$. Since $0 \in I_i$, for all $i \in \Lambda$, it follows that $0 \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$.

Let $x * y \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ and $y \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$. We get that $x * y \in I_i$ and $y \in I_i$, for all $i \in \Lambda$, then $x \in I_i$, for all $i \in \Lambda$, because I_i is an ideal of X .

So $x \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$. ■

Proposition 2.3.9.

Let $\{I_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of subalgebra of an ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$, then $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ is an subalgebra of X .

Proof.

Let $\{I_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of subalgebra of X .

It is obvious that $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i \subseteq X$.

Let $x, y \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$. We get that $x, y \in I_i$ for all $i \in \Lambda$, then $x * y \in I_i$, for all $i \in \Lambda$, because I_i is an subalgebra of X .

So $x * y \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$. ■

Proposition 2.3.10.

Let $\{I_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of ARZ-ideals of an ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$. Then $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ is an ARZ-ideal of X , where $I_i \subseteq I_{i+1}$.

Proof.

Let $\{I_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of ARZ-ideals of X . It can be proved easily that $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i \subseteq X$. Since I_i is an ARZ-ideal of X for all i , so $0 \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$.

Let $((x * y) * z) \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ and $y \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$. It follows that $((x * y) * z) \in I_i$ for some $i \in \Lambda$ and $y \in I_j$ for some $j \in \Lambda$. Furthermore, let $I_i \subseteq I_j$.

Hence $((x * y) * z) \in I_j$ and $y \in I_j$. By assumption, I_j is an ARZ-ideal of X , it follows that $x * z \in I_j$.

Therefore, $x * z \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$, proving that $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ is an ARZ-ideal of X . ■

Proposition 2.3.11.

Let $\{I_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of ideals of an ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$. Then $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ is an ideal of X , where $I_i \subseteq I_{i+1}$.

Proof.

Let $\{\{I_i : i \in \Lambda\}\}$ be a family of ideals of X . It can be proved easily that $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i \subseteq X$. Since I_i is an ideal of X for all i , so $0 \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$.

Let $x * y \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ and $y \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$. It follows that $x * y \in I_i$ for some $i \in \Lambda$ and $y \in I_j$ for some $j \in \Lambda$.

Furthermore, let $I_i \subseteq I_j$.

Hence, $x * y \in I_j$ and $y \in I_j$. By assumption, I_j is an ideal of X , it follows that $x \in I_j$.

Therefore, $x \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$, proving that $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ is an ideal of X . ■

Proposition 2.3.12.

Let $\{I_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of subalgebras of an ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$. Then $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ is a subalgebra of X , where $I_i \subseteq I_{i+1}$.

Proof.

Let $\{\{I_i : i \in \Lambda\}\}$ be a family of subalgebra of X .

It can be proved easily that $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i \subseteq X$. Since I_i is an ideal of X for all i , so $0 \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$.

Let $x, y \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$. It follows that $x \in I_i$ for some $i \in \Lambda$ and $y \in I_j$ for some $j \in \Lambda$.

Furthermore, let $I_i \subseteq I_j$.

Hence $x * y \in I_j$. By assumption, I_j is an subalgebra of X , it follows that

$$x * y \in I_j.$$

Therefore, $x * y \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$, proving that $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ is an subalgebra of X . ■

2.4 The Quotient of ARZ-Algebra

In this section, we describe congruence on ARZ-algebras and we study quotient of ARZ-algebra and describe its properties.

Definition 2.4.1.

Let I be an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra X . Define a **relation** (\sim) on X by: $x \sim y$ if and only if, $x * y \in I$ and $y * x \in I$, as define a relation (\sim).

Theorem 2.4.1.

If I is an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then the relation (\sim) is an equivalence relation on X .

Proof.

Let I be an ARZ-ideal of X and $x, y, z \in X$. By (iv), $x * x = 0$ and assumption, $x * x \in I$. That is, $x \sim x$. Hence (\sim) is reflexive.

Next, suppose that $x \sim y$. It follows that $x * y \in I$ and $y * x \in I$, then $y \sim x$, so (\sim) is symmetric.

Finally, let $x \sim y$ and $y \sim z$, then $x * y, y * x, y * z, z * y \in I$ and

$((x * y) * (z * y)) * (x * z) = 0 \in I$ and $z * y \in I$, then $(x * y) * (x * z) \in I$, and since $x * y \in I$, so $x * z \in I$. Similarly, $z * x \in I$.

Thus (\sim) is transitive. Therefore (\sim) is an equivalence relation. ■

Proposition 2.4.1.

Let I be an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$. For any $x, y, u, v \in X$, if $u \sim v$ and $x \sim y$, then $u * x \sim v * y$.

Proof.

Assume that $u \sim v$ and $x \sim y$, for any $x, y, u, v \in X$, then $u * v, v * u, x * y, y * x \in I$ and by (i), we see that $((u * x) * (v * x)) * (u * v) = 0$ and $(v * x) * (u * x) * (v * u) = 0$, then by theorem $((u * x) * (u * v)) * (v * x) = 0$ and $(v * x) * (v * u) * (u * x) = 0$. From assumption and I is an ideal of X , these imply that $(u * x) * (v * x) \in I$ and $(v * x) * (u * x) \in I$.

This shows that $u * x \sim v * x$ (1).

On the other hand, by (i), we have that $((v * x) * (y * x)) * (v * y) = 0$ and $((v * y) * (x * y)) * (v * x) = 0$. From assumption and I is an ARZ-ideal of X , these imply that $(v * x) * (v * y) \in I$ and $(v * y) * (v * x) \in I$.

Thus $v * x \sim v * y$... (2).

From (1) and (2), $u * x \sim v * y$. This completes the proof. ■

Corollary 2.4.1.

If I is an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$, then the relation (\sim) is a congruence relation on X .

Proof.

By Theorem (2.4.1) and Proposition (2.4.1). ■

Definition 2.4.2.

Let I be an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$. Given $x \in X$, **the equivalence class $[x]_I$ of x** is defined as the set of all element of X that are equivalent to x , that is, $[x]_I = \{y \in X : x \sim y\}$.

We define **the set $X/I = \{[x]_I : x \in X\}$ and a binary operation \odot on X/I by $[x]_I \odot [y]_I = [x * y]_I$.**

Theorem 2.4.2.

If I is an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$ with $X/I = \{[x]_I : x \in X\}$, then the binary operation \odot is a mapping from $X/I \times X/I$ to X/I .

Proof.

Let $[x_1]_I, [x_2]_I, [y_1]_I, [y_2]_I \in X/I$ such that $[x_1]_I = [x_2]_I$ and

$[y_1]_I = [y_2]_I$. It follows that $x_1 \sim x_2$ and $y_1 \sim y_2$. By Proposition (2.4.1),

$x_1 * y_1 \sim x_2 * y_2$, proving that $[x_1 * y_1]_I = [x_2 * y_2]_I$. ■

Theorem 2.4.3.

If I is an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$, then $(X/I; \odot, [0]_I)$ is an ARZ-algebra. Moreover, the set X/I is called **the quotient ARZ-algebra**.

Proof.

Let $[x]_I, [y]_I, [z]_I \in X/I$. Then

- i.
$$\begin{aligned} & (([x]_I \odot [y]_I) \odot ([z]_I \odot [y]_I)) \odot ([x]_I \odot [z]_I) \\ &= ([x * y]_I \odot [z * y]_I) \odot [x * z]_I \\ &= [(x * y) * (z * y)]_I \odot [x * z]_I \\ &= [(x * y) * (z * y)] * [x * z]_I = [0]_I. \end{aligned}$$
- ii. $[0]_I \odot [x]_I = [0 * x]_I = [x]_I$
- iii. $[x]_I \odot [0]_I = [x * 0]_I = [0]_I$
- iv. $[x]_I \odot [x]_I = [x * x]_I = [0]_I$
- v. $[x]_I \odot [y]_I = [x * y]_I = [0]_I$ and $[y]_I \odot [x]_I = [y * x]_I = [0]_I$
then $[x]_I = [y]_I$
- vi. $[x]_I \odot [y]_I = [x * y]_I = [0]_I$ and $[y]_I \odot [x]_I = [y * x]_I \neq [0]_I$
then $[y]_I \odot [x]_I = [y * x]_I = [x]_I$

Therefore, $(X/I; \odot, [0]_I)$ is an ARZ-algebra. ■

Example 2.4.1.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a set with the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1
2	2	1	0	1
3	3	3	3	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra. It is easy to show that $I = \{0, 1, 2\}$ is an ARZ-ideal of X . We can get that $X/I = \{[0]_I, [1]_I\}$, and $[1]_I = [2]_I = \{1, 2\}$.

Let \odot be defined on X/I by:

\odot	$[0]_I$	$[1]_I$
$[0]_I$	$[0]_I$	$[0]_I$
$[1]_I$	$[1]_I$	$[0]_I$

Condition i. $\forall x, y, z \in X$, **to prove**

$$(([x]_I \odot [y]_I) \odot ([z]_I \odot [y]_I)) \odot ([x]_I \odot [z]_I) = 0$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 0$ then

$$\begin{aligned} & (([0]_I \odot [0]_I) \odot ([0]_I \odot [0]_I)) \odot ([0]_I \odot [0]_I) \\ &= [((0 * 0) * (0 * 0)) * (0 * 0)]_I = [0]_I. \end{aligned}$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 1$ then

$$\begin{aligned} & (([0]_I \odot [0]_I) \odot ([1]_I \odot [0]_I)) \odot ([0]_I \odot [1]_I) \\ &= [((0 * 0) * (1 * 0)) * (0 * 1)]_I = [0]_I. \end{aligned}$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 1$ & $z = 0$ then

$$\begin{aligned} & (([0]_I \odot [1]_I) \odot ([0]_I \odot [1]_I)) \odot ([0]_I \odot [0]_I) \\ &= [((0 * 1) * (0 * 1)) * (0 * 0)]_I = [0]_I. \end{aligned}$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 1$ & $z = 1$ then

$$\begin{aligned} & (([0]_I \odot [1]_I) \odot ([1]_I \odot [1]_I)) \odot ([0]_I \odot [1]_I) \\ &= [((0 * 1) * (1 * 1)) * (0 * 1)]_I = [0]_I. \end{aligned}$$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 0$ then

$$\begin{aligned} & (([1]_I \odot [0]_I) \odot ([0]_I \odot [0]_I)) \odot ([1]_I \odot [0]_I) \\ &= [((1 * 0) * (0 * 0)) * (1 * 0)]_I = [0]_I. \end{aligned}$$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 1$ then

$$\begin{aligned} & (([1]_I \odot [0]_I) \odot ([1]_I \odot [0]_I)) \odot ([1]_I \odot [1]_I) \\ &= [((1 * 0) * (1 * 0)) * (1 * 1)]_I = [0]_I. \end{aligned}$$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 1$ & $z = 0$ then

$$\begin{aligned} & (([1]_I \odot [1]_I) \odot ([0]_I \odot [1]_I)) \odot ([1]_I \odot [0]_I) \\ &= [((1 * 1) * (0 * 1)) * (1 * 0)]_I = [0]_I. \end{aligned}$$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 1$ & $z = 1$ then

$$\begin{aligned} & (([1]_I \odot [1]_I) \odot ([1]_I \odot [1]_I)) \odot ([1]_I \odot [1]_I) \\ & = [((1 * 1) * (1 * 1)) * (1 * 1)]_I = [0]_I. \end{aligned}$$

Condition ii. to prove $[0]_I \odot [x]_I = [0 * x]_I = [0]_I$:

If $x = 0$, then $[0]_I \odot [0]_I = [0 * 0]_I = [0]_I$

If $x = 1$, then $[0]_I \odot [1]_I = [0 * 1]_I = [0]_I$

This shows that $(X; *, 0)$ satisfies condition ii.

Condition iii. to prove $[x]_I \odot [0]_I = [x * 0]_I = [x]_I$:

If $x = 0$, then $[0]_I \odot [0]_I = [0 * 0]_I = [0]_I$

If $x = 1$, then $[1]_I \odot [0]_I = [1 * 0]_I = [1]_I$

This shows that $(X; *, 0)$ satisfies condition ii.

Condition iv. to prove $[x]_I \odot [x]_I = [x * x]_I = [0]_I$:

If $x = 0$, then $[0]_I \odot [0]_I = [0 * 0]_I = [0]_I$

If $x = 1$, then $[1]_I \odot [1]_I = [1 * 1]_I = [0]_I$

This shows that $(X; *, 0)$ satisfies condition ii.

Condition vi. to prove $[x]_I \odot [y]_I = [0]_I$ and $[y]_I \odot [x]_I = [0]_I$ then $[x]_I = [y]_I$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 0$ then

$[0]_I \odot [0]_I = [0 * 0]_I = [0]_I$ and $[0]_I \odot [0]_I = [0 * 0]_I = [0]_I$ then $[x]_I = [y]_I$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 1$ then

$[0]_I \odot [1]_I = [0 * 1]_I = [0]_I$ and $[1]_I \odot [0]_I = [1 * 0]_I \neq [0]_I$ then $[x]_I \neq [y]_I$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 0$ then

$[1]_I \odot [0]_I = [1 * 0]_I \neq [0]_I$ and $[0]_I \odot [1]_I = [0 * 1]_I = [0]_I$ then $[x]_I \neq [y]_I$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 1$ then

$[1]_I \odot [1]_I = [1 * 1]_I = [0]_I$ and $[1]_I \odot [1]_I = [1 * 1]_I = [0]_I$ then $[x]_I = [y]_I$

This shows that $(X; *, 0)$ satisfies condition.

Condition v. to prove $[x]_I \odot [y]_I = [0]_I$ and $[y]_I \odot [x]_I \neq [0]_I$ then

$[y]_I \odot [x]_I = [x]_I$, where $[x]_I \neq [0]_I$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 0$ then

$[1]_I \odot [0]_I = [1 * 0]_I \neq [0]_I$ and $[0]_I \odot [1]_I = [0 * 1]_I = [0]_I$ then

$[y]_I \odot [x]_I \neq [x]_I$

If $x = 1$ & $y = 1$ then

$[1]_I \odot [1]_I = [1 * 1]_I = [0]_I$ and $[1]_I \odot [1]_I = [1 * 1]_I = [0]_I$ then

$[y]_I \odot [x]_I \neq [x]_I$

Then $(X/I; \odot, [0]_I)$ is an ARZ-algebra.

Proposition 2.4.2.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-algebra and I, J be any sets such that $I \subseteq J \subseteq X$. If I is an ARZ-ideal of X , then J is an ARZ-ideal of X if and only if J/I is an ARZ-ideal of X/I .

Proof.

Let I be an ARZ-ideal of X with $I \subseteq J \subseteq X$. Suppose firstly that J is an ARZ-ideal of X , then $J/I = \{[x]_I : x \in J\}$, where $[x]_I = \{y \in I : x \sim y\}$, and $X/I = \{[x]_I : x \in X\}$, where $[x]_I = \{y \in X : x \sim y\}$.

Obviously, $J/I \subseteq X/I$ and $[0]_I \in J/I$.

Now, let $([x]_I \odot [y]_I) \odot [z]_I \in J/I$ and $[y]_I \in J/I$. Then

$[(x * y) * z]_I = ([x]_I \odot [y]_I) \odot [z]_I \in J/I$, it follows that $((x * y) * z) \in J$ and $y \in J$. By assumption, $(x * z) \in J$. Accordingly, $[x * z]_I = [x]_I \odot [z]_I \in J/I$, this shows that J/I is an ARZ-ideal of X/I .

On the other hand, suppose that J/I is an ARZ-ideal of X/I and I is an ARZ-ideal of X with $I \subseteq J \subseteq X$. Thus, $0 \in J$. Let $((x * y) * z) \in J$ and $y \in J$. It follows that $[(x * y) * z]_I, [y]_I \in J/I$.

Since $[(x * y) * z]_I = ([x]_I \odot [y]_I) \odot [z]_I$,

so $([x]_I \odot [y]_I) \odot [z]_I \in J/I$.

By hypothesis, $[x * z]_I = [x]_I \odot [z]_I \in J/I$ implies $x * z \in J$. ■

Corollary 2.4.2.

Let $(X ; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-algebra and I, J be any sets such that $I \subseteq J \subseteq X$. If I is an ARZ-subalgebra of X . Then J is an ARZ-subalgebra of X if and only if J/I is an ARZ-subalgebra of X/I .

Proof.

Similar to that of Proposition (2.4.2). ■

Corollary 2. 4.3.

Let I be ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra X with $I \subseteq J$, then J is an ARZ-ideal of $(X ; *, 0)$.

Next, the basic properties of equivalence classes are considered are as the following theorem.

Theorem 2.4.4.

Let I be a subalgebra of ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$ and $a, b \in X$. Then:

- (1) $[a]_I = I$ if and only if $a \in I$,
- (2) $[a]_I = [b]_I$ or $[a]_I \cap [b]_I = \emptyset$.

Proof.

Let I be a subalgebra of X and $a, b \in X$.

(1) It is clear due to the fact that $a \sim a$ for all $a \in X$ and $a * a = 0 \in I$, so we get that $a \in [a]_I = I$.

Conversely, let $x \in [a]_I$. Then $x \sim a$, it follows that $x * a, a * x \in I$.

By hypothesis, $x \in I$. Hence, $[a]_I \subseteq I$. To show that $I \subseteq [a]_I$, choose $x \in I$. Since I is a subalgebra of X , we have $x * a, a * x \in I$. Thus, $x \sim a$, this means that $x \in [a]_I$ and shows that $I \subseteq [a]_I$. Consequently, $[a]_I = I$.

(2) Assume that $[a]_I \cap [b]_I \neq \emptyset$. Then there is $x \in [a]_I \cap [b]_I$ such that $x \in [a]_I$ and $x \in [b]_I$. It follows that $x \sim a$ and $x \sim b$, so $a \sim b$ by the symmetric and transitive properties. Thus $[a]_I = [b]_I$. ■

2.5 Homomorphism of ARZ-algebra

In this section, we introduce the concept homomorphism and we can describe properties of homomorphism of ARZ-algebra, also we give examples and results of it.

Definition 2.5.1.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *', 0')$ be ARZ-algebras. A **homomorphism** is a mapping $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ satisfying $f(x * y) = f(x) *' f(y)$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 2.5.2.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *', 0')$ be ARZ-algebras. In a mapping $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$. The set $\{x \in X | f(x) = 0'\}$ is called **the kernel of f** denoted by $\ker f$.

Definition 2.5.3.

Let $f:(X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a mapping of an ARZ-algebra X into an ARZ-algebra Y , and let $I \subseteq X$ and $A \subseteq Y$. **The image of I of X under f is $f(I) = \{f(x) \mid x \in I\}$ and **the inverse image of A of Y is $f^{-1}(A) = \{x \in X \mid f(x) \in A\}$.****

Next, the basic properties of homomorphism are considered as the following theorem.

Theorem 2.5.1.

Let $f:(X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a mapping of an ARZ-algebra X into an ARZ-algebra Y . Then:

- (1) $f(0) = 0'$.
- (2) If 0 is the identity in X , then $f(0)$ is the identity in Y .
- (3) f is injective if and only if $\ker f = \{0\}$.
- (4) If $x \leq y$ implies $f(x) \leq f(y)$.

Proof.

Assume that $f:(X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ is a homomorphism.

- (1) Since $0 * 0 = 0$, then $f(0) = f(0 * 0) = f(0) *' f(0) = 0'$.
- (2) Assume that (0) is the identity in X and (0') is the identity in Y .

From (ii), $0' *' f(0) = f(0) = 0'$ and

$$f(0) *' 0' = f(0) *' (f(0) *' f(0)) = f(0) *' f(0 * 0) = f(0) *' f(0) = 0'$$

By (0), we get that $f(0) = 0'$.

This show that $f(0)$ is the identity in Y .

(3) Suppose that f is injective and $x \in \text{Ker} f$. It follows that $f(x) = 0'$.

Since $f(0) = 0'$, so $f(x) = f(0)$. By assumption, $x = 0$.

Thus $\text{Ker} f = \{0\}$.

Conversely, suppose that $\text{Ker} f = \{0\}$. Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $f(x) = f(y)$. Then we get that $f(x * y) = f(x) * f(y) = 0'$ and

$f(y * x) = f(y) * f(x) = 0'$, thus $x * y, y * x \in \text{Ker} f$, this means that

$x * y = 0 = y * x$. Hence $x = y$, and shows that f is injective.

(4) Let $x \leq y$. It follows that $x * y = 0$. So

$f(x) * f(y) = f(x * y) = f(0) = 0'$. Hence $f(x) \leq f(y)$. ■

Theorem 2.5.2.

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a homomorphism of ARZ-algebras respectively. Then:

(1) If I is an ideal of X , then $f(I)$ is an ideal of Y , where f is onto.

(2) If I is a subalgebra of X , then $f(I)$ is a subalgebra of Y , where f is onto.

(3) If I is an ARZ-ideal of X , then $f(I)$ is an ARZ-ideal of Y , where f is onto.

(4) If J is an ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is an ideal of X .

(5) If J is a subalgebra of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is a subalgebra of X .

(6) If J is an ARZ-ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is an ARZ-ideal of X .

Proof.

Assume that $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ is a homomorphism.

(1) Let I be an ideal of X . We see that $0 \in I$, and by theorem (2.5.1(1)), $0' = f(0) \in f(I)$, so $0' \in f(I)$.

Now, assume that $(f(x) *' f(y)) \in f(I)$ and $f(y) \in f(I)$, it follows that $f(x) \in f(I)$, so $x * y, y \in I$.

Since I is an ideal of $x, y \in I$ implies that $x \in I$.

It follows that $f(x) \in f(I)$. Hence $f(I)$ is an ARZ-ideal of Y .

(2) Let I be a subalgebra of X and $x, y \in f(I)$. Then there exist $a, b \in I$ such that $x = f(a)$ and $y = f(b)$.

Since $x *' y = f(a) *' f(b) = f(a * b) \in f(I)$.

Thus $f(I)$ is a subalgebra of Y .

(3) Let I be an ARZ-ideal of X . We see that $0 \in I$, and by theorem (2.5.1(1)), $0' = f(0) \in f(I)$, so $0' \in f(I)$.

Now, assume that $(f(x) *' f(y)) *' f(z) \in f(I)$ and $f(y) \in f(I)$,

it follows that $f(x * z) \in f(I)$, so $(x * y) * z, y \in I$.

Since I is an ARZ-ideal of $x, y, z \in I$ implies that $x * z \in I$.

It follows that $f(x * z) = f(x) *' f(z) \in f(I)$. Hence $f(I)$ is an ARZ-ideal of Y .

(4) Let J be an ideal of Y . Then $0' \in J$, we get that $0 = f^{-1}(0') \in f^{-1}(J)$.

For any $x, y \in X$, let $(x * y) \in f^{-1}(J)$ and $y \in f^{-1}(J)$. It follows that

$((f(x) *' f(y))) = f(x * y) \in J$ and $f(y) \in J$

Since J is an ideal of Y , we obtain that $f(x) \in J$. Consequently $x \in f^{-1}(J)$, proving that $f^{-1}(J)$ is an ideal of X .

(5) Let J be a subalgebra of Y and $x, y \in f^{-1}(J)$. Then $f(x) = a$ and $f(y) = b$ for some $a, b \in J$.

Thus $f(x * y) = f(x) * f(y) = a * b \in J$, as J is a subalgebra.

Hence $x * y \in f^{-1}(J)$.

(6) Let J be an ARZ-ideal of Y . Then $0' \in J$, we get that

$0 = f^{-1}(0') \in f^{-1}(J)$. For any $x, y, z \in X$, let $((x * y) * z) \in f^{-1}(J)$ and $y \in f^{-1}(J)$. It follows that

$((f(x) * f(y)) * f(z)) = f(((x * y) * z)) \in J$ and $f(y) \in J$.

Since J is an ARZ-ideal of Y , we obtain that $f(x * z) = f(x) * f(z) \in J$.

Consequently $x * z \in f^{-1}(J)$, proving that $f^{-1}(J)$ is an ARZ-ideal of X . ■

Theorem 2.5.3.

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism. Then:

- (1) $\ker f$ is an ARZ-ideal of X .
- (2) $\text{Im}(f)$ is a subalgebra of Y .
- (3) f is one to one if and only if $\ker f = \{0\}$.

Proof.

Assume that $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ is a homomorphism.

(1) It is clear that $\ker f \subseteq X$. Since $f(0) = 0'$, so $0 \in \ker f$. It follows that $\ker f \neq \emptyset$.

Let $((x * y) * z) \in \ker f$ and $y \in \ker f$. Then $f(((x * y) * z)) = 0'$, $f(y) = 0'$.

Since $0' = f(((x * y) * z)) = f(x * y) * f(z) = (f(x) * f(y)) * f(z)$,

but $f(y) = 0'$, then $(f(x) * f(z)) = 0'$ imply $f(x * z) = f(x) * f(z) = 0'$

i.e., $x * z \in \ker f$. Therefore $\ker f$ is an ARZ-ideal of X .

(2) Let $a, b \in \text{Im}(f)$, then there exist $x, y \in X$ such that $a = f(x)$ and $b = f(y)$, so $a * b = f(x) * f(y) = f(x * y) \in \text{Im}(f)$. This proves that $\text{Im}(f)$ is a subalgebra of Y . In general, $\text{Im}(f)$ may not be an ARZ-ideal.

(3) Suppose f is one to one, let $x \in \ker f$, thus $f(x) = 0$, since $f(0) = 0$, $f(x) = f(0)$ and f is one to one, then $x = 0$. Hence $\ker f = \{0\}$.

Conversely, suppose $\ker f = \{0\}$. Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $f(x) = f(y)$. Then we get that $f(x * y) = f(x) * f(y) = 0$ and $f(y * x) = f(y) * f(x) = 0$.

Thus $x * y, y * x \in \ker f$, so $x * y = 0 = y * x$ imply Proposition (1.2.4(5)),

$x = y$. Hence f is one to one. ■

Example 2.5.1.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2\}$. Define an operation $(*)$ on X by :

*	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1
2	2	2	0

Then, it can be easily shown that $(X ; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra.

Now,

Let f be the mapping from X to itself such that $f(0) = 0, f(1) = 0$ and

$f(2) = 1$, then we see that $\text{Im}(f) = \{0, 1\}$.

So,

$\text{Im}(f)$ is not an ARZ-ideal of X , since $1 \in \text{Im}(f)$ and $1 * 2 = 1 \in \text{Im}(f)$, but $2 \notin \text{Im}(f)$.

Remark 2.5.1.

Let f be a homomorphism from an ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$ to an ARZ-algebra $(Y ; * ', 0')$. Then:

(1) f is an epimorphism if and only if $\text{Im}(f) = Y$.

(2) f is an isomorphism if and only if the inverse mapping f^{-1} is an isomorphism.

Theorem 2.5.4.

Let I be a subalgebra of ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$. Defined the map

$f: (X ; *, 0) \rightarrow (X/I, \circ, [0]_I)$ by: $f(x) = [x]_I$, for all $x \in X$. Then f is epimorphism, we call f is **the natural homomorphism of X onto X/I** . Furthermore, $\ker f = I$.

Proof.

Let I be a subalgebra of ARZ-algebra X and $x, y \in X$. Since

$f(x * y) = [x * y]_I = [x]_I \circ [y]_I = f(x) \circ f(y)$, proving that f is a homomorphism.

Next, we will show f is surjective, let $[x]_I \in X/I$ and $x \in X$. Then $f(x) = [x]_I$, so f is surjective.

Finally, to show that $\ker f = I$, let $x \in \ker f$. We get that $[x]_I = f(x) = [0]_I$, then $x \sim 0$. It follows that $x * 0 \in I$ and $0 * x \in I$. By hypothesis $0 \in I$.

Hence, $x \in I$, this mean $\ker f \subseteq I$. To show that $I \subseteq \ker f$, let $x \in I$. Since I is a subalgebra of X , we have $0 \in I$. Thus $x * 0 \in I$ and $0 * x \in I$.

It follows that $x \sim 0$, so $[x]_I = [0]_I$. Since $f(x) = [x]_I = [0]_I$, then $x \in \ker f$. Accordingly, $\ker f = I$. ■

Theorem 2.5.5.

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; \circ, 0')$ be an ARZ-homomorphism, and I be an ARZ-ideal of X contain in $\ker f$. Let g be the natural homomorphism of X onto X/I , then there exists a unique homomorphism h of X/I onto Y such that $f = h \circ g$. Furthermore, h is an injective if and only if $I = \ker f$.

Proof.

Define the mapping $h : X/I \rightarrow Y$ by $h([a]_I) = f(a)$ for all $[a]_I \in X/I$. We first show that, h is well-defined.

Let $[a]_I, [b]_I \in X/I$ be such that $[a]_I = [b]_I$. We get that $a \sim b$, so $a * b \in I$ and $b * a \in I$. Since $I \subseteq \ker f$, $a * b \in \ker f$ and $b * a \in \ker f$.

Thus $f(a) \circ f(b) = f(a * b) = 0'$ and $f(b) \circ f(a) = f(b * a) = 0'$. From Proposition (2.2.2(3)), $f(a) = f(b)$. Hence h is well-defined.

We will show that h is a homomorphism. Let $[a]_I, [b]_I \in X/I$. Then $h([a]_I \circ [b]_I) = h([a * b]_I) = f(a * b) = f(a) \circ f(b) = h([a]_I) \circ h([b]_I)$, proving that h is a homomorphism.

Next, to show that $f = h \circ g$. For any $a \in X$, then

$$(h \circ g)(a) = (h(g(a))) = h([a]_I) = f(a). \text{ Hence } h \circ g = f.$$

Finally, if $h' : X/I \rightarrow Y$ is another function such that $f = h' \circ g$. Let $[a]_I \in X/I$.

The equation $h([a]_I) = f(a) = (h' \circ g)(a) = h'(g(a)) = h'([a]_I)$.

Thus $h([a]_I) = h'([a]_I)$, for all $[a]_I \in X/I$.

Now, we will show that h is injective if and only if $I = \ker f$. Suppose firstly that h is injective and $a \in \ker f$. Then $h([0]_I) = 0' = f(a) = h([a]_I)$ and since h is an injective, thus $[0]_I = [a]_I$.

It follows that $0 \sim a$, then $0 * a \in I$ and $a * 0 \in I$. By hypothesis, $0 \in I$. Hence, $a \in I$, this mean $\ker f \subseteq I$. This show that $\ker f = I$.

On the other hand, suppose that $\ker f = I$ and $[a]_I, [b]_I \in X/I$ such that

$h([a]_I) = h([b]_I)$. Then $f(a) = f(b)$, it follows that

$f(a * b) = f(a) \circ f(b) = 0'$. Thus $a * b \in \ker f$. Since $\ker f = I$, so $a * b \in I$.

Similarly, $b * a \in I$. Hence $a \sim b$, proving that $[a]_I = [b]_I$. This show that h is injective. This completes the proof. ■

2.6 Fundamental Theorems

Now, we state the first isomorphism of ARZ-algebras as the following theorem.

Theorem 2.6.1. (First Isomorphism Theorem)

If f be a homomorphism of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ into an ARZ-algebra $(Y; \circ, 0')$, then the quotient ARZ-algebra $X/\ker(\varphi)$ is isomorphic to $\varphi(X)$.

Proof.

Let $\varphi : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; \circ, 0')$ be a homomorphism and let

$K = \ker(\varphi) = \{a \in X \mid \varphi(a) = 0'\}$. We get that $X/K = \{[a]_K \mid a \in X\}$, where $[a]_K = \{b \in X \mid a \sim b\}$. From theorem (2.5.2(6)), we have $\ker(\varphi)$ is an ARZ-

ideal of X . Thus $(X/K; *, ', [a]_K)$ is an ARZ-algebra and $\varphi(X) = \{\varphi(a) \mid a \in X\}$.

Assume that $f: X/K \rightarrow \varphi(X)$ defined by $f([a]_K) = \varphi(a)$, where $[a]_K \in X/K$.

Let $[a]_K, [b]_K \in X/K$ be such that $[a]_K = [b]_K$. Then $a \sim b$,

it follows that

$a * b \in K$ and $b * a \in K$. Thus $\varphi(a) \circ \varphi(b) = 0' = \varphi(b) \circ \varphi(a)$, we get that $\varphi(a) = \varphi(b)$. Hence f is well-defined.

Let $[a]_K, [b]_K \in X/K$. We get that

$$\begin{aligned} f([a]_K * '[b]_K) &= f([a * b]_K) = \varphi(a * b) \\ &= \varphi(a) \cdot \varphi(b) = f([a]_K) \circ f([b]_K). \end{aligned}$$

This show that f is a homomorphism.

Let $[a]_K, [b]_K \in X/K$ be such that $f([a]_K) = f([b]_K)$. Then $\varphi(a) = \varphi(b)$,

it follows that $\varphi(a * b) = \varphi(a) \circ \varphi(b) = 0'$.

Thus $a * b \in \ker(\varphi) = K$.

Similarly, $b * a \in K$. We see that $a \sim b$, this mean $[a]_K = [b]_K$. Hence f is an injective.

Let $a \in \varphi(X)$. Then there exists $b \in X$ such that $a = \varphi(b)$ and $[b]_K \in X/K$. Thus $f([b]_K) = \varphi(b) = a$. Therefore f is a surjective, proving our theorem. ■

Remark 2.6.1.

If I is an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and J is an ARZ-ideal of I , then J is an ARZ-ideal of X . So, it follows that J is an ARZ-ideal of $I \cup J$ and $I \cap J$ is an ARZ-ideal of I .

Theorem 2.6.2. (Second Isomorphism Theorem)

If f be an ARZ-homomorphism of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ into an ARZ-algebra $(Y; \circ, 0')$. Let X be an ARZ-algebra and I, J be ARZ-ideals of X . If $I \cup J$ is an ARZ-algebra, then the quotient ARZ-algebras $I/(I \cap J)$ and $(I \cup J)/J$ are isomorphic.

Proof.

Let $\varphi : I \rightarrow (I \cup J)/J$ be a map by $\varphi(x) = [x]_J$ for all $x \in I$. It is obvious that φ is well defined.

Let $[x]_J \in (I \cup J)/J$. If $x \in I$, then $[x]_J = \varphi(x)$. If $x \in J$, then $[x]_J = [0]_J = \varphi(0)$. Thus φ is onto $(I \cup J)/J$.

Consider the equation $\varphi(x * y) = [x * y]_J = [x]_J \circ [y]_J = \varphi(x) \circ \varphi(y)$. Shows that φ is a homomorphism.

Now, let $x \in \ker(\varphi)$. Then we get $\varphi(x) = [0]_J$, so $[x]_J = [0]_J$. It follows that $x \in J$. Since $\ker(\varphi) \subseteq I$, so $x \in I \cap J$. Hence $\ker(\varphi) \subseteq I \cap J$.

On the other hand, let $x \in I \cap J$. Then $x \in J$. Thus $\varphi(x) = [x]_J = [0]_J$, so $x \in \ker(\varphi)$.

Hence $I \cap J \subseteq \ker(\varphi)$. Therefore, $\ker(\varphi) = I \cap J$. From theorem (2.5.5), immediately gives us that $I/(I \cap J) \cong (I \cup J)/J$. ■

Next, we state the third isomorphism theorem of ARZ-algebras.

Theorem 2.6.3. (Third Isomorphism Theorem)

Let $(X ; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-algebra and I, J be ARZ-ideals of X , with $I \subseteq J \subseteq X$. Then:

- (1) the quotient J/I is an ARZ-ideal of the quotient X/I , and
- (2) the quotient ARZ-algebra $(X/I)/(J/I)$ is isomorphic to X/J .

Proof.

(1) To show that J/I is an ARZ-ideal of X/I . It is clear that $J/I \subseteq X/I$ and $[x]_I \in J/I$.

Let $(([x]_I \circ [y]_I) \circ [z]_I) \in J/I$ and $[y]_I \in J/I$. Then $((x * y) * z) \in J$ and $y \in J$.

Since J is an ARZ-ideal of X , $x * z \in J$, so $([x]_I \circ [z]_I) \in J/I$. Therefore, J/I is an ARZ-ideal of X/I .

(2) Let $\varphi : X/I \rightarrow X/J$ defined by $\varphi([x]_I) = [x]_J$. Assume that $[x]_I = [y]_I$.

Then $x \sim y$ determined by I , that is $x * y, y * x \in I$. Since $I \subseteq J$, $x * y, y * x \in J$. Thus, $x \sim y$ determined by J , and hence $[x]_J = [y]_J$. Then $\varphi([x]_I) = \varphi([y]_I)$. Therefore, φ is well defined.

Next, to show that φ is onto X/J , let $[x]_J \in X/J$. If $x \in X$ and $x \notin J$, then $[x]_J = \varphi([x]_I)$. If $x \in J$, then $[x]_J = [0]_J = \varphi([0]_I)$. Hence φ is onto.

Consider the equation

$\varphi([x]_I \circ [y]_I) = \varphi([x * y]_I) = [x * y]_J = [x]_J \circ [y]_J = \varphi([x]_I) \circ \varphi([y]_I)$. Shows that φ is an ARZ-homomorphism.

Finally, to show that $\ker(\varphi) = J/I$, let $[x]_I \in \ker(\varphi)$. Then $\varphi([x]_I) = [0]_J$, so $[x]_J = [0]_J$. It follows that $x \in J$.

Now, we have $[x]_I \in J/I$.

Hence, $\ker(\varphi) \subseteq J/I$. Going the other hand, let $[x]_I \in J/I$. We get that $\varphi([x]_I) = [x]_J = [0]_J$, since $x \in J$. Thus $[x]_I \in \ker(\varphi)$, and hence

$J/I \subseteq \ker(\varphi)$. Consequently, $\ker(\varphi) = J/I$. By Theorem (2.5.5), $(X/I)/(J/I)$ is isomorphic to X/J . ■

Chapter Three

**On Fuzzy ARZ-ideals of ARZ-
algebra**

Chapter Three

On Fuzzy ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebra

3.1 Introduction

This chapter consists of five sections. The first section clarifies some basic definitions, examples, theorems and characteristics of fuzzy subalgebra. The second section includes some definitions, examples, theorems and preliminaries proprieties of fuzzy ideal. The third section includes some definitions, examples, theorems and preliminaries proprieties of fuzzy ARZ- ideal. The forth section discusses some definitions, examples, theorems and preliminaries proprieties of fuzzy homomorphism. The fifth section includes some definitions, examples, theorems and preliminaries proprieties of cartesian product fuzzy ideal.

3.2 Fuzzy Subalgebras of ARZ-algebras

In this section, we will discuss a new notion called fuzzy subalgebras of ARZ-algebras and study several basic properties which are related to fuzzy subalgebras.

Definition 3.2.1.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-algebra, a fuzzy subset μ of X is called a **fuzzy subalgebra of X** if for all $x, y \in X$,

$$\mu(x * y) \geq \min \{ \mu(x), \mu(y) \}.$$

Example 3.2.1.

Let $X = \{0, a, b, c\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	a	b	c
0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	0	0
b	b	c	0	c
c	c	0	0	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra . Define a fuzzy subset $\mu : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.7 & \text{if } x \in \{0, a\} \\ 0.3 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Condition: To prove for all $x, y \in X$, $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 0$, then

$$\mu(0 * 0) \geq \min\{\mu(0), \mu(0)\}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min\{0.7, 0.7\}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.7$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = a$, then

$$\mu(0 * a) \geq \min\{\mu(0), \mu(a)\}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min\{0.7, 0.7\}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.7$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = b$, then

$$\mu(0 * b) \geq \min\{\mu(0), \mu(b)\}$$

$$0.3 \geq \min\{0.7, 0.3\}$$

$$0.3 \geq 0.3$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = c$, then

$$\mu(0 * c) \geq \min\{\mu(0), \mu(c)\}$$

$$0.3 \geq \min\{0.7, 0.3\}$$

$$0.3 \geq 0.3$$

If $x = a$ & $y = 0$, then

$$\mu(a * 0) \geq \min\{\mu(a), \mu(0)\}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min\{0.7, 0.7\}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.7$$

If $x = a$ & $y = a$, then

$$\mu(a * a) \geq \min\{\mu(a), \mu(a)\}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min\{0.7, 0.7\}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.7$$

If $x = a$ & $y = b$, then

$$\mu(a * b) \geq \min\{\mu(a), \mu(b)\}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min\{0.7, 0.3\}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.3$$

If $x = a$ & $y = c$, then

$$\mu(a * c) \geq \min\{\mu(a), \mu(c)\}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min\{0.7, 0.3\}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.3$$

If $x = b$ & $y = 0$, then

$$\mu(b * 0) \geq \min\{\mu(b), \mu(0)\}$$

$$0.3 \geq \min\{0.3, 0.7\}$$

$$0.3 \geq 0.3$$

If $x = b$ & $y = a$, then

$$\mu(b * a) \geq \min\{\mu(b), \mu(a)\}$$

$$0.3 \geq \min\{0.3, 0.7\}$$

$$0.3 \geq 0.3$$

If $x = b$ & $y = b$, then

$$\mu(b * b) \geq \min\{\mu(b), \mu(b)\}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min\{0.3, 0.3\}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.3$$

If $x = b$ & $y = c$, then

$$\mu(b * c) \geq \min\{\mu(b), \mu(c)\}$$

$$0.3 \geq \min\{0.3, 0.3\}$$

$$0.3 \geq 0.3$$

If $x = c$ & $y = 0$, then

$$\mu(c * 0) \geq \min\{\mu(c), \mu(0)\}$$

$$0.3 \geq \min\{0.3, 0.7\}$$

$$0.3 \geq 0.3$$

If $x = c$ & $y = a$, then

$$\mu(c * a) \geq \min\{\mu(c), \mu(a)\}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min\{0.3, 0.7\}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.3$$

If $x = c$ & $y = b$, then

$$\mu(c * b) \geq \min\{\mu(c), \mu(b)\}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min\{0.3, 0.3\}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.3$$

If $x = c$ & $y = c$, then

$$\mu(c * c) \geq \min\{\mu(c), \mu(c)\}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min\{0.3, 0.3\}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.3$$

Then μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of ARZ-algebras X .

Theorem 3.2.1.

Let μ be a fuzzy subset of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X , then μ_t is a subalgebra of X , for any $t \in [0, 1]$.

Proof:

Assume that μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X . Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x \in \mu_t$ and $y \in \mu_t$, then $\mu(x) \geq t$ and $\mu(y) \geq t$, since μ is a fuzzy subalgebra, it follows that $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\} \geq t$ and we have that $x * y \in \mu_t$. Hence μ_t is a subalgebra of X . ■

Theorem 3.2.2.

Let μ be a fuzzy subset of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ_t is a subalgebra of X , for all $t \in [0, 1]$, then μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Proof:

Assume that μ_t is a fuzzy subalgebra of X .
suppose there exist $x', y' \in X$ such that, $\mu(x' * y') < \min\{\mu(x'), \mu(y')\}$.

Putting $t = (\mu(x * y) + \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\})/2$, then

$\mu(x * y) < t$ and $0 \leq t < \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\} \leq 1$, hence

$\mu(x) > t$ and $\mu(y) > t$, which imply that

$x \in \mu_t$ and $y \in \mu_t$. Since μ_t is a subalgebra, it follows that

$x * y \in \mu_t$ and that $\mu(x * y) \geq t$, this is also a contradiction.

Hence μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X . ■

Corollary 3.2.1.

Let μ be a fuzzy subset of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ is a fuzzy subalgebra, then for every $t \in \text{Im}(\mu)$, μ_t is a subalgebra of X , when

$\mu_t \neq \phi$.

Proof:

Similar to that of theorem (3.2.1).

Proposition 3.2.1.

The intersection of any set of fuzzy subalgebras of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is also fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Proof:

Let $\{\mu_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of fuzzy subalgebras of ARZ-algebra X , then for any $x, y \in X, i \in \Lambda$,

$$\begin{aligned} (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x * y) &= \inf(\mu_i(x * y)) \\ &\geq \inf(\min\{\mu_i(x), \mu_i(y)\}) \\ &= \min\{\inf(\mu_i(x)), \inf(\mu_i(y))\} \\ &= \min\{(\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x), (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. ■

Remark 3.2.1.

The union of two fuzzy subalgebras is not necessary to be fuzzy subalgebra as shown in the following example.

Example 3.2.2.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ and let $*$ be a binary operation defined by the table:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	0	1
2	2	2	0	2	0
3	3	1	3	0	3
4	4	4	2	4	0

It is clear that $(X; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra and $F_1 = \{1, 4\}$ and $F_2 = \{2, 3\}$ are subalgebras, but $F_1 \cup F_2 = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ is not subalgebra, since $2 \in F_1 \cup F_2$ and $4 \in F_1 \cup F_2$, but $2 * 4 = 0 \notin F_1 \cup F_2$.

Proposition 3.2.2.

Let $\{\mu_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of fuzzy subalgebras of ARZ-algebra X , the union of its is also fuzzy subalgebra, where $\mu_j \subseteq \mu_{j+1}$, for all $j \in \Lambda$.

Proof.

Let $\{\mu_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of fuzzy subalgebras of ARZ-algebra X , then for any $x, y \in X$, $i \in \Lambda$, such that $x, y \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i$ implies that $x \in \mu_i$ and $y \in \mu_j$, for some $i, j \in \Lambda$.

Furthermore, let $\mu_j \subseteq \mu_i$ implies that $x \in \mu_i$ and $y \in \mu_i$, for some $i \in \Lambda$.

Since μ_i is a fuzzy subalgebra of X , it follows that then

$$\mu_i(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu_i(x), \mu_i(y)\} \text{ for some } i \in \Lambda.$$

$$\text{Therefore, } (\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x * y) \geq \min\{(\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x), (\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(y)\}.$$

Hence, $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i$ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X . ■

3.3 Fuzzy Ideals of ARZ-algebras

In this section, we will discuss a new notion called fuzzy ideals of ARZ-algebras and study several basic properties which are related to fuzzy ideals.

Definition 3.3.1.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-algebra, a fuzzy subset μ of X is called a **fuzzy ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: , for all $x, y \in X$,

- (1) $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$,
 (2) $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x*y), \mu(y)\}$.

Example 3.3.1.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1
2	2	0	0	2
3	3	3	3	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra . Define a fuzzy subset $\mu : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.7 & \text{if } x \in \{0,1\} \\ 0.3 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Condition: It clear that $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$

To prove for all $x, y \in X$, $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x*y), \mu(y)\}$.

If $I_1 = \{0, 3\}$,

If $x = 0$ & $y = 0$, then

$$\mu(0) \geq \min\{\mu(0*0), \mu(0)\}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min\{0.7, 0.7\}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.7$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 3$, then

$$\mu(0) \geq \min\{\mu(0*3), \mu(3)\}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min\{0.7, 0.3\}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.3$$

If $x = 3$ & $y = 0$, then

$$\mu(3) \geq \min\{\mu(3*0), \mu(0)\}$$

$$0.3 \geq \min\{0.3, 0.7\}$$

$$0.3 \geq 0.3$$

If $x = 3$ & $y = 3$, then

$$\mu(3) \geq \min\{\mu(3*3), \mu(3)\}$$

$$0.3 \geq \min\{0.7, 0.3\}$$

$$0.3 \geq 0.3.$$

Then μ is a fuzzy ideal of ARZ-algebras X .

Lemma 3.3.1.

Let μ be a fuzzy ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and if $x \leq y$, then $\mu(x) \geq \mu(y)$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof:

Assume that $x \leq y$, then $x * y = 0$ and $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x*y), \mu(y)\} = \min\{\mu(0), \mu(y)\} = \mu(y)$. Hence $\mu(x) \geq \mu(y)$. ■

Theorem 3.3.1.

Let μ be a fuzzy subset of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ is a fuzzy ideal of X , then μ_t is an ideal of X for any $t \in [0,1]$.

Proof:

Assume that μ is a fuzzy ideal of X , by (1), we have $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$ therefore $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \geq t$ for $x \in \mu_t$ and so $0 \in \mu_t$. Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x * y \in \mu_t$ and $y \in \mu_t$, then $\mu(x * y) \geq t$ and $\mu(y) \geq t$, since μ is a fuzzy ideal, it follows that $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\} \geq t$ and we have that $x \in \mu_t$. Hence μ_t is an ideal of X .

Theorem 3.3.2.

Let μ be a fuzzy subset of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ_t is an ideal of X for all $t \in [0,1]$, then μ is a fuzzy ideal of X .

Proof:

Assume that μ is a fuzzy ideal of X .

We only need to show that (1) and (2) are true .

If (1) is false , then there exist $x' \in X$ such that $\mu(0) < \mu(x')$.

If we take $t' = (\mu(x') + \mu(0))/2$, then

$\mu(0) < t'$ and $0 \leq t' < \mu(x') \leq 1$, then $x' \in \mu$ and $\mu \neq \phi$.

As $\mu_{t'}$ is an ideal of X , we have $0 \in \mu_{t'}$ and so $\mu(0) \geq t'$.

This is a contradiction.

Now , assume (2) is not true ,then there exist $x', y' \in X$ such that ,

$$\mu(x') < \min \{ \mu(x' * y'), \mu(y') \}.$$

Putting $t' = (\mu(x') + \min \{ \mu(x' * y'), \mu(y') \})/2$, then

$\mu(x') < t'$ and $0 \leq t' < \min \{ \mu(x' * y'), \mu(y') \} \leq 1$, hence

$\mu(x' * y') > t'$ and $\mu(y') > t'$, which imply that

$$(x' * y') \in \mu_{t'} \text{ and } y' \in \mu_{t'}.$$

Since $\mu_{t'}$ is an ideal ,it follows that $x' \in \mu_{t'}$ and that $\mu(x') \geq t'$, this is also a contradiction .

Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of X . ■

Corollary 3.3.1.

Let μ be a fuzzy subset of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ is a fuzzy ideal, then for every $t \in Im(\mu)$, μ_t is an ideal of X , when $\mu_t \neq \phi$.

Proof:

The theorem (3.3.1) is used to the complete proof.

Proposition 3.3.1.

Every fuzzy ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Proof:

Since μ is fuzzy ideal of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then by Theorem (3.3.1) , for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is ideal of X . By Proposition (2.3.3), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is a subalgebra of X .

Hence μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X by Theorem (3.2.2.) . ■

Theorem 3.3.3.

Let A be an ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. Then for any fixed number t in an open interval $(0,1)$, there exists a fuzzy ideal μ of X such that $\mu_t = A$.

Proof:

$$\text{Define } \mu: X \rightarrow [0,1] \text{ by } \mu(x) = \begin{cases} t & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} .$$

Where t is a fixed number in $(0, 1)$.

Clearly, $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y \in X$.

If $y \notin A$, then $\mu(y) = 0$ and so $\mu(x) \geq 0 = \min\{\mu(x*y), \mu(y)\}$.

If $x*y \in A$, then clearly $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x*y), \mu(y)\}$.

If $x \notin A, y \in A$, then $x*y \notin A$, since A is ideal.

Thus $\mu(x) = 0 = \min\{\mu(x*y), \mu(y)\}$.

Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of X . It is clear that $\mu_t = A$. ■

Theorem 3.3.4.

Let A be a nonempty subset of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and μ be a fuzzy subset of X such that μ is into $\{0, 1\}$, so that μ is the characteristic function of A . Then μ is a fuzzy ideal of X if and only if A is an ideal of X .

Proof:

Assume that μ is a fuzzy ideal of X , since $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$, clearly we have $\mu(0) = 1$, and so $0 \in A$.

Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x*y \in A$ and $y \in A$, since μ is a fuzzy ideal of X , it follows that $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x*y), \mu(y)\} = 1$, and $\mu(x) = 1$.

This mean that $x \in A$, i.e., A is an ideal of X .

Conversely, suppose A is an ideal of X , since $0 \in A$,

$$\mu(0) = 1 \geq \mu(x), \text{ for all } x \in X.$$

Let $x, y \in X$,

If $x \notin A$, then $\mu(x) = 0$, and so $\mu(x) \geq 0 = \min\{\mu(x*y), \mu(y)\}$.

If $y \notin A$, and $x \in A$, then $(x * y) \notin A$ (since A is ideal).

Thus $\mu(x) = \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\} = 0$.

Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of X . ■

Proposition 3.3.2.

The intersection of any set of fuzzy ideals of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is also fuzzy ideal.

Proof:

Let $\{\mu_i / i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of fuzzy ideals of ARZ-algebra X , then for any $x, y \in X, i \in \Lambda$,

$$(\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(0) = \inf(\mu_i(0)) \geq \inf(\mu_i(x)) = (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x) \text{ and}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i(x) &= \inf(\mu_i(x)) \geq \inf(\min\{\mu_i(x * y), \mu_i(y)\}) \\ &= \min\{\inf(\mu_i(x * y)), \inf(\mu_i(y))\} \\ &= \min\{(\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x * y), (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(y)\}. \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

Remark 3.3.1.

The union of two fuzzy ideals is not necessary to be fuzzy ideal as shown in the following example.

Example 3.3.2.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ and let $*$ be a binary operation defined by the table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1
2	2	1	0	1
3	3	3	3	0

It is clear that $(X; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra and $I_1 = \{0, 1, 3\}$ and $I_2 = \{0, 3\}$ are ideals, but $I_1 \cup I_2 = \{0, 1, 3\}$ is not ideal, since $2 * 1 = 1 \in I_1 \cup I_2$ and $1 \in I_1 \cup I_2$, but $2 \notin I_1 \cup I_2$.

Proposition 3.3.3.

Let $\{\mu_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of fuzzy ideals of ARZ-algebra X . The union of its is also fuzzy ideal, where $\mu_j \subseteq \mu_{j+1}$, for all $j \in \Lambda$.

Proof.

Let $\{\mu_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of fuzzy ideals of ARZ-algebra X , then for any $x, y \in X$, $i \in \Lambda$, such that $x, y \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i$ implies that $x * y \in \mu_i$ and $y \in \mu_j$, for some $i, j \in \Lambda$. Furthermore, let $\mu_j \subseteq \mu_i$ implies that $x * y \in \mu_i$ and $y \in \mu_i$, for some $i \in \Lambda$. Since μ_i is a fuzzy ideal of X , it follows that then

$$\mu_i(x) \geq \min \{ \mu_i(x * y), \mu_i(y) \} \text{ for some } i \in \Lambda .$$

$$\text{Therefore, } (\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x) \geq \min \{ (\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x * y), (\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(y) \}.$$

Hence $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i$ is a fuzzy ideal of X . ■

3.4 Fuzzy ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebras

In this section, we will discuss a new notion called fuzzy ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebras and study several basic properties which are related to fuzzy ARZ-deals .

Definition 3.4.1.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-algebra, a fuzzy subset μ of X is called a **fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: , for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(3) \quad \mu(0) \geq \mu(x) ,$$

$$(4) \quad \mu(x * z) \geq \min \{ \mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y) \} .$$

Example 3.4.1.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1
2	2	0	0	1
3	3	3	3	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is ARZ-algebra . Define a fuzzy subset $\mu : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.7 & \text{if } x \in \{0,1\} \\ 0.3 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Solve: $\forall x, y, z \in X$

Condition: It clear that $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$

to prove $\mu(x * z) \geq \min \{ \mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y) \}$

If $I_1 = \{0, 3\}_2$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 0$, then

$$\mu(0 * 0) \geq \min \{ \mu((0 * 0) * 0), \mu(0) \}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min \{ 0.7, 0.7 \}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.7$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 3$, then

$$\mu(0 * 3) \geq \min \{ \mu((0 * 0) * 3), \mu(0) \}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min \{ 0.7, 0.7 \}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.7$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 3$ & $z = 0$, then

$$\mu(0 * 0) \geq \min \{ \mu((0 * 3) * 0), \mu(3) \}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min \{ 0.7, 0.3 \}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.3$$

If $x = 0$ & $y = 3$ & $z = 3$, then

$$\mu(0 * 3) \geq \min \{ \mu((0 * 3) * 3), \mu(3) \}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min \{ 0.7, 0.3 \}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.3$$

If $x = 3$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 0$, then

$$\mu(3 * 0) \geq \min \{ \mu((3 * 0) * 0), \mu(0) \}$$

$$0.3 \geq \min \{ 0.3, 0.7 \}$$

$$0.3 \geq 0.3$$

If $x = 3$ & $y = 0$ & $z = 3$, then

$$\mu(3 * 3) \geq \min \{ \mu((3 * 0) * 3), \mu(0) \}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min \{ 0.7, 0.7 \}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.7$$

If $x = 3$ & $y = 3$ & $z = 0$, then

$$\mu(3 * 0) \geq \min \{ \mu((3 * 3) * 0), \mu(3) \}$$

$$0.3 \geq \min \{ 0.7, 0.3 \}$$

$$0.3 \geq 0.3$$

If $x = 3$ & $y = 3$ & $z = 3$, then

$$\mu(3 * 3) \geq \min \{ \mu((3 * 3) * 3), \mu(3) \}$$

$$0.7 \geq \min \{ 0.7, 0.3 \}$$

$$0.7 \geq 0.3$$

Then μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebras X .

Proposition 3.4.1.

Let μ be a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and $x \leq y$, then $\mu(x) \geq \mu(y)$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof:

Assume that $x \leq y$, then $x * y = 0$, and

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(x * 0) &= \mu(x) \\ &\geq \min \{ \mu((x * y) * 0), \mu(y) \} \\ &= \min \{ \mu(x * y), \mu(y) \} \\ &= \min \{ \mu(0), \mu(y) \} \\ &= \mu(y). \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\mu(x) \geq \mu(y)$. ■

Theorem 3.4.1.

Let μ be a fuzzy subset of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X , then for any $t \in [0, 1]$, μ_t is an ARZ-ideal of X .

Proof:

Assume that μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X , by (3), we have

$\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$ therefore $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \geq t$ for $x \in \mu_t$ and so $0 \in \mu_t$. Let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $((x * y) * z) \in \mu_t$ and $y \in \mu_t$, then

$\mu((x * y) * z) \geq t$ and $\mu(y) \geq t$, since μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal, it follows that $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\} \geq t$ and we have that $x * z \in \mu_t$.

Hence μ_t is an ARZ-ideal of X .

Theorem 3.4.2.

Let μ be a fuzzy subset of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ_t is an ARZ-ideal of X for all $t \in [0,1]$, then μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X .

Proof:

Assume that μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X .

We only need to show that (3) and (4) are true. If (3) is false, then there exist $x' \in X$ such that $\mu(0) < \mu(x')$. If we take $t' = (\mu(x') + \mu(0))/2$, then $\mu(0) < t'$ and $0 \leq t' < \mu(x') \leq 1$, thus $x' \in \mu_{t'}$ and $0 \notin \mu_{t'}$. As $\mu_{t'}$ is an ARZ-ideal of X , we have $0 \in \mu_{t'}$ and so $\mu(0) \geq t'$. This is a contradiction.

Now, assume (4) is not true, then there exist x', y' and $z' \in X$ such that,

$$\mu(x' * z') < \min\{\mu((x' * y') * z'), \mu(y')\}.$$

Putting $t' = (\mu(x' * z') + \min\{\mu((x' * y') * z'), \mu(y')\})/2$, then

$$\mu(x' * z') < t' \text{ and } 0 \leq t' < \min\{\mu((x' * y') * z'), \mu(y')\} \leq 1,$$

hence $\mu((x' * y') * z') > t'$ and $\mu(y') > t'$, which imply that

$(x' * y') * z' \in \mu_{t'}$ and $y' \in \mu_{t'}$, since $\mu_{t'}$ is an ARZ-ideal, it follows that

$x' * z' \in \mu_{t'}$ and that $\mu(x' * z') \geq t'$, this is also a contradiction.

Hence μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X . ■

Corollary 3.4.1.

Let μ be a fuzzy subset of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal , then for every $t \in Im(\mu)$, μ_t is an ARZ-ideal of X , when $\mu_t \neq \phi$.

Proof:

Similar to that of theorem (3.4.1)

Proposition 3.4.2.

Every fuzzy ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Proof:

Since μ is fuzzy ARZ-ideal of an ARZ-algebra X , then by Theorem (3.3.1) , for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is ARZ-ideal of X . By Proposition (2.3.1), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is a subalgebra of X .

Hence μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of ARZ-algebra X by Theorem (3.2.2) . ■

Proposition 3.4.3.

Every fuzzy ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a fuzzy ideal of X

Proof:

Since μ is fuzzy ARZ-ideal of an ARZ-algebra X , then by Theorem (3.3.1) , for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is ARZ-ideal of X . By Proposition (2.3.2), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is a fuzzy ideal of X .

Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of ARZ-algebra X by Theorem (3.3.2) . ■

Theorem 3.4.3.

Let A be an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. Then for any fixed number t in an open interval $(0,1)$, there exists a fuzzy ARZ-ideal μ of X such that $\mu_t = A$.

Proof:

$$\text{Define } \mu: X \rightarrow [0,1] \text{ by } \mu(x) = \begin{cases} t & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} .$$

Where t is a fixed number in $(0, 1)$.

Clearly, $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y, z \in X$,

If $((x * y) * z) \notin A$, then $\mu((x * y) * z) = 0$ and so

$$\mu(x * z) \geq 0 = \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\}.$$

If $((x * y) * z) \in A$, then clearly

$$\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\}.$$

If $y \notin A$, $x * z \in A$, then $((x * y) * z) \notin A$, since A is ARZ-ideal.

Thus $\mu(x * z) = \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\} = 0$.

Hence μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X . It is clear that $\mu_t = A$. ■

Proposition 3.4.3.

Let A be a nonempty subset of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and μ be a fuzzy subset of X such that μ is into $\{0, 1\}$, so that μ is the characteristic function of A . Then μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X if and only if A is an ARZ-ideal of X .

Proof:

Assume that μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal in X , since $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$, clearly we have $\mu(0) = 1$, and so $0 \in A$.

Let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $(x * y) * z \in A$ and $(y) \in A$, since μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X , it follows that

$$\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\} = 1, \text{ and } \mu(y) = 1. \text{ This mean that } y \in A, \text{ i.e., } A \text{ is an ARZ-ideal of } X.$$

Conversely, suppose A is an ideal of X , since $0 \in A$, $\mu(0) = 1 \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y, z \in X$,

If $((x * y) * z) \notin A$, then $\mu(x * z) = 0$, and so

$$\mu(x * z) \geq 0 = \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\}.$$

If $y \notin A$, and $x * z \in A$, then $((x * y) * z) \notin A$, (since A is ARZ-ideal).

Thus $\mu(x * z) = \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\} = 0$.

Hence μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X . ■

Proposition 3.4.4.

Let μ be a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of a ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and let μ_{t_1} , μ_{t_2} be level ARZ-ideals of μ , where $t_1 < t_2$, then the following are equivalent.

E₁) $\mu_{t_1} = \mu_{t_2}$.

E₂) There is no $x \in X$ such that $t_1 \leq \mu(x) < t_2$.

Proof:

Assume that $\mu_{t_1} = \mu_{t_2}$, for $t_1 < t_2$ and that there exist $x \in X$ such that

$t_1 \leq \mu(x) < t_2$. Then μ_{t_2} is proper subset of μ_{t_1} , a contradiction.

Conversely suppose that there is no $x \in X$ such that $t_1 \leq \mu(x) < t_2$. It follows from $t_1 < t_2$, that $\mu_{t_2} \subset \mu_{t_1}$.

Let $x \in \mu_{t_1}$, then $\mu(x) \geq t_1$, and hence $\mu(x) > t_2$, because $\mu(x)$ does not lie between t_1 and t_2 .

Hence $x \in \mu_{t_2}$, this implies that $\mu_{t_1} \subset \mu_{t_2}$.

Therefore, $\mu_{t_1} = \mu_{t_2}$. ■

3.5 Homomorphism of ARZ-algebras

In this section, we will discuss a new notion called fuzzy ideals and fuzzy ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebras and study several basic properties which are related to fuzzy ideals and fuzzy ARZ-ideals.

Proposition 3.5.1.

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a homomorphism between ARZ-algebras X and Y respectively. An into homomorphic pre-image of a fuzzy subalgebra is also a fuzzy subalgebra.

Proof:

Let β a fuzzy subalgebra of Y and μ the pre-image of β under f , let $x, y \in X$, then we get

$$\begin{aligned}\mu(x * y) &= \beta(f(x * y)) = \beta(f(x) * 'f(y)) \\ &\geq \min\{\beta(f(x)), \beta(f(y))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}\end{aligned}$$

i.e., $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, This completed the Proof. ■

Proposition 3.5.2.

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a homomorphism between ARZ-algebras X and Y respectively. An into homomorphic pre-image of a fuzzy ideal is also a fuzzy ideal.

Proof:

Let β a fuzzy ideal of Y and μ the pre-image of β under f , then $\beta(f(x)) = \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$.

Since $f(x) \in Y$ and β is a fuzzy ideal of Y , it follows that

$\beta(0') \geq \beta(f(x)) = \mu(x)$, for every $x \in X$, where $0'$ is the zero element of Y .

But $\beta(0') = \beta(f(0)) = \mu(0)$ and so $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for $x \in X$.

Now, let $x, y \in X$, then we get

$$\begin{aligned}\mu(x) &= \beta(f(x)) \\ &\geq \min\{\beta(f(x) * 'f(y)), \beta(f(y))\} \\ &= \min\{\beta(f(x * y)), \beta(f(y))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}\end{aligned}$$

i.e., $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$, This completed the Proof. ■

Theorem 3.5.1.

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a homomorphism between ARZ - algebras X and Y respectively. An into homomorphic pre-image of a fuzzy ARZ-ideal is also a fuzzy ARZ-ideal .

Proof:

Let β a fuzzy ideal of Y and μ the pre-image of β under f , then $\beta(f(x)) = \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Since $f(x) \in Y$ and β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of Y , it follows that $\beta(0') \geq \beta(f(x)) = \mu(x)$, for every $x \in X$, where $0'$ is the zero element of Y . But $\beta(0') = \beta(f(0)) = \mu(0)$ and so $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for $x \in X$.

Now, let $x, y, z \in X$, then we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(x * z) &= \beta(f(x * z)) \\ &\geq \min\{\beta((f(x) *' f(y)) *' f(z)), \beta(f(y))\} \\ &= \min\{\beta(f(x * y) * z), \beta(f(y))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu(x * y) * z, \mu(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

i.e., $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y) * z, \mu(y)\}$, This completed the Proof. ■

Proposition 3.5.3.

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a homomorphism between ARZ- algebras X and Y respectively. For every fuzzy subalgebra μ of X with sup property, $f(\mu)$ is a fuzzy subalgebra of Y .

Proof:

By definition $\beta(y') = f(\mu)(y') = \sup\{\mu(x) \mid x \in f^{-1}(y')\}$, for all $y' \in Y$ ($\sup \emptyset = 0$).

We have to prove that $\beta(x' *' y') \geq \min\{\beta(x'), \beta(y')\}$,

for all $x', y' \in Y$.

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a homomorphism of ARZ-algebras with sup property, μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X with sup property and β the

image of μ under f . Since μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X , for any $x', y' \in Y$, let $x_0 \in f^{-1}(x'), y_0 \in f^{-1}(y')$ be such that

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(x_0) &= \beta(f(x_0)) = \beta((x')) = \sup_{x_0 \in f^{-1}(x')} \mu(x_0) \text{ and} \\ \mu(y_0) &= \beta(f(y_0)) = \beta((y')) = \sup_{y_0 \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(y_0), \text{ then} \\ \beta(x' * y') &= \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(x' * y')} \mu(t) \geq \min\{\mu(x_0), \mu(y_0)\} \\ &= \min\{\sup_{t \in f^{-1}(x')} \mu(t), \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(t)\} \\ &= \min\{\beta(x'), \beta(y')\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence β is a fuzzy subalgebra of Y . ■

Proposition 3.5.4.

Let $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a homomorphism between ARZ-algebras X and Y respectively. For every fuzzy ideal μ of X with sup property, $f(\mu)$ is a fuzzy ideal of Y .

Proof:

By definition $\beta(y') f(\mu)(y') = \sup\{\mu(x) \mid x \in f^{-1}(y')\}$, for all $y' \in Y$ ($\sup \emptyset = 0$). We have to prove that

$$\beta(x') \geq \min\{\beta(x' *' y'), \beta(y')\}, \text{ for all } x', y' \in Y.$$

Let $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a homomorphism of ARZ-algebras with sup property, μ is a fuzzy ideal of X with sup property and β the image of μ under f . Since μ is a fuzzy ideal of X , we have

$\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$. Note that $0 \in f^{-1}(0')$, where 0 and $0'$ are the zero elements of X and Y respectively. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} \beta(0') &= \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(0')} \mu(t) = \mu(0) \geq \mu(x), \text{ for all } x \in X, \text{ which implies} \\ \text{that } \beta(0') &\geq \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(x')} \mu(t) = \beta(x'), \text{ for any } x' \in Y. \end{aligned}$$

For any $x', y' \in Y$, let $x_0 \in f^{-1}(x'), y_0 \in f^{-1}(y')$ be such that

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(x_0 * y_0) &= \beta(f(x_0 * y_0)) = \beta((x' *' y')) \\ &= \sup_{x_0 * y_0 \in f^{-1}(x' *' y')} \mu(x_0 * y_0) \text{ and } \mu(y_0) = \beta(f(y_0)) = \beta((y')) \\ &= \sup_{y_0 \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(y_0), \text{ then} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta(x') &= \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(x')} \mu(t) \\
&\geq \min\{\mu(x_0 * y_0), \mu(y_0)\} \\
&= \min\{\sup_{t \in f^{-1}(x' * y')} \mu(t), \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(t)\} \\
&= \min\{\beta(x' * y'), \beta(y')\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence β is a fuzzy ideal of Y . ■

Theorem 3.5.2.

Let $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be an epimorphism between ARZ-algebras X and Y respectively. For every fuzzy ARZ-ideal μ of X with sup property, $f(\mu)$ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of Y .

Proof:

By definition $\beta(y') = f(\mu)(y') = \sup\{\mu(x) \mid x \in f^{-1}(y')\}$, for all $y' \in Y$ ($\sup \phi = 0$). We have to prove that $\beta(y') \geq \min\{\beta(x' *' y'), \beta(x')\}$, for all $x', y' \in Y$.

Let $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a homomorphism of ARZ-algebras with sup property, μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X with sup property and β the image of μ under f . Since μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X , we have

$$\mu(0) \geq \mu(x), \text{ for all } x \in X.$$

Note that $0 \in f^{-1}(0')$, where 0 and $0'$ are the zero elements of X and Y respectively. Thus $\beta(0') = \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(0')} \mu(t) = \mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$, which implies that $\beta(0') \geq \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(x')} \mu(t) = \beta(x')$, for any $x' \in Y$

For any $x', y', z' \in Y$, let $((x_0 * y_0) * z_0) \in f^{-1}((x' *' y') *' z')$, $y_0 \in f^{-1}(y')$ be such that

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu((x_0 * y_0) * z_0) &= \beta(f((x_0 * y_0) * z_0)) = \beta(((x' *' y') *' z')) \\
&= \sup_{((x_0 * y_0) * z_0) \in f^{-1}((x' *' y') *' z')} \mu((x_0 * y_0) * z_0) \text{ and} \\
\mu(y_0) &= \beta(f(y_0)) = \beta(y') = \sup_{y_0 \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(y_0), \text{ then} \\
\beta(x' *' z') &= \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(x' *' z')} \mu(t) \geq \min\{\mu((x_0 * y_0) * z_0), \mu(y_0)\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \min\{\sup_{t \in f^{-1}((x' * y') * z')} \mu(t), \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(t)\} \\
&= \min\{\beta((x' * y') * z'), \beta(y')\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of Y . ■

3.6 Cartesian Product of Fuzzy ideal

In this section , we will discuss , investigate a new notion called Cartesian product of fuzzy ideals, fuzzy ARZ-ideals and we study several basic properties which related to fuzzy ideals and fuzzy ARZ-ideals.

Proposition 3.6.1.

For a given fuzzy subset β of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, let R_β be the strongest fuzzy relation on X . If β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of $X \times X$, then $R_\beta(x, x) \leq R_\beta(0, 0)$, for all $x \in X$.

Proof:

Since R_β is a strongest fuzzy relation of $X \times X$, it follows from that, $R_\beta(x, x) = \min\{\beta(x), \beta(x)\} \leq \min\{\beta(0), \beta(0)\} = R_\beta(0, 0)$, which implies that $R_\beta(x, x) \leq R_\beta(0, 0)$. ■

Proposition 3.6.2.

For a given fuzzy subset β of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, let R_β be the strongest fuzzy relation on X . If R_β is a fuzzy ideal (fuzzy ARZ-ideal) of $X \times X$, then $\beta(x) \leq \beta(0)$, for all $x \in X$.

Proof:

Since R_β is a fuzzy ideal (fuzzy ARZ-ideal) of $X \times X$, it follows from (A), $R_\beta(x, x) \leq R_\beta(0, 0)$. Where $(0, 0)$ is the zero element of $X \times X$. But this means that, $\min\{\beta(x), \beta(x)\} \leq \min\{\beta(0), \beta(0)\}$ which implies that $\beta(x) \leq \beta(0)$. ■

Remark 3.6.1.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *, 0')$ be ARZ-algebras, we define $(*)$ on $X \times Y$ by: for all $(x, y), (u, v) \in X \times Y$, $(x, y) * (u, v) = (x * u, y * v)$. Then clearly $(X \times Y, *, (0, 0'))$ is an ARZ-algebra.

Proposition 3.6.3.

Let μ and β be fuzzy ideals of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. Then $\mu \times \beta$ is a fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$.

Proof:

Note first that for every $(x, y) \in X \times X$,

$$\begin{aligned} (\mu \times \beta)(0, 0) &= \min\{\mu(0), \beta(0)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\mu(x), \beta(y)\} \\ &= (\mu \times \beta)(x, y) . \end{aligned}$$

Now let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times X$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\mu \times \beta)(x_1, x_2) &= \min\{\mu(x_1), \beta(x_2)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\min\{\mu(x_1 * y_1), \mu(y_1)\}, \min\{\beta(x_2 * y_2), \beta(y_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{\mu(x_1 * y_1), \beta(x_2 * y_2)\}, \min\{\mu(y_1), \beta(y_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{(\mu \times \beta)(x_1 * y_1, x_2 * y_2), (\mu \times \beta)(y_1, y_2)\} \end{aligned}$$

Hence $(\mu \times \beta)$ is a fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$. ■

Proposition 3.6.3.

Let μ and β be fuzzy ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then $\mu \times \beta$ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of $X \times X$.

Proof:

Note first that for every $(x, y) \in X \times X$,

$$\begin{aligned} (\mu \times \beta)(0, 0) &= \min\{\mu(0), \beta(0)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\mu(x), \beta(y)\} \\ &= (\mu \times \beta)(x, y) . \end{aligned}$$

Now let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2), (z_1, z_2) \in X \times X$. Then

$$(\mu \times \beta)(x_1 * z_1, x_2 * z_2) = \min\{\mu(x_1 * z_1), \beta(x_2 * z_2)\}.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\geq \min \{ \min \{ \mu ((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), \mu (y_1) \}, \min \{ \beta ((x_2 * y_2) * z_2), \beta (y_2) \} \} \\
&= \min \{ \min \{ \mu ((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), \beta ((x_2 * y_2) * z_2) \}, \min \{ \mu (y_1), \beta (y_2) \} \} \\
&= \min \{ (\mu \times \beta) ((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), ((x_2 * y_2) * z_2), (\mu \times \beta) (y_1, y_2) \}
\end{aligned}$$

Hence $(\mu \times \beta)$ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of $X \times X$. ■

Theorem 3.6.1.

Let μ and β be fuzzy subsets of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ such that $\mu \times \beta$ is a fuzzy ideal (fuzzy ARZ-ideal) of $X \times X$. Then for all $x \in X$,

- (i) Either $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ or $\beta(0) \geq \beta(x)$.
- (ii) If $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, then either $\beta(0) \geq \mu(x)$ or $\beta(0) \geq \beta(x)$.
- (iii) If $\beta(0) \geq \beta(x)$, then either $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ or $\mu(0) \geq \beta(x)$.
- (iv) Either μ or β is a fuzzy ideal of X .
- (v) Either μ or β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X .

Proof:

(i) Suppose that $\mu(x) > \mu(0)$ and $\beta(y) > \beta(0)$, for some $x, y \in X$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
(\mu \times \beta)(x, y) &= \min \{ \mu(x), \beta(y) \} \\
&> \min \{ \mu(0), \beta(0) \} \\
&= (\mu \times \beta)(0, 0).
\end{aligned}$$

This is a contradiction and we obtain (i).

(ii) Assume that there exist $x, y \in X$ such that $\mu(x) > \beta(0)$ and $\beta(y) > \beta(0)$, then

$(\mu \times \beta)(0, 0) = \min \{ \beta(0), \beta(0) \} = \beta(0)$ it follows that

$$(\mu \times \beta)(x, y) = \min \{ \mu(x), \beta(y) \} > \beta(0) = (\mu \times \beta)(0, 0).$$

which is a contradiction. Hence (ii) holds.

(iii) is by similar method to part (ii).

(iv) Since by (i) either $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ or $\beta(0) \geq \beta(x)$, for all $x \in X$.

Without loss of generality we may assume that

$\beta(0) \geq \beta(x)$, for all $x \in X$, from (iii) it follows that either

$$\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \text{ or } \mu(0) \geq \beta(x).$$

If $\mu(0) \geq \beta(x)$, for any $x \in X$, then

$$(\mu \times \beta)(0, x) = \min\{\mu(0), \beta(x)\} = \beta(x).$$

Let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times X$, since $\mu \times \beta$ is a fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$, we have

$$(\mu \times \beta)(x_1, x_2) \geq \min\{(\mu \times \beta)(x_1 * y_1, x_2 * y_2), (\mu \times \beta)(y_1, y_2)\} \text{--- } (*)$$

If we take $x_1 = y_1 = 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \beta(x_2) &= (\mu \times \beta)(0, x_2) \\ &\geq \min\{(\mu \times \beta)(0, x_2 * y_2), (\mu \times \beta)(0, y_2)\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{\mu(0), \beta(x_2 * y_2)\}, \min\{\mu(0), \beta(y_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\beta(x_2 * y_2), \beta(y_2)\} \end{aligned}$$

This prove that β is a fuzzy ideal of X .

Now, we consider the case $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$.

Suppose that

$\mu(0) < \mu(y)$, for some $y \in X$. then $\beta(0) \geq \beta(y) > \mu(0)$. Since $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$, it follows that $\beta(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for any $x \in X$.

Hence

$$(\mu \times \beta)(x, 0) = \min\{\mu(x), \beta(0)\} = \mu(x), \text{ taking}$$

$x_2 = y_2 = 0$ in $(*)$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(x_1) &= (\mu \times \beta)(x_1, 0) \\ &\geq \min\{(\mu \times \beta)(x_1 * y_1, 0), (\mu \times \beta)(y_1, 0)\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{\mu(x_1 * y_1), \beta(0)\}, \min\{\mu(y_1), \beta(0)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\mu(x_1 * y_1), \mu(y_1)\} \end{aligned}$$

Which proves that μ is a fuzzy ideal of X . Hence either μ or β is a fuzzy ideal of X .

(v) $\mu \times \beta$ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of $X \times X$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (\mu \times \beta)(x_1, x_2) &\geq \min\{(\mu \times \beta)((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), ((x_2 * y_2) * z_2), \\ &(\mu \times \beta)(y_1, y_2)\} \text{--- } (**). \end{aligned}$$

If we take $x_1 = y_1 = 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta(x_2 * z_2) &= (\mu \times \beta)(0, x_2 * y_2) \\
&\geq \min\{(\mu \times \beta)(0, (x_2 * y_2) * z_2), (\mu \times \beta)(0, y_2)\} \\
&= \min\{\min\{\mu(0), \beta((x_2 * y_2) * z_2)\}, \min\{\mu(0), \beta(y_2)\}\} \\
&= \min\{\beta((x_2 * y_2) * z_2), \beta(y_2)\}
\end{aligned}$$

This prove that β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X .

Or taking $x_2 = y_2 = 0$ in (**), then

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu(x_1 * z_1) &= (\mu \times \beta)(x_1 * y_1, 0) \\
&\geq \min\{(\mu \times \beta)((x_1 * y_1) * z_1, 0), (\mu \times \beta)(y_1, 0)\} \\
&= \min\{\min\{\mu((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), \beta(0)\}, \min\{\mu(y_1), \beta(0)\}\} \\
&= \min\{\mu((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), \mu(y_1)\}
\end{aligned}$$

Which proves that μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X .

Hence either μ or β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X . ■

Proposition 3.6.4.

Let β be a fuzzy subset of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and let R_β be the strongest fuzzy relation on X , then β is a fuzzy ideal of X if and only if R_β is a fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$.

Proof:

Assume that β is a fuzzy ideal of X . By Proposition (3.6.1), we get,
 $R_\beta(0,0) \geq R_\beta(x,y)$, for any $(x,y) \in X \times X$.

Let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times X$, we have from (2) :

$$\begin{aligned}
R_\beta(x_1, x_2) &= \min\{\beta(x_1), \beta(x_2)\} \\
&\geq \min\{\min\{\beta(x_1 * y_1), \beta(y_1)\}, \min\{\beta(x_2 * y_2), \beta(y_2)\}\} \\
&= \min\{\min\{\beta(x_1 * y_1), \beta(x_2 * y_2)\}, \min\{\beta(y_1), \beta(y_2)\}\} \\
&= \min\{R_\beta(x_1 * y_1, x_2 * y_2), R_\beta(y_1, y_2)\}
\end{aligned}$$

Hence R_β is a fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$.

Conversely, suppose that R_β is a fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$,
 by Proposition (3.6.2)

$\beta(0) \geq \beta(x)$, for all $x \in X$, which prove (1).

Now, let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times X$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \min\{\beta(x_1), \beta(x_2)\} &= R_\beta(x_1, x_2) \\ &\geq \min\{R_\beta((x_1, x_2) * (y_1, y_2)), R_\beta(y_1, y_2)\} \\ &= \min\{R_\beta((x_1 * y_1), (x_2 * y_2)), R_\beta(y_1, y_2)\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{\beta(x_1 * y_1), \beta(x_2 * y_2)\}, \min\{\beta(y_1), \beta(y_2)\}\} \end{aligned}$$

In particular if we take $x_2 = y_2 = 0$, then

$$\beta(x_1) \geq \min\{\beta(x_1 * y_1), \beta(y_1)\}.$$

This proves (B) and β is a fuzzy ideal of X . ■

Theorem 3.6.2.

Let β be a fuzzy subset of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and let R_β be the strongest fuzzy relation on X , then β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X if and only if R_β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of $X \times X$.

Proof:

Assume that β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X . By Proposition (3.6.1), we get, $R_\beta(0,0) \geq R_\beta(x, y)$, for any $(x, y) \in X \times X$.

Let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2), (z_1, z_2) \in X \times X$, we have from (4) :

$$\begin{aligned} R_\beta(x_1 * z_1, x_2 * z_2) &= \min\{\beta(x_1 * z_1), \beta(x_2 * z_2)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\min\{\beta((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), \beta(y_1)\}, \min\{\beta((x_2 * y_2) * z_2), \beta(y_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{\beta((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), \beta((x_2 * y_2) * z_2)\}, \min\{\beta(y_1), \beta(y_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{R_\beta(((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), ((x_2 * y_2) * z_2)), R_\beta(y_1, y_2)\} \end{aligned}$$

Hence R_β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of $X \times X$.

Conversely, suppose that R_β is a fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$,

by Proposition (3.6.2)

$\beta(0) \geq \beta(x)$, for all $x \in X$, which prove (3).

Now, let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2), (z_1, z_2) \in X \times X$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \min\{\beta(x_1 * z_1), \beta(x_2 * z_2)\} &= R_\beta(x_1 * z_1, x_2 * z_2) \\ &\geq \min\{R_\beta(((x_1, x_2) * (y_1, y_2)) * (z_1, z_2)), R_\beta(y_1, y_2)\} \\ &= \min\{R_\beta(((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), ((x_2 * y_2) * z_2)), R_\beta(y_1, y_2)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$= \min\{\min\{\beta((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), \beta((x_2 * y_2) * z_2)\}, \min\{\beta(y_1), \beta(y_2)\}\}$$

In particular if we take $x_2 = y_2 = 0$, then

$$\beta(x_1 * z_1) \geq \min\{\beta((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), \beta(y_1)\}.$$

Hence, (4) and β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X . ■

Chapter Four
The ARZ-algebra and its
Application in Binary Coding and
Cryptography

Chapter Four

The ARZ-algebra and its Application in Binary Coding and Cryptography

4.1 Introduction

This chapter falls in to three sections. The first section states some basic definitions and examples ARZ-Valued Function. The second section includes some definitions, examples, theorems and preliminaries proprieties of ARZ-code. The third section states hybrid the ARZ-algebra and RC6 encryption, decryption algorithm, and key expansion algorithm, also it's include examples and system algorithm.

4.2 Basic Facts for Proposing the ARZ-Code

This section proposes some new definitions that are useful to build the ARZ-code as follows.

Definition4.2.1. (The ARZ-valued Function) .

Let A be a nonempty set and let X be the ARZ-algebra . A mapping $f: A \rightarrow X$ is called a ARZ- valued function(or ARZ- function) on A .

Definition 4.2.2. (A Cut Function of ARZ-Valued Function) .

A cut function of the **ARZ-valued function** f is a map $f_r : A \rightarrow \{0,1\}$, $r \in X$, such taht

$$f_r(x) = 1 \text{ if and only if } r * f(x) = 0 , \forall x \in A.$$

Obviously, f_r is the characteristic function. A cut subset A_r of A is the following subset of A : $A_r = \{ x \in A : r * f(x) = 0 \} \dots (4.1)$

4.3 The ARZ-Code (Binary Block-Code of ARZ-Function)

Definition4.3.1.

Let A be a set has n elements . Suppose a set $A = \{ 1,2, \dots, n\}$

and X is the ARZ-algebra . For each ARZ- valued function $f: A \rightarrow X$, a binary block-code of length n can be defined .

In other words, for each equivalence class \tilde{x} of $x \in X$, will correspond the codeword $w_x = x_1 x_2 \dots x_n$ with $x_i = j$, if and only if

$$f_x(i) = j, i \in A, j \in \{0,1\}.$$

This code is donated by V_x which is called the ARZ-code.

Definition 4.3.2. (Partial Order Relation).

Let V be a binary block-code . If $w_x = x_1 x_2 \dots x_n \in V$,

$w_y = y_1 y_2 \dots y_n$ are two codewords in V . On a code V ,a partial order relation is defined by

$$w_x \preceq w_y \text{ if and only if } y_i \leq x_i, i \in \{ 1,2, \dots, n\}.$$

Proposition 4.3.1.

Let (X, \leq) be a finite partial ordered set with the minimum element 0 . We define the following binary relation " $*$ " on X :

$$\begin{cases} 0 * x = 0 \text{ and } x * x = 0, \forall x \in X; \\ x * y = 0, \text{ if } x \leq y, \forall x, y \in X; \\ x * y = x, \text{ if } y < X, \forall x, y \in X; \\ x * y = 0 \text{ and } y * x \neq 0 \Rightarrow y * x = x, \text{ where } x \neq 0 \text{ can't be compared} \end{cases} \quad (4.1)$$

Then the algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is

- i. Commutative and implicative ARZ-algebra. Then the ARZ-code is a existed.
- ii. Not commutative and implicative ARZ-algebra. Then the ARZ-code is a existed.
- iii. Not commutative and not implicative ARZ-algebra. Then the ARZ-code is existed.
- iv. Commutative and not implicative ARZ-algebra. Then the ARZ-code is existed.

Proof:

Based on commutative and implicative definition, the proof is directly done.

Remark 4.3.1:

The ARZ-algebra with n elements can be denoted by C_n .

Definition 4.3.3. (The matrix Associated to the code V).

Let V be a binary block-code with n codewords of length n . The matrix $M_V = (m_{i,j})_{i,j \in \{1,2,\dots,n\}} \in M_n(\{0,1\})$ with the rows consisting of the codewords of V is called a matrix associated to the code V .

Theorem 4.3.1.

Suppose the relations in Equation (4.1) are holds. If the codeword

$\underbrace{11\dots1}_{n\text{-time}} \in V$ and let M_V be an upper triangular matrix with

$m_{ii} = 1$, for all $i = 1, \dots, n$. Then, there are

- i. A set A with n elements
- ii. An ARZ-algebra X and a ARZ- valued function $f: A \rightarrow X$ determines the ARZ-code V and the converse is true.

Proof:

Let $V = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n\}$. Based on Definition (1.3.1) of the lexicographic order results to, (V, \leq_{lex}) is a totally ordered set. This means that

$$w_1 \geq_{lex} w_2 \geq_{lex} \dots w_n \geq_{lex}.$$

This leads to $w_1 = \underbrace{11\dots1}_{n\text{-time}}$ and $w_n = \underbrace{00\dots01}_{n\text{-time}}$.

Now, one can get $w_1 \preceq w_i$, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ based on definition (4.3.2) of a partial order set (V, \preceq) on V . In a set (V, \preceq) , it is easy to see that $w_1 = 0$ is the zero element and w_n is a maximal element. A binary operation $*$ is defined on (V, \preceq) as given in proposition (4.3.1), this leads to $X = (V; *, w_1)$ is an ARZ-algebra and the ARZ-code V is isomorphic to ARZ-algebra C_n .

If suppose $A = V$ and the identity map $f: A \rightarrow V$ such that $f(w) = w$ as a ARZ- function, then f can be decomposed into family of maps

$$V_{cn} = \{ f_r : A \rightarrow \{0,1\} : f_r(x) = 1, \text{ if and only if } r * f(x) = 0, \\ \forall x \in A, r \in X \}$$

The family V_{cn} considers as a binary block-code V relative to the order relation \preceq .

This means that, if $w_k \in V, 1 < k < n$ and

$$w_k = \underbrace{00\dots0}_{k-1} x_{ik} \dots x_{in}, x_{ik} \dots x_{in} \in \{0,1\} \text{ then}$$

$$\begin{cases} w_k \preceq w_{ij} \text{ and } w_k * w_{ij} = 0 & \text{if } x_{ij} = 0 \\ w_{ij} \preceq w_k \text{ or } w_{ij} \text{ and } w_k \text{ can't be compared therefore } w_k * w_{ij} = w_k & \text{if } x_{ij} = 1 \end{cases}$$

Example 4.3.1.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as shown in table (4-1) :

Table 4-1: The ARZ-algebra

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	1
2	2	2	0	2
3	3	3	3	0

The ARZ-algebra $(X ; * , 0)$ is commutative and Implicative.

In other words,

Let $f: X \rightarrow X$ be a ARZ-function on X which is given by :

$$f = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{pmatrix}$$

And its cut subsets are

$$f_0 = f , f_1 = \{1\} , f_2 = \{2\} , f_3 = \{3\}$$

Then

Table 4-2: The ARZ- valued function f of ARZ-algebra

f_r	0	1	2	3
f_0	1	1	1	1
f_1	0	1	0	0
f_2	0	0	1	0
f_3	0	0	0	1

Thus $V = \{1111, 0100 , 0010, 0001\}$ is a binary block code that is called ARZ-code which satisfies the lexicographic order that is given in Definition (1.1.).

Now, if $V = \{ 1111, 0100 , 0010, 0001\} = \{ w_1 , w_2 , w_3 , w_4 \}$, then the ARZ-code V with $*$ operation that is computed in Table (4.3) is the ARZ-algebra.

In other words, one can get, based on Definition (1.1), $w_1 \preceq w_i , for$

$i = 2,3,4$. Also w_2 cannot be compared with w_3 and w_2 cannot be compared with w_4 , w_3 cannot be compared with w_1 and w_3 cannot

be compared with w_4 and w_4 cannot be compared with w_2 and w_4 cannot be compared with w_3

Table 4-3: The ARZ-algebra based on the ARZ- code V with $*$ operation.

*	w_1	w_2	w_3	w_4
w_1	w_1	w_1	w_1	w_1
w_2	w_2	w_1	w_2	w_2
w_3	w_3	w_3	w_1	w_3
w_4	w_4	w_4	w_4	w_1

Theorem 4.3.2.

Suppose the relations in Equation (4.1) are holds .

- i. V be a binary block-code with n codewords of length m and $n \neq m$, or
- ii. V be a block-code with n codewords of length n such that the codeword $\underbrace{11\dots1}_{n\text{-time}}$ is not in V , or
- iii. V be a block-code with n codewords of length n such that the matrix M_V is not upper triangular.

Then , there are

- i. a natural number $q \geq \max\{m, n\}$, and
- ii. a ARZ-function $f: A \rightarrow C_q$ such that the obtained block-code V_{C_n} contains the block-code V as a subset, where A is a set with m elements.

Proof:

Let V be a binary block-code $V = \{ w_1 , w_2 , \dots , w_n \}$, with codewords of length m . The codewords w_1 , w_2 , \dots , w_n lexicographic ordered is given by $w_1 \geq_{lex} w_2 \geq_{lex} \dots w_n \geq_{lex}$. Suppose $M \in M_{n,m} (\{0,1\})$ is an associated matrix, as given in Definition (4.3.3), with the rows w_1 , w_2 , \dots , w_n in this order .

It requires to extend the matrix M to a square matrix $\hat{M} \in M_q(\{0,1\})$ is an upper triangular matrix with $m_{ii} = 1, \forall i \in \{1,2,\dots,q\}$. First, the extension of a matrix M is done using proposition (4.3.2) which is proved in the following proposition .

Proposition 4.3.2.

If $M = (m_{i,j})_{\substack{i \in \{1,2,\dots,n\} \\ j \in \{1,2,\dots,m\}}} \in M_{n,m}(\{0,1\})$ is a matrix, its rows has

lexicographic ordered in the descending sense. Then, it is possible to find a matrix $\hat{M} = (\hat{m}_{i,j})_{i,j \in \{1,2,\dots,q\}} \in M_q(\{0,1\}), q = n + m$, such that \hat{M} is an upper triangular matrix, with $\hat{m}_{ii} = 1 \forall i \in \{1,2, \dots, q\}$ and M is a sub-matrix of a matrix \hat{M} .

Proof:

Let M be a matrix. It is possible to insert in the left side of M , a n new columns of the form $\underbrace{00\dots01}_n, \underbrace{00\dots10}_n, \dots, \underbrace{10\dots00}_n$, this inserting from the right to the left. This results a new matrix H with n rows and $m + n$ columns. In the bottom of the matrix H also adding the following m rows: $\underbrace{00\dots01}_n \underbrace{00\dots00}_m, \underbrace{00\dots001}_{n+1} \underbrace{01\dots00}_{m-1}, \dots, \underbrace{000\dots1}_{n+m-1}$, results a matrix \hat{M} . ■

Remark 4.3.2.

If the first line of the matrix \hat{M} is not $11 \dots 1_q$ then the row $11 \dots 1_{q+1}$ is inserted as a first row and the column $10 \dots 0_q$ as a first column.

On the matrix \hat{M} , applying theorem (4.3.1) results a ARZ-algebra X_q with q elements, namely $X_q = \{x_1, \dots, x_q\}$, with $x_1 = 0$ which is the zero of the ARZ-algebra X_q . It is also based on Theorem (4.3.1), one can

get a binary block-code V_{X_q} which is a ARZ-Code. Suppose the initial columns of the matrix M are columns in a new matrix \hat{M} that have positions

$i_{j_1}, i_{j_2}, \dots, i_{j_m} \in \{1, 2, \dots, q\}$, Let $A = \{x_{j_1}, x_{j_2}, \dots, x_{j_m}\} \subseteq X_q$. The

ARZ- function $f: A \rightarrow X_q$, $f(x_{j_i}) = x_{j_i}$, $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$ determines the binary block-code V_{X_q} such that $V \subseteq V_{X_q}$. ■

Example 4.3.2.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as shown in table (4-4) :

Table 4-4: The ARZ-algebra based on $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	2	0	3
3	3	3	0	0

The ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is commutative and not Implicative. In other words,

Let $f: X \rightarrow X$ be a ARZ-function on X which is given by :

$$f = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{pmatrix}$$

And its cut subsets are $f_0 = f$, $f_1 = \{1, 2, 3\}$, $f_2 = \{2\}$,

$f_3 = \{2, 3\}$. So, Table (4.5), shows the cut function f_r of the ARZ-valued function f of ARZ- algebra.

Table 4-5: The cut function
f_r of the ARZ-valued function *f* of ARZ- algebra with a set $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$.

<i>f_r</i>	0	1	2	3
<i>f₀</i>	1	1	1	1
<i>f₁</i>	0	1	1	1
<i>f₂</i>	0	0	1	0
<i>f₃</i>	0	0	1	1

Thus $V =$

$\{1111, 0111, 0010, 0011\}$ is a ARZ-code which is a binary block code.

Now based on the lexicographic order, this code can be rearranged by

$V = \{1111, 0111, 0010, 0011\} = \{w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4\}$ be a ARZ-code

which is a binary block code that has the lexicographic order. Based on

Definition (1.1), it is possible to form the associated matrix

$M_v \in M_{4,4}(\{0,1\})$ which is given by:

$$M_v = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Using Proposition (4.3.2), an upper triangular matrix D is constructed on

a matrix M_v by

$$D = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Now, a matrix \hat{M} is created by

$$\hat{M} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

So, the binary block-code $W = \{ w_1, w_2, \dots, w_8 \}$ whose codewords are the rows of the matrix \hat{M} , determines a ARZ-algebra $(X; *, w_1)$.

Let $A = \{ w_5, w_6, w_7, w_8 \}$ and $f: A \rightarrow X, f(w_i) = w_i \ i \in \{5,6,7,8\}$ be a ARZ-function which determines the binary block-code

$$U = \{ 1111, 0111, 0011, 0010, 1000, 0100, 0001 \}.$$

The ARZ-code V is a subset of the code U .

4.4 The Hybrid ARZ- RC6 encryption Scheme

This section discusses the RC6 method (algorithm) that consists of three parts, as follows.

4.4.1 Key Generation Process of The Hybrid ARZ-RC6 Scheme

The steps to generate the key of RC6 algorithm is given and explained in algorithm (4.1)

Algorithm (4.1): Generation Process of the Hybrid ARZ-RC6 Algorithm.

Input: Array $L[0, \dots, c-1]$ content words, c is number of words in key,
 r number of rounds,

$P_w = \lceil (e - 2) 2^w \rceil$, and $Q_w = \lceil (\varphi - 1) 2^w \rceil$, where $e=2.71828\dots$,

is an exponential number and $\varphi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} = 1.618033\dots$ is an golden

ratio **Output:** w -bit round keys S_1, \dots, S_{2r+4} .

Begin:

Step 1: Divided key into 4 blocks, where each block equal w , w is size of word ($w=32$) and L is ARZ-key word.

Step 2: $S_1 = P_w$

For $i=2$ to $2r+4$

$$S_i = S_{i-1} + Q_w$$

End For

Step 3: $A = B = 0$; is store values

$i = j = 1$; // counters

$v = 3 * \max\{c, 2r+4\}$; v is number time for change key and c number of word for key

Step 4: For $t=1$ to v

$\{ A = S_i = (S_i + A + B) \lll 3$, where \lll is shift and S_i is a value of A

$$B = L_j = (L_j + A + B) \lll (A + B), \text{ where } L_j \text{ is a value of } B$$

$$i \equiv i + 1 \pmod{(2r + 4)}$$

$$j \equiv j + 1 \pmod{c}$$

}

End

Example 4.4.1.1: Let $L = [8, 4, 12, 2]$ and $w = 4$. The parameters

P_w and Q_w are computed respectively by

$$P_w = [((e - 2) 2^w)] = 11, \text{ and}$$

$$Q_w = [((\varphi - 1) 2^w)], \text{ Where } \varphi = \frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2} = 1.618033989. \text{ So,}$$

$$Q_w = 10 \text{ and } S = [s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{2r+4}]. \text{ Thus, } s_1 = P_w = 11.$$

$$\text{Now, } s_i \equiv s_{i-1} + Q_w \pmod{2^w}, \text{ for } i=2, \dots, 6.$$

Therefore, S is $S = [11, 5, 15, 9, 3, 13]$. Let $c = 4$ which is a number of a word for key. The parameter v is computed by

$v = 3 * \max\{c, 2r + 4\} = 3 * \max\{4, 6\} = 18$, where v is number time for change key, with a round $r=1$.

Now, with $i = 1, s_1 = 7, S = [7, 5, 15, 9, 3, 13]$

$i = 2, s_2 = 11, S = [7, 11, 15, 9, 3, 13]$

$i = 3, s_3 = 1, S = [7, 11, 1, 9, 3, 13]$

$i = 4, s_4 = 13, S = [7, 11, 1, 13, 3, 13]$

$i = 5, s_5 = 5, S = [7, 11, 1, 13, 5, 13]$

$i = 6, s_6 = 4, S = [7, 11, 1, 13, 5, 4]$

$i = 1, s_1 = 11, S = [11, 11, 1, 13, 5, 4]$

$i = 2, s_2 = 13, S = [11, 13, 1, 13, 5, 4]$

$i = 3, s_3 = 11, S = [11, 13, 11, 13, 5, 4]$

$i = 4, s_4 = 4, S = [11, 13, 11, 4, 5, 4]$

$i = 5, s_5 = 3, S = [11, 13, 11, 4, 3, 4]$

$i = 6, s_6 = 13, S = [11, 13, 11, 4, 3, 13]$

$i = 1, s_1 = 7, S = [7, 13, 11, 4, 3, 13]$

$i = 2, s_2 = 10, S = [7, 10, 11, 4, 3, 13]$

$i = 3, s_3 = 9, S = [7, 10, 9, 4, 3, 13]$

$i = 4, s_4 = 8, S = [7, 10, 9, 8, 3, 13]$

$i = 5, s_5 = 15, S = [7, 10, 9, 8, 15, 13]$

$$i = 6, s_6 = 8, S = [7, 10, 9, 8, 15, 8]$$

One iteration can be done with s_1 through the following computations:

If $i = j = 1, A = B = 0$ and $v = 18$, one can compute

$$s_1 = (s_1 + A + B) \lll 3$$

$$= (11 + 0 + 0) \lll 3$$

$$= 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \lll 3$$

$$= 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 = 13$$

$$A = 13.$$

$$\text{Then, } S = [13, 5, 15, 9, 3, 13]$$

$$\text{Now, } l_1 = (l_1 + A + B) \lll (A + B \text{ mod } w)$$

$$= (8 + 13 + 0) \lll 13 \text{ mod } 4$$

$$= 21 \text{ mod } 16 \lll 7$$

$$= 5 \lll 1$$

$$= 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \lll 1$$

$$= 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 = 10$$

$$B = 10$$

$$\text{Now, } L = [10, 4, 12, 2]$$

$$i \equiv i + 1 \pmod{(2r + 4)}$$

$$\equiv 1 + 1 \pmod{6}$$

$$\equiv 1 + 1 = 2$$

$$j \equiv j + 1 \pmod{c} \equiv 1 + 1 \pmod{4} = 2.$$

Similarly , another iteration can be done.

4.4.2 Encryption Process of the Hybrid ARZ-RC6 Scheme

The encryption process of the hybrid ARZ-RC6 scheme is explained in algorithm (4.2) :

Algorithm 4.2: Encryption Process of the Hybrid ARZ-RC6 Algorithm

Input: Plaintext blocks A, B, C, D , number of

Rounds r and keys S_1, \dots, S_{2r+4} .

Output: Ciphertext blocks are A', B', C', D' .

Begin:

$$B' = B + S_1$$

$$D' = D + S_2$$

for $i=1$ to r do

{

$$t = B' * (2B' + 1) \lll \log w.$$

$$u = D' * (2D' + 1) \lll \log w.$$

$$A = ((A \oplus t) \lll u) + S_{2i}$$

$$C = ((C \oplus u) \lll t) + S_{2i+1}$$

$$(A, B', C, D') = (B', C, D', A)$$

}

$$A' = A + S_{2r+2}$$

$$C' = C + S_{2r+3}$$

Ciphertext blocks= $\{A', B', C', D'\}$.

End

Example 4.4.2.1: Suppose a plaintext is the word "Hi". Based on , the ASCII table , the decimal representation of the plaintext is $\{H,i\}=\{72,105\}$. Thus, the binary representation of the plaintext is

$$H=72= 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0$$

$$i = 105 = 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1$$

The binary strings divided into 4-blocks, where each block length equal 4 bit as follows:

$$A = 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0,$$

$$B = 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0,$$

$$C = 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0,$$

$$D = 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1.$$

Now, converting the blocks into decimal numbers by:

$$A = 4, \quad B = 8, \quad C = 6, \quad D = 9.$$

Now, the computation of A,B,C,and D are done as follows :

With the parameters $r = 1, w = 4, \text{mod } 2^w = \text{mod } 2^4 = 16$, the shift is $\log_2 w = 2$ and

$S = [12, 4, 13, 3, 12, 14]$ such that $s_1 = 12, s_2 = 4, s_3 = 13, s_4 = 3, s_5 = 12, s_6 = 14$, then

$$B' = B + s_1 = 8 + 12 = 20 \text{ mod } 16 \equiv 4$$

$$D' = D + s_2 = 9 + 4 = 13 \text{ mod } 16 \equiv 13$$

The values of t and u are computed by

$$t = B' (2B' + 1) \ll 2$$

$$= 4 (2 * 4 + 1) \ll 2$$

$$= 36 \text{ (mod } 16)$$

$$\equiv 4. \text{ The binary representation of 4 is } 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0.$$

By shifting two positions, the binary representation becomes 0 0 0 1. So, the decimal number of 0 0 0 1 is equal to 1. The value of t as follows:

$$t = 1 \text{ mod } 4 = 1 = t_{\text{mod}}$$

$$\text{Now, } u = D' (2D' + 1) \ll 2$$

$$= 13 (2 * 13 + 1) \ll 2$$

$$= 351 \text{ (mod } 16) \equiv 15. \text{ The binary representation of } 15 \text{ is } 1 1 1 1.$$

By shifting two positions, the binary representation becomes 1 1 1 1. So, the decimal number of 1 1 1 1 is equal to 15. The value of u as follows:

$$u = 15 \text{ mod } 4 = 3 = u_{\text{mod}}$$

$$A = (A \oplus t) \ll u_{\text{mod}} + s_3 \text{ (mod } 16)$$

$$= (0 1 0 0 \oplus 0001) \ll 3 + 13 \text{ (mod } 16)$$

$$= 0 1 0 1 \ll 3 + 13 \text{ (mod } 16)$$

$$= 1 0 1 0 + 13 \text{ (mod } 16)$$

$$= 10 + 13 \text{ (mod } 16) \equiv 7$$

$$C = (C \oplus u) \ll u_{\text{mod}} + s_4 \text{ (mod } 16)$$

$$= (01 1 0 \oplus 1111) \ll 3 + 8 \text{ (mod } 16)$$

$$= 1001 \ll 3 + 8 \text{ (mod } 16)$$

$$= 0 0 11 + 8 \text{ (mod } 16)$$

$$= 3 + 3 \text{ (mod } 16)$$

$$= 6 \text{ (mod } 16) \equiv 6$$

$$(A, B', C, D') = (B', C, D', A) = (4, 6, 13, 7)$$

$$(A, B', C, D') = (4, 6, 13, 7)$$

$$A' = A + s_5 = 4 + 12 = 16(\text{mod}16) \equiv 0$$

$$C' = C + s_6 = 13 + 14 = 27(\text{mod}16) \equiv 11$$

The ciphertext is $[A', B', C', D'] = [0, 6, 11, 7]$

4.4.3 Decryption process of the hybrid ARZ-RC6 scheme

The decryption process can be explained by the following algorithm.

Algorithm 4.3: Decryption Process of the hybrid ARZ-RC6 Algorithm

Input: Ciphertext blocks (A', B', C', D') , r is number of rounds, and

S_1, \dots, S_{2r+4} .keys.

Output: Plaintext blocks are A, B, C, D .

Begin:

$$C = C' - S_{2r+3}$$

$$A = A' - S_{2r+2}$$

for $i=r$ down to 1 do

{

$$(A, B', C, D') = (D', A, B', C)$$

$$u = D' * (2D' + 1) \ll \log w$$

$$t = B' * (2B' + 1) \ll \log w$$

$$C = ((C - S_{2i+1}) \gg \gg t) \oplus u$$

$$A = ((A - S_{2i}) \gg \gg u) \oplus t$$

}

$$D = D' - S_1$$

$$B = B' - S_2$$

Plaintext blocks = A, B, C, D .

End

Example 4.4.3.1. (Decryption process of the hybrid ARZ-RC6 algorithm)

Let the ciphertext is given by $[0, 6, 11, 7]$, namely

$$A' = 0, B' = 6, C' = 11, D' = 7$$

With $r = 1$ and $w = 4$, so

$$C = C' - s_6 = 11 - 14 = -3 \pmod{16} \equiv 13 \text{ and}$$

$$A = A' - s_5 = 0 - 12 = -12 \pmod{16} \equiv 4.$$

$$(A, B', C, D') = (D', A, B', C) = (7, 4, 6, 13)$$

$$(A, B', C, D') = (7, 4, 6, 13)$$

$$u = D'(2D' + 1) \lll 2$$

$$= 13(2 * 13 + 1) \lll 2$$

$$= 351 \pmod{16} \equiv 15. \text{ The binary representation of } 15 \text{ is } 1111.$$

By shifting two positions, the binary representation becomes 1111. So, the decimal number of 1111 is equal to 15. The value of u as follows:

Now, $u = 15 \pmod{4} = 3 = u_{mod}$. The parameter t is computed by

$$t = B'(2B' + 1) \ll 2 = 4(2 * 4 + 1) \ll 2$$

$$= 36 \pmod{16} \equiv 4. \text{ The binary representation of } 4 \text{ is } 0100.$$

By shifting two positions, the binary representation becomes 0001.

So, the decimal number of 0001 is equal to 1. The value of t as follows:

$$t = 1 \pmod{4} \equiv 1 = t_{mod}$$

$$C = ((C - s_4) \ggg t_{mod}) \oplus u$$

$$= ((6 - 3) \ggg 3) \oplus 15 = ((3) \ggg 3) \oplus 15$$

$$= 0011 \ggg 3 \oplus 15$$

$$= 1001 \oplus 1111$$

$$= 0110 = 6$$

$$A = ((A - s_3) \gg u_{mod}) \oplus t$$

$$= ((7 - 13) \gg 3) \oplus 1$$

$$= (10) \ggg 3 \oplus 1$$

$$= 1010 \ggg 3 \oplus 1$$

$$= 0101 \oplus 0001$$

$$= 0100 = 4$$

$$D = D' - s_2 = 13 - 4 = 9 \pmod{16} \equiv 9 \text{ and}$$

$B = B' - s_1 = 4 - 12 = -8 \pmod{16} \equiv 8$. So, the decryption of the ciphertext is $[A, B, C, D] = [4, 8, 6, 9]$.

The binary representation of A and B are 0 1 0 0 and 1 0 0 0 and for C and D are 0 1 1 0 and 1 0 0 1 respectively. The decimal numbers are 72 and 105. So, the Plaintext is Hi.

4.5 The ARZ-Algebra for Image Encryption Scheme

The image encryption scheme using the ARZ-algebra implemented using algorithm (4.4).

4.5.1 The image encryption process using the ARZ-algebra

This section explains biometric encryption by ARZ-algebra and RC6 algorithm. ARZ-algebra used to key generated and applied RC6 to attain ciphertext. Input of system is text or biometric image. Output of the system is image or text encryption. The steps of system to get on ciphertext include:

- Changing the size of image into 100×100 .
- Changing class image into double; where this class content large size of number with real number
- After converting the pixels of image into bits; these bits are divided into blocks; where each block length is 128 bits in RC6 .
- Creating ARZ-algebra as its explained in chapter two, then generating a shared secret random key and computing xor between two keys.
- Expansion key according RC6-key expansion, where need r key and r is number of round.
- Encryptions bit-blocks by using ARZ-RC6 encryption algorithm, where output is decimal blocks and each block encryption by same algorithm.
- Convert decimal blocks into binary bits.
- Convert binary bits into pixel to give image encryption.
- The output is encryption image with same size of input image.

Algorithm 4.4: the ARZ-algebra for image encryption algorithm

Input: Biometric image

Output: Encryption image

Begin:

Step1: resize input image into size $(100 * 100)$.

Step 2: convert class image into double class (large class).

Step 3: convert pixels of image into binary bits .

Step 4: divided binary bits into blocks, where each blocks length equal 128 bits.

Step 5: generated a shared secret key by using ARZ-algebra.

Step 6: created a shared secret random key.

Step 7: xor operation between ARZ-algebra key and random key.

Step 8: expansion key by using Algorithm (4.1).

Step 9: encryption the blocks using the ARZ-RC6 algorithm (4.2)

Step 10: converting blocks into binary bits.

Step 11: converting binary bits into pixels.

Step 12: storing pixels into encryption image .

End

4.5.2 The image Decryption Process using the ARZ-algebra

This section explains biometric decryption by ARZ-algebra and RC6 algorithm. ARZ-algebra used to key generated and applied RC6 decryption to attained plaintext. Input of system is ciphertext or cipher biometric image. Output of the system is original image or text. The steps of system to get on plaintext include :

- Converting pixel image into binary bits.
- After converting pixels of image into bits; these bits are divided into blocks; where each block length is 128 bits in RC6 .
- Creating ARZ-algebra as its explained in chapter two, then generating a shared secret random key and compute xor between two keys.
- Expansion key according RC6-key expansion, where need r key and r is number of round.
- Decryption bit-blocks by using ARZ-RC6 decryption algorithm, where output is decimal blocks and each block decryption by same algorithm.
- Converting decimal blocks into binary bits.
- Converting binary bits into pixel to give image encryption.
- Sort pixels into image to give original image.

- Applying some measures such as SNR, PSNR, MSE and RMSE, where the quality of measures for SNR, MSE, RMSE is equal zero and PSNR is equal inf.

The output is encryption image with same size of input image.

Algorithm 4.5: the ARZ-algebra for image decryption algorithm

Input: Encryption image

Output: Original image

Begin:

Step 1: convert pixels to binary bits .

Step 2: divided binary bits into blocks, where each blocks length equal 128 bits.

Step 3: generated a shared secret key by using ZAR-algebra.

Step 4: created a shared secret random key.

Step 5: xor operation between ARZ-algebra key and random key.

Step 6: expansion key by using algorithm (3.1).

Step 7: decryption of blocks by using algorithm (3.3)

Step 8: converting blocks into binary bits.

Step 9: converting binary bits into pixels.

Step 10: storing pixels into image to give original image .

Step 11: applying some measures such as SNR, MSE.

End

Figure 4-1: Flowchart of ARZ-Algebra Method.

Chapter Five

The Implementation Results

Chapter Five

The Implementation Results

5.1 Introduction

This chapter represents the results of the encryption biometric data. Using ORL database, CMU AMP Face Database, MMI Face Database, Faces94 Database and HZ Face Database, implemented approaches are explained for both training and testing phases. All the implemented approaches presented in this dissertation were developed, trained and tested by carrying out programs written by MATLAB R2015b.

5.2 Face Database

This section explains face database as follows:

5.2.1 ORL Database

The ORL database includes 40 persons. There are 10 images per person. Total number of images 400 image in database, the images are taken at different times and contain various expressions (opened /closed eyes, smiling/not smiling) and facial details (glasses or no glasses). The size of each the image is 92×112 pixels with 256 gray levels. The experiment was performed using ORL database with 5 training and 5 testing images per person [48] as shown in Figure(5.1).

Figure 5-1: Examples images of the ORL database

5.2.2 CMU AMP Face Database

The CMU AMP Face database includes 13 persons, each with 75 images. We collected these face images in the same lighting condition, and only allow human expression changes. The size of each image is 64×64 pixels with 256 gray levels. The experiment was performed with 37 training and 37 testing images per person.

Figure 5-2: Examples images of the CMU AMP database

5.2.3 MMI Face Database

The MMI facial expression database holds over 2000 videos and over 500 images of about 50 subjects displaying various facial expressions. The database have includes 19 different faces of students and research staff

members of (4400 female), ranging in age from 19 to 62, having either a European, Asian, or South American ethnic background .The size of each the image is 720x576 pixels [50] . The experiment is implemented using MMI face database as shown in Figure (5.3).

Figure 5-3: Examples images of the IMM Face database

5.2.4 Faces94 Database

The faces94 database includes Number of individuals 153 image resolution 180×200 pixels (portrait format) directories females (20), males (113), male staff (20) contains images of males and females subjects in separate directories with a green background. The experiment is performed using face94 database with 9 training and 9 testing images per person. { faces94.zip (18.8 MBytes) } [49] as show in figure (5.4).

Figure 5-4: Examples images of the Faces94 database

5.2.5 HZ face Database

The HZ database includes 8 persons. There are 8 images per person. Total number of images 64 image in database .The images are taken at different times and contain various expressions (opened/closed eyes, smiling/not smiling, surprised/ not surprised) and facial details (glasses or no glasses). In this experiment, the camera type Nikoa (D610) was used and shutter speed with 1=160 and it was 5:6 lens aperture and fumbling 160 and its photic source is natural and it was the background of the image used a white board.The size of each the image is 336×480 pixels. The experiment performed using the HZ database with 4 training and 4 testing images per person as shown in Figure (5.5).

Figure 5-5: Examples images of the HZ database

5.2.6 Iris System Database

Using two databases :The first database IITD contains 240 persons, for each one there are 10 iris images, five for the right eye and five for the left eye except persons 1-13, 55,27 and 65 left eye image only. They are 167 males and 48 females only. The images bitmap format and taken in a closed environment for students and staff .The size of each image is 320 x 240 pixels. Second database was CASIA v4.0. Intervals are also used to test present work . The CASIA image catches in a gray scale in the JPEG format with 8 bits[51] as shown in Figure (5.6).

Samples from IITD

Samples from CASIA interval v4

Figure 5-6: Samples from different Iris image database.

5.3 ARZ-RC6 Scheme Example

In this section explain applied ARZ-RC6 scheme as follows:

Example 5.3.1 (Key Generation).

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2\}$ be a ARZ-algebra with the following tables:

$$m_1 =$$

*	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0
2	2	0	0

$$m_2 =$$

*	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0
2	2	1	0

$$m_3 =$$

*	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1
2	2	2	0

$$m_4 =$$

*	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	1	0	2
2	2	0	0

Then summation of tables are:

$$M =$$

*	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	4	0	3
2	8	3	0

User key (M) in binary = $L =$

[0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0
 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 1
 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
 0].

Divided key into blocks, where each block length equal 16 bit as follows:

$l_1 = (1:16) = [0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0]$.

$l_2 = (17:32) = [0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0]$.

$l_3 = (33:48) = [0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 1]$.

$l_4 = (49:64) = [0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 1]$.

Now, convert L into decimal numbers, $L = [0, 4, 3, 2051]$. The parameters $w = 16$, P_w and Q_w are computed respectively by

$P_w = [(e - 2) 2^w] = 47073$, where $Q_w = \text{Odd}((\infty - 1) 2^w)$, where

$$\varphi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} = 1.618033 \dots$$

$$Q_w = \lceil ((\varphi - 1) 2^w) \rceil, \text{ Where } \varphi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} = 1.618033989$$

$$\text{So, } Q_w = 40503, S = [s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{2r+4}].$$

$$\text{So, } s_1 = P_w = 47073. \text{ Now, } s_i = s_{i-1} + Q_w \pmod{2^w}, \text{ for } i=2, \dots, 6,$$

where $\text{mod} 2^w = 65536$ are computed by

$S = [47073, 22041, 62544, 37512, 12480, 52983]$. Let $c = 4$ which is a number of a word for key.

Now, $v = 3 * \max\{c, 2r + 4\} = 3 * \max\{4, 6\} = 18$, where v is number time for change key, with a round $r=1$.

$$i = 1, s_1 = 48909, S = [48909, 22041, 62544, 37512, 12480, 52983]$$

$$i = 2, s_2 = 39444, S = [48909, 39444, 62544, 37512, 12480, 52983]$$

$$i = 3, s_3 = 32818, S = [48909, 39444, 32818, 37512, 12480, 52983]$$

$$i = 4, s_4 = 53408, S = [48909, 39444, 32818, 53408, 12480, 52983]$$

$$i = 5, s_5 = 2774, S = [48909, 39444, 32818, 53408, 2774, 52983]$$

$$i = 6, s_6 = 2369, S = [48909, 39444, 32818, 53408, 2774, 2369]$$

$$i = 1, s_1 = 53626, S = [53626, 39444, 32818, 53408, 2774, 2369]$$

$$i = 2, s_2 = 45832, S = [53626, 45832, 32818, 53408, 2774, 2369]$$

$$i = 3, s_3 = 30491, S = [53626, 45832, 30491, 53408, 2774, 2369]$$

$$i = 4, s_4 = 50528, S = [53626, 45832, 30491, 50528, 2774, 2369]$$

$$i = 5, s_5 = 36352, S = [53626, 45832, 30491, 50528, 36352, 2369]$$

$$i = 6, s_6 = 24516, S = [53626, 45832, 30491, 50528, 36352, 24516]$$

$$i = 1, s_1 = 36459, S = [36459, 45832, 30491, 50528, 36352, 24516]$$

$$i = 2, s_2 = 2620, S = [36459, 2620, 30491, 50528, 36352, 24516]$$

$$i = 3, s_3 = 61662, S = [36459, 2620, 61662, 50528, 36352, 24516]$$

$$i = 4, s_4 = 64837, S = [36459, 2620, 61662, 64837, 36352, 24516]$$

$$i = 5, s_5 = 16861, S = [36459, 2620, 61662, 64837, 16861, 24516]$$

$$i = 6, s_6 = 57792, S = [36459, 2620, 61662, 64837, 16861, 57792]$$

One iteration can be done with s_1 through the following computations:

If $i = j = 1, A = B = 0$ and $v = 18$, one can compute

$$s_1 = (s_1 + A + B) \lll 3$$

$$= (47073 + 0 + 0) \lll 3$$

$$= 47073 \bmod 65536 \lll 3$$

$$= 47073 \lll 3$$

$$= 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \lll 3$$

$$= 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 = 48909$$

thus, $A = 48909$.

$$\text{Then, } S = [48909, 22041, 62544, 37512, 12480, 52983]$$

$$\text{Now, } l_1 = (l_1 + A + B) \lll A + B \pmod{w}$$

$$\equiv (0 + 48909 + 0) \lll 7$$

$$= 48909 \lll 48909 \pmod{16}$$

$$\equiv 48909 \lll 1$$

$$= 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \lll 1$$

= 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 1

= 32283 ,so $B = 32283$.

$L = [32283, 4, 3, 2051]$

$$i \equiv i+1 \pmod{2r+4}$$

$$\equiv 1+1 \pmod{6} \equiv 2$$

$j \equiv j+1 \pmod{c} \equiv 1+1 \pmod{4} \equiv 2$. Other iterations can be done in similar way .

(Encryption) Suppose a plaintext is the sentence "The World is Beautiful_9". Based on the ASCII Table , the decimal representation of the plaintext in character is {T,h,e, ,W,o,r,l,d, ,i,s, ,B,e,a,u,t,i,f,u,l,_,9}

plaintext in decimal= { 84, 104, 101, 32, 87, 111, 114, 108, 100, 32, 105, 115, 32, 66, 101, 97, 117, 116, 105, 102, 117, 108, 95, 57}.

Thus, the binary representation of the plaintext is

binary = [

0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0,

0 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0,

0 1 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 1,

0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 0,

0 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0,

0 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 1,

0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0,

0 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 1,

0 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 0 0,
 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0,
 0 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 0,
 0 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1]

Take 4-blocks for encryption, where each block length equal 16 bits, and repetition the process for all binary string as follows:

$$A = [0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]$$

$$B = [0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]$$

$$C = [0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1]$$

$$D = [0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0]$$

Converting these blocks into decimal number:

$$A = 21608, \quad B = 25888, \quad C = 22383, \quad D = 29292$$

Now, the computation of $A, B, C,$ and D are done as follows :

With $r = 1, w = 16, \text{mod}2^w = \text{mod}2^{16} = 65536, \log_2 w=4$ (shift)
and

$S = [36459, 2620, 61662, 64837, 16861, 57792]$, where

$$s_1 = 36459, s_2 = 2620, s_3 = 61662, s_4 = 64837, s_5 = 16861,$$

$$s_6 = 57792.$$

$$B' = B + s_1 = 25888 + 36459 = 62347 \pmod{65536} \equiv 62347,$$

and

$$D' = D + s_2 = 29292 + 2620 = 31912 \pmod{65536} \equiv 31912$$

The values of t and u are computed by

$$t = B'(2B' + 1) \lll 4$$

$$= 62347 (2 * 62347 + 1) \lll 4$$

$$= 7774359165 \pmod{65536} \equiv 20093. \text{ The binary representation of } 20093 \text{ is } 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1$$

By shifting four positions, the binary representation becomes

$$1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0.$$

So, the decimal number of $1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0$
 $1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0$ is equal to 59348.

The value of t as follows:

$$t = 59348 \pmod{16} \equiv 4 = t_{mod}$$

$$u = D'(2D' + 1) \lll 4$$

$$= 31912 (2 * 31912 + 1) \lll 4$$

$$= 2036783400 \pmod{65536} \equiv 55592$$

Convert 55592 into binary : $1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1$
 $0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0$

Shift four position, the above binary bits become: $1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0$

$$1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1$$

Convert the binary into decimal: 37517

$$u = 37517 \pmod{16} \equiv 13 = u_{mod}$$

$$A = (A \oplus t) \lll u_{mod} + s_3$$

$$= (21608 \oplus 59348) \lll 13 + 61662$$

$$= 46012 \lll 13 + 61662$$

$$= 1\ 0\ 1\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 1\ 1\ 0\ 1\ 1\ 1\ 1\ 0\ 0 \lll 13 + 61662$$

$$= 1\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 1\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 1\ 1\ 0\ 1\ 1\ 1 + 61662 \pmod{65536}$$

$$= 38519 + 61662 \pmod{65536}$$

$$= 100181 \pmod{65536} \equiv 34645$$

$$C = (C \oplus u) \lll t_{\text{mod}} + s_4$$

$$= (22383 \oplus 37517) \lll 4 + 64837$$

$$= 50658 \lll 4 + 64837$$

$$= 1\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 1\ 1\ 1\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0 \lll 4 + 64837$$

$$= 0\ 1\ 0\ 1\ 1\ 1\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 1\ 1\ 0\ 0 + 64837 \pmod{65536}$$

$$= 24108 + 64837 \pmod{65536}$$

$$= 88945 \pmod{65536} \equiv 23409$$

$$(A, B', C, D') = (B', C, D', A) = (62347, 23409, 31912, 34645),$$

namely

$$(A, B', C, D') = (62347, 23409, 31912, 34645)$$

One loop:

$$A' = A + s_5 = 62347 + 16861 = 79208 \pmod{65536} \equiv 13672$$

$$C' = C + s_6 = 31912 + 57792 = 89704 \pmod{65536} \equiv 24168$$

The ciphertext is $[A', B', C', D'] = [13672, 23409, 24168, 34645]$

Block1 = $[13672, 23409, 24168, 34645]$,

The remainder blocks encryption by same procedure of block1, where encryption for the remainder blocks are:

$Block2 = [14779, 10403, 20829, 4883]$ and

$Block3 = [14766, 14857, 19253, 40738]$.

Decryption Process:

$Block1 = [13672, 23409, 24168, 34645]$, one can determine the values.

$A' = 13672, B' = 23409, C' = 24168$ and $D' = 34645$

$C = C' - s_6 = 24168 - 57792 = -33624 \pmod{65536} \equiv 31912$ and

$A = A' - s_5 = 13672 - 16861 = -3189 \pmod{65536} \equiv 62347$.

Thus, $(A', B', C', D') = (D', A, B', C) = (34645, 62347, 23409, 31912)$

$(A, B', C, D') = (34645, 62347, 23409, 31912)$

$u = D' (2D' + 1) \lll 4$

$= 31912 (2 * 31912 + 1) \lll 4$

$= 2036783400 \pmod{65536} \equiv 55592$. The binary representation of 55592 is 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0.

By shifting four positions, the binary representation becomes

1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 0 1. So, the decimal number of 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 is equal to 37517. The value of u as follows:

$u = 37517 \pmod{16} = 13 = u_{mod}$. The parameter t is computed by

$t = B' (2B' + 1) \lll 4 =$

$62347 (2 * 62347 + 1) \lll 4$

$= 7774359165 \pmod{65536} \equiv 20093$. The binary representation of 20093 is 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 1.

By shifting four positions, the binary representation becomes

1 1 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0. So, the decimal number of

1 1 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 is equal to 59348 . The value of t as follows:

$$t = 59348 \pmod{16} \equiv 4 = t_{mod}$$

$$C = ((C - s_4) \ggg t_{mod}) \oplus u$$

$$= ((23409 - 64837) \ggg 4) \oplus 37517$$

$$= ((-41428 \pmod{65536}) \ggg 4) \oplus 37517$$

$$= (24108) \ggg 4) \oplus 37517$$

$$= 50658 \oplus 37517 = 22383$$

$$A = ((A - s_3) \ggg u_{mod}) \oplus t =$$

$$((34645 - 61662) \ggg 13) \oplus 59348$$

$$= (-27017 \pmod{65536}) \ggg 13) \oplus 59348$$

$$= (38519) \ggg 13) \oplus 59348$$

$$= 46012 \oplus 59348 = 21608$$

One loop:

$$D = D' - s_2 = 31912 - 2620 = 29292 \pmod{65536} \equiv 29292 \text{ and}$$

$$B = B' - s_1 = 62347 - 36459 = 25888 \pmod{65536} \equiv 25888 .$$

So, the decryption of the ciphertext is

$$[A, B, C, D] = [21608, 25888, 22383, 29292].$$

$$Block1 = [21608, 25888, 22383, 29292].$$

The remainder blocks decryption by same procedure of Block1, where decryption for the remainder blocks are:

$Block2 = [25632, 26995, 8258, 25953]$.

$Block3 = [30068, 26982, 30060, 24377]$.

The plaintext for all blocks are The World is Beautiful_9.

5.4 Implementation Results of The Encryption and Decryption Image

This section explains an example, with more details, of the encryption and decryption image .

5.4.1 The Implementation Results For Gray Face Image.

Stage A: Generated key

This stage explains the steps of generated key as follows:

Step 1 : Random key generated

This step generates shared secret random key to increase security of key, this key generated with selected seed to enable receiver's side from created same key. It generates a uniformly distributed random integer between a minimum and maximum as follow:

Columns 1 through 27	1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0
Columns 28 through 54	1 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 0
Columns 55 through 81	1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1
Columns 82 through 108	1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 0
Columns 109 through 128	1 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1

Step 2 : ARZ-key generated

This step will generate ARZ-key, where $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$ and 56 matrixes satisfy condition of ARZ-algebra, where summation of ARZ-algebra matrixes is:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	56	0	59	62
2	112	69	0	79
3	168	76	77	0

Step 3 : ARZ-Algebra key

In this step convert summation matrix into binary bit, where each number length equal 8-bits as follow:

Columns 1 through 27	0 0
Columns 28 through 54	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 1
Columns 55 through 81	0 0 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0
Columns 82 through 108	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 1
Columns 109 through 128	0 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0

Step 4: Xor between two keys

In this step applied xor operation between ARZ-algebra key and random key as follows:

Columns 1 through 27	1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0
Columns 28 through 54	1 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 0 1
Columns 55 through 81	1 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 1
Columns 82 through 108	1 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1
Columns 109 through 128	1 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1

Step 5 : Expansion key

The parameters of expansion key are $w = 32, r = 1, P_w = [(e - 2) 2^w] = 3084996963$, and

$$Q_w = [(\varphi - 1) 2^w] \text{ where } \varphi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} = 1.618033 \dots$$

$$Q_w = [((\varphi - 1) 2^w)], \text{ Where } \varphi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} = 1.618033989$$

$Q_w = 2654435769$ and $S = [s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{2r+4}]$. Let L= result of step 7 in binary.

So, $s_1 = P_w = 3084996963$. Now, $s_i = s_{i-1} + Q_w \pmod{2^w}$, for $i=2, \dots, 6$, where $\text{mod } 2^w = 4294967295$ are computed by

$$S = [3084996963, 1444465437, 4098901206, 2458369680, 817838154, 3472273923].$$

Let $c = 4$ which is a number of a word for key. Now,

$$v = 3 * \max\{c, 2r + 4\} = 3 * \max\{4, 6\} = 18, \text{ where } v \text{ is number time for change key, with a round } r = 1.$$

$$S = [1996237356, 1444465437, 4098901206, 2458369680, 817838154, 3472273923]$$

$$S = [1996237356, 2347392679, 4098901206, 2458369680, 817838154, 3472273923]$$

$S = [1996237356, 2347392679, 3636435855, 2458369680, 817838154, 3472273923]$

$S = [1996237356, 2347392679, 3636435855, 1335299054, 817838154, 3472273923]$

$S = [1996237356, 2347392679, 3636435855, 1335299054, 885819881, 3472273923]$

$S = [1996237356, 2347392679, 3636435855, 1335299054, 885819881, 154996453]$

$S = [1118549894, 2347392679, 3636435855, 1335299054, 885819881, 154996453]$

$S = [1118549894, 3058131813, 3636435855, 1335299054, 885819881, 154996453]$

$S = [1118549894, 3058131813, 2673923269, 1335299054, 885819881, 154996453]$

$S = [1118549894, 3058131813, 2673923269, 552233607, 885819881, 154996453]$

$S = [1118549894, 3058131813, 2673923269, 552233607, 3440409442, 154996453]$

$S = [1118549894, 3058131813, 2673923269, 552233607, 3440409442, 3689030037]$

$S = [622612876, 3058131813, 2673923269, 552233607, 3440409442, 3689030037]$

$S = [622612876, 49404699, 2673923269, 552233607, 3440409442, 3689030037]$

Columns 1 through 41	1 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0
Columns 42 through 82	0 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 1
Columns 83 through 123	1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0
Columns 124 through 164	1 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 1
Columns 165 through 205	1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 0
Columns 206 through 246	0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0
Columns 247 through 287	1 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 1
Columns 288 through 328	0 0 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0
Columns 329 through 369	1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 1
Columns 370 through 400	1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 0

Step 3: Divide binary in step two into blocks

This step divide binary into Blocks, where each block length equal 128 bit as follows:

Columns 1 through 41	1 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0
	0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1
	0 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 1
Columns 42 through 82	0 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 1
	1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 1
	1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0
Columns 83 through 123	1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0
	1 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1
	0 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 0
Columns 124 through 128	1 1 0 1 0
	1 1 0 1 0
	1 0 1 0 0

Step 4: Divided the block into 4-blocks each block with 32 bit are A, B, C,D.

Block 1:

A=[1 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0
0 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 0]

$$B = [1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \\ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0]$$

$$C = [1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \\ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0]$$

$$D = [1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \\ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0].$$

Divided block 2 & block3 in same block 1.

Step 5: This step encryption 4-blocks by ARZ-RC6 algorithm as follows:

Block1 = [15141141, 1250626920, 3625760506, 3120090708],

The remainder blocks encryption by same procedure of block1, where encryption for remainder blocks are:

Block2 = [486687842, 3418998145, 3676487707, 3667386097]

Block3 = [4057272365, 2510593181, 2834729437, 2106083670]

Step 6: Convert blocks into binary, where each block length equal 64-bits as follows:

Columns 1 through 27	1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 0
Columns 28 through 54	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 0
Columns 55 through 81	0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 0
Columns 82 through 108	0 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 1
Columns 109 through 135	0 0 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1
Columns 136 through 162	0 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0
Columns 163 through 189	0 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 0
Columns 190 through 216	0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0
Columns 217 through 243	1 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 1
Columns 244 through 270	0 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0
Columns 271 through 297	0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0
Columns 298 through 324	0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 1
Columns 325 through 351	1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0
Columns 352 through 378	1 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 0
Columns 379 through	1 1 1 1 1 0

Step 7: Convert binary into decimal, where each number length equal 8-bits and output is encryption image as follows:

Columns 1 through 27	21 9 231 0 104 13 139 74 250 182 28 216 84 206 248 185 98 68 2 29 129 197 201 203 27 192 34
Columns 28 through 50	219 241 222 151 218 45 16 213 241 157 156 164 149 221 137 246 168 86 73 136 125 42 15

Stage C: Decryption by ARZ-RC6 algorithm

This stage explains the decryption steps as follow:

Step 1: generated a symmetric key as in stage A.

Step 2: input is encryption image and show sub-encryption image as follows:

Columns 1 through 27
21 9 231 0 104 13 139 74 250 182 28 216 84 206 248 185 98 68 2 29 129 197 201 203 27 192 34
Columns 28 through 50
219 241 222 151 218 45 16 213 241 157 156 164 149 221 137 246 168 86 73 136 125 42 15

Step 3: Convert pixels of encryption image into binary with 8-bits as follows:

Columns 1 through 27	1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 0
Columns 28 through 54	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 0
Columns 55 through 81	0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 0
Columns 82 through 108	0 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 1
Columns 109 through 135	0 0 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1
Columns 136 through 162	0 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0
Columns 163 through 189	0 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 0
Columns 190 through 216	0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0
Columns 217 through 243	1 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 1
Columns 244 through 270	0 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0
Columns 271 through 297	0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0
Columns 298 through 324	0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 1
Columns 325 through 351	1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0
Columns 352 through 378	1 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 0
Columns 379 through	1 1 1 1 1 0

Step 4: Divide blocks into 4-blocks with 32-bits are A, B, C, D.

Block 1:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$C = [1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \\ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0]$$

$$D = [1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \\ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0]$$

Divided block 2 & block3 in same block 1.

Step 5: Apply ARZ-RC6 algorithm to give original image as follows:

Block1 = [943466533, 1112292397, 1026965827, 1515016507],

The reminder blocks decryption by same procedure of Block1, where decryption for remainder blocks are:

Block2 = [1835429222, 1583839098, 1413958998, 1565743708]

Block3 = [1347311966, 859456326, 455093043, 723985438]

Step 6: convert blocks into binary as follows:

Columns 28 through 54	1 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 0
Columns 55 through 81	1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0
Columns 82 through 108	1 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 0
Columns 109 through 135	1 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1
Columns 136 through 162	0 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 1
Columns 163 through 189	0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 1 1
Columns 190 through 216	0 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0
Columns 217 through 243	0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 1 0
Columns 244 through 270	0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 0
Columns 271 through 297	1 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 1
Columns 298 through 324	1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0
Columns 325 through 351	1 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 0
Columns 352 through 378	0 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 1
Columns 379 through 384	0 1 0 1 0 0

Step 7: Convert binary into decimal with 8-bits for each decimal number and create original image as follows:

Columns 1 through 27
37 40 60 56 45 60 76 66 67 65 54 61 59 81 77 90 102 109 102 109 122 119 103 94 86 77 71
Columns 28 through 50
84 92 90 83 93 94 89 78 80 70 67 58 51 51 43 32 27 30 36 39 43 47 47

5.4.2 Other Implemented Result

This section explain run of encryption method as follows:

Face image	Resize image	Encryption	Decryption	
Measures ,	MSE =0	PSNR=Inf	RMSE=0	SNR =0
Face image	Resize image	Encryption	Decryption	
Measures ,	MSE =0	PSNR=Inf	RMSE=0	SNR =0
Face image	Resize image	Encryption	Decryption	
Measures ,	MSE =0	PSNR=Inf	RMSE=0	SNR =0

Figure 5-7:face encryptionand decryption images

iris image	Resize image	Encryption	Decryption
Measures			
MSE =0	PSNR=Inf	RMSE=0	SNR =0
iris image	Resize image	Encryption	Decryption
Measures			
MSE =0	PSNR=Inf	RMSE=0	SNR =0
Face image 11	Resize image	Encryption	Decryption
Measures			
MSE =0	PSNR=Inf	RMSE=0	SNR =0

Figure 5-8: iris encryption and decryption images.

fingerprint image	Resize image	Encryption	Decryption
Measures			
MSE =0	PSNR=Inf	RMSE=0	SNR =0
fingerprint image	Resize image	Encryption	Decryption
Measures			
MSE =0	PSNR=Inf	RMSE=0	SNR =0

Figure 5-9: fingerprint encryption and decryption images.

5.4.3 Type Implementation Result For Encryption Color biometric images

Hand image	Resize image	Encryption	Decryption	
Layer 1:	MSE = 0;	PSNR = Inf;	RMSE = 0 ;	SNR = 0;
Layer 2:	MSE = 0;	PSNR = Inf;	RMSE = 0 ;	SNR = 0;
Layer 3:	MSE = 0;	PSNR = Inf;	RMSE = 0 ;	SNR = 0
Iris image	Resize image	Encryption	Decryption	
Layer 1:	MSE = 0;	PSNR = Inf;	RMSE = 0 ;	SNR = 0;
Layer 2:	MSE = 0;	PSNR = Inf;	RMSE = 0 ;	SNR = 0;
Layer 3:	MSE = 0;	PSNR = Inf;	RMSE = 0 ;	SNR = 0;
Lena image	Resize image	Encryption	Decryption	
Layer 1:	MSE = 0;	PSNR = Inf;	RMSE = 0 ;	SNR = 0;
Layer 2:	MSE = 0;	PSNR = Inf;	RMSE = 0 ;	SNR = 0;

Layer 3: MSE = 0; PSNR = Inf; RMSE = 0 ; SNR = 0;			
Fruit image	Resize image	Encryption	Decryption
Layer 1: MSE = 0; PSNR = Inf; RMSE = 0 ; SNR = 0;			
Layer 2: MSE = 0; PSNR = Inf; RMSE = 0 ; SNR = 0;			
Layer 3: MSE = 0; PSNR = Inf; RMSE = 0 ; SNR = 0;			
Face image	Resize image	Encryption	Decryption
Layer 1: MSE = 0; PSNR = Inf; RMSE = 0 ; SNR = 0;			
Layer 2: MSE = 0; PSNR = Inf; RMSE = 0 ; SNR = 0;			
Layer 3: MSE = 0; PSNR = Inf; RMSE = 0 ; SNR = 0;			

Figure 5-10: color images encryption and decryption.

5.4.4 The Implementation Results For Color Face Image.

Stage A: Generated key

This stage explain steps of generated key as follows:

Step 1 : Random key generated

This step generate shared secret random key to increasing security of key, this key generated with selected seed to enable receiver's side from created same key. It generates a uniformly distributed random integer between a minimum and maximum as follow:

Columns 1 through 27	1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0
Columns 28 through 54	1 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 0
Columns 55 through 81	1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1
Columns 82 through 108	1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 0
Columns 109 through 128	1 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1

Step 2: ARZ-key generated

This step will generate ARZ-key, where $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ and 56 matrixes satisfy condition of ARZ-algebra, where summation of ARZ-algebra matrixes is:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	56	0	59	62
2	112	69	0	79
3	168	76	77	0

Step 3 : ARZ-Algebra key

This step convert summation matrix into binary bit, where each number length equal 8-bits as follow:

Columns 1 through 27	0 0
Columns 28 through 54	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 1
Columns 55 through 81	0 0 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0
Columns 82 through 108	0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 1
Columns 109 through 128	0 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0

Step 4: Xor between two keys

This step apply xor operation between ARZ-algebra key and random key as follows:

Columns 1 through 27	1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0
Columns 28 through 54	1 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 0 1
Columns 55 through 81	1 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 1
Columns 82 through 108	1 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1
Columns 109 through 128	1 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1

Step 5: Expansion key

The parameters of expansion key are $w = 32, r = 1,$

$P_w = [(e - 2) 2^w] = 3084996963,$ and $Q_w = [\varphi - 1) 2^w]$ where

$$\varphi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} = 1.618033989$$

$Q_w = 2654435769$ and $S = [s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{2r+4}]$. Let L= result of step 7 in binary.

So, $s_1 = P_w = 3084996963$. Now, $s_i = s_{i-1} + Q_w \pmod{2^w}$, for $i=2, \dots, 6$, where $\text{mod}2^w = 4294967295$ are computed by

$S = [3084996963, 1444465437, 4098901206, 2458369680, 817838154, 3472273923]$.

Let $c = 4$ which is a number of a word for key. Now,

$v = 3 * \max\{c, 2r + 4\} = 3 * \max\{4, 6\} = 18$, where v is number time for change key, with a round $r = 1$.

$S = [1996237356, 1444465437, 4098901206, 2458369680, 817838154, 3472273923]$

$S = [1996237356, 2347392679, 4098901206, 2458369680, 817838154, 3472273923]$

$S = [1996237356, 2347392679, 3636435855, 2458369680, 817838154, 3472273923]$

$S = [1996237356, 2347392679, 3636435855, 1335299054, 817838154, 3472273923]$

$S = [1996237356, 2347392679, 3636435855, 1335299054, 885819881, 3472273923]$

$S = [1996237356, 2347392679, 3636435855, 1335299054, 885819881, 154996453]$

$S = [1118549894, 2347392679, 3636435855, 1335299054, 885819881, 154996453]$

$S = [1118549894, 3058131813, 3636435855, 1335299054, 885819881, 154996453]$

$S = [1118549894, 3058131813, 2673923269, 1335299054, 885819881, 154996453]$

$S = [1118549894, 3058131813, 2673923269, 552233607, 885819881, 154996453]$

$S = [1118549894, 3058131813, 2673923269, 552233607, 3440409442, 154996453]$

$S = [1118549894, 3058131813, 2673923269, 552233607, 3440409442, 3689030037]$

$S = [622612876, 3058131813, 2673923269, 552233607, 3440409442, 3689030037]$

$S = [622612876, 49404699, 2673923269, 552233607, 3440409442, 3689030037]$

$S = [622612876, 49404699, 2305356886, 552233607, 3440409442, 3689030037]$

$S = [622612876, 49404699, 2305356886, 1314790898, 3440409442, 3689030037]$

$S = [622612876, 49404699, 2305356886, 1314790898, 2575203163, 3689030037]$

$S = [622612876, 49404699, 2305356886, 1314790898, 2575203163, 2061339300]$

Stage B: Encryption Color Image by ARZ-RC6 Algorithm

This stage explain steps of encryption as follows:

Step 1 : Sub-image.

This step cut part from the original image and namely sub-image, where input original image is face image as follows:

Layer 1:

Columns 1 through 20																			
229	165	39	35	40	81	137	167	173	184	195	198	204	210	215	219	222	223	224	220
Columns 21 through 40																			
220	221	222	221	222	223	221	220	221	221	221	222	223	222	217	214	208	204	201	195
Columns 41 through 50																			
188	176	166	143	89	44	30	32	145	228										

Layer 2:

Columns 1 through 20																			
213	149	23	18	21	54	102	123	123	132	139	144	148	151	153	152	155	156	158	160
Columns 21 through 40																			
163	163	167	168	170	170	170	167	164	162	162	159	157	154	153	153	150	148	145	138
Columns 41 through 50																			
131	125	121	103	55	20	18	22	131	212										

Layer 3:

Columns 1 through 20																			
216	152	26	21	19	49	93	115	116	122	127	130	135	139	141	137	139	140	141	140
Columns 21 through 40																			
144	148	152	151	153	154	153	150	148	147	143	141	140	137	135	137	137	134	131	127
Columns 41 through 50																			
123	117	114	101	57	26	20	23	133	215										

Step 2: Binary pixels of image

This step convert the pixels into binary and each pixel equal 8-bits as follow:

Layer 1:

Columns 1 through 41	1 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 1
Columns 42 through 82	0 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1
Columns 83 through 123	0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 1 1 1 0
Columns 124 through 164	1 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 1
Columns 165 through 205	1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1
Columns 206 through 246	0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0
Columns 247 through 287	1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 1
Columns 288 through 328	1 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 1
Columns 329 through 369	0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0
Columns 370 through 384	1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0

Layer 2:

Columns 1 through 41	1 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0
Columns 42 through 82	1 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 1
Columns 83 through 123	0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 0
Columns 124 through 164	1 1 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0
Columns 165 through 205	0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 0
Columns 206 through 246	1 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1
Columns 247 through 287	0 1 1 1 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0
Columns 288 through 328	1 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 1
Columns 329 through 369	1 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0
Columns 370 through 384	1 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0

Layer 2:

Columns 1 through 41																																											
1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0				
1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	
1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Columns 42 through 82																																											
1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1		
1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	
0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0		
Columns 83 through 123																																											
0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0		
0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1		
0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
Columns 124 through 128																																											
1	1	0	0	1																																							
1	1	0	0	1																																							
0	1	0	0	0																																							

Layer 3:

Columns 1 through 41																																														
0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1				
1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0		
0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0		
Columns 42 through 82																																														
0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1		
0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0		
1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	
Columns 83 through 123																																														
1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0		
0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1			
0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1
Columns 124 through 128																																														
1	0	0	0	1																																										
1	0	0	0	1																																										
0	1	0	0	0																																										

Step 4: Divide the block into 4-blocks each block with 64 bit are A, B, C,D from step3.

Step 5: This step encryption 4-blocks by ARZ-RC6 algorithm as follows:

Layer 1:

$Block1 = [1713643024, \quad 478225702, 1504131212, 1496410724]$

The reminder blocks encryption by same procedure of Block1, where encryption for remainder blocks are:

$Block2 = [2625219268, 1321228962, 1554858909, \quad 245564106]$

$Block3 = [2187631032, 3212557780, 2649592344, 3675186000]$

Layer 2:

$Block1 = [973144829, 2015886686, 375979348, 3869487822]$

The reminder blocks encryption by same procedure of Block1, where encryption for remainder blocks are:

$Block2 = [1732407435, 163654259, 494012516, 987374021]$

$Block3 = [1227645310, 2497357063, 2481027574, 1751805340]$

Layer3:

$Block1 = [838335995, 91820376, 123531591, 1048453075]$

The reminder blocks encryption by same procedure of Block1, where encryption for remainder blocks are:

$Block2 = [1446207864, 1178784848, 190773588, 423501363]$

$Block3 = [1042174833, 798746947, 2497937400, 3575820419]$

Step 6: Convert blocks into binary , where each block length equal 64-bits as follows:

Layer 3:

Columns 1 through 27	1 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 0
Columns 28 through 54	0 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 1
Columns 55 through 81	1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0
Columns 82 through 108	0 1 1 1 0 1 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 1
Columns 109 through 135	1 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1
Columns 136 through 162	0 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0
Columns 163 through 189	0 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 0
Columns 190 through 216	0 1 0 0 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 1 1 0 1 0
Columns 217 through 243	1 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 1
Columns 244 through 270	1 1 1 0 0 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 0
Columns 271 through 297	1 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 0 0 0 0 1 0 1
Columns 298 through 324	0 0 1 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 0 0 0 0 0 1
Columns 325 through 351	1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 0 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 1 0 1 0 0
Columns 352 through 378	1 1 1 0 0 0 0 0 1 0 0 0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1 0 0 0 1 0 0 1 0
Columns 379 through 384	1 0 1 0 1 1

Step 7: Convert binary into decimal, where each number length equal 8-bits and output is encryption image as follows:

Layer 1:

Columns 1 through 27	16 30 36 102 38 37 129 28 140 56 167 89 100 106 49 89 196 170 121 156 162 90 192 78 157 67 173
Columns 28 through 50	92 202 2 163 14 184 153 100 130 212 189 123 191 24 146 237 157 80 227 14 219 19 244

Layer2:

Columns 1 through 27	253 2 1 58 94 253 39 120 84 253 104 22 206 178 163 230 139 112 66 103 115 42 193 9 100 8 114
Columns 28 through 50	29 197 33 218 58 126 97 44 73 7 165 218 148 246 121 225 147 156 109 106 104 3 226

Layer 3:

Columns 1 through 27	251 253 247 49 88 17 121 5 71 241 92 7 211 31 126 62 120 97 51 86 80 212 66 70 84 249 94
Columns 28 through 50	11 51 30 62 25 113 83 30 62 67 233 155 47 248 127 227 148 131 176 34 213 6 229

Stage C: Decryption by ARZ-RC6 algorithm

This stage explain decryption steps as follow:

Step 1: Generate a symmetric key as in stage A.

Step 2: Input is encryption image and show sub-encryption image as follows:

Layer 1:

Columns 1 through 27																																						
16	30	36	102	38	37	129	28	140	56	167	89	100	106	49	89	196	170	121	156	162	90	192	78	157	67	173												
Columns 28 through 50																																						
92	202	2	163	14	184	153	100	130	212	189	123	191	24	146	237	157	80	227	14	219	19	244																

Layer2:

Columns 1 through 27																																						
253	2	1	58	94	253	39	120	84	253	104	22	206	178	163	230	139	112	66	103	115	42	193	9	100	8	114												
Columns 28 through 50																																						
29	197	33	218	58	126	97	44	73	7	165	218	148	246	121	225	147	156	109	106	104	3	226																

Layer 3:

Columns 1 through 27																																						
251	253	247	49	88	17	121	5	71	241	92	7	211	31	126	62	120	97	51	86	80	212	66	70	84	249	94												
Columns 28 through 50																																						
11	51	30	62	25	113	83	30	62	67	233	155	47	248	127	227	148	131	176	34	213	6	229																

Step 3: Convert pixels of encryption image into binary with 8-bits as follows:

Layer 3:

Columns 1 through 27	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	
Columns 28 through 54	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1
Columns 55 through 81	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1
Columns 82 through 108	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Columns 109 through 135	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
Columns 136 through 162	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0
Columns 163 through 189	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1
Columns 190 through 216	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
Columns 217 through 243	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1
Columns 244 through 270	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
Columns 271 through 297	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1
Columns 298 through 324	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1
Columns 325 through 351	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
Columns 352 through 378	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
Columns 379 through 384	1	0	1	0	1	1																			

Step 4: Divide blocks into 4-blocks with 64-bits are A, B, C, D.

Step 5: Apply ARZ-RC6 algorithm to give original image as follows:

Layer 1:

Block 1 = [589800933, 2810794280, 3334715565, 3688354508]

The remainder blocks decryption by same procedure of *Block1*, where decryption for remainder blocks are:

Block 2 = [3705724894, 3722370524, 3705528286, 3739082205]

Block 3 = [3604602591, 3284782288, 2410066108, 538848345]

Layer 2:

Block 1 = [303535573, 2070296085, 2425062523, 2560202644]

The remainder blocks decryption by same procedure of *Block1*, where decryption for remainder blocks are:

Block 2 = [2694749339, 2829558691, 2812979882, 2678235812]

Layer 2:

Columns 1 through 27	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	
Columns 28 through 54	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
Columns 55 through 81	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
Columns 82 through 108	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
Columns 109 through 135	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
Columns 136 through 162	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1
Columns 163 through 189	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
Columns 190 through 216	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
Columns 217 through 243	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
Columns 244 through 270	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0
Columns 271 through 297	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Columns 298 through 324	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0
Columns 325 through 351	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1
Columns 352 through 378	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Columns 379 through 384	1	0	1	0	0	0																					

Layer 3:

Columns 1 through 27	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
Columns 28 through 54	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0
Columns 55 through 81	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1
Columns 82 through 108	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1
Columns 109 through 135	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
Columns 136 through 162	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
Columns 163 through 189	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1
Columns 190 through 216	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
Columns 217 through 243	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1
Columns 244 through 270	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0
Columns 271 through 297	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
Columns 298 through 324	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
Columns 325 through 351	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1
Columns 352 through 378	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1
Columns 379 through 384	1	0	1	0	0	0																					

Step 7: Convert binary into decimal with 8-bits for each decimal number and create original image as follows:

Layer1:

Columns 1 through 20																			
229	165	39	35	40	81	137	167	173	184	195	198	204	210	215	219	222	223	224	220
Columns 21 through 40																			
220	221	222	221	222	223	221	220	221	221	221	222	223	222	217	214	208	204	201	195
Columns 41 through 50																			
188	176	166	143	89	44	30	32	145	228										

Layer 2:

Columns 1 through 20																			
213	149	23	18	21	54	102	123	123	132	139	144	148	151	153	152	155	156	158	160
Columns 21 through 40																			
163	163	167	168	170	170	170	167	164	162	162	159	157	154	153	153	150	148	145	138
Columns 41 through 50																			
131	125	121	103	55	20	18	22	131	212										

Layer 3:

Columns 1 through 20																			
216	152	26	21	19	49	93	115	116	122	127	130	135	139	141	137	139	140	141	140
Columns 21 through 40																			
144	148	152	151	153	154	153	150	148	147	143	141	140	137	135	137	137	134	131	127
Columns 41 through 50																			
123	117	114	101	57	26	20	23	133	215										

Figure 5-11: Some samples of the ORL database.

Figure 5-12: Some samples of the MMI database.

Figure 5-13: Some samples of the CMU database.

Figure 5-14: Some samples of the Face94 database.

Figure 5-15: Some samples of the HZ database.

Example 1. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	0	0	0
3	3	0	0	0

Example 2. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	0	0	0
3	3	1	2	0

Example 3. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	0	0	0
3	3	2	2	0

Example 4. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	0
3	3	1	0	0

Example 5. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	0
3	3	2	2	0

Example 6. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	1
3	3	1	1	0

Example 7. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	3
3	3	0	0	0

Example 8. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	2	0	0
3	3	2	2	0

Example 9. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	2	0	0
3	3	3	2	0

Example 10. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	2	0	2
3	3	1	1	0

Example 11. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow::

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	2	0	3
3	3	3	0	0

Example 12. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	3	0	3
3	3	0	0	0

Example 13. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	3	0	3
3	3	1	0	0

Example 14. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	3	0	3
3	3	3	0	0

Example 15. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1
2	2	0	0	1
3	3	3	3	0

Example 16. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1
2	2	0	0	2
3	3	3	3	0

Example 17. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1
2	2	1	0	1
3	3	3	3	0

Example 18. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1
2	2	1	0	2
3	3	3	3	0

Example 19. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	2
2	2	0	0	1
3	3	3	3	0

Example 20. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	2
2	2	0	0	2
3	3	3	3	0

Example 21. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	3
2	2	0	0	3
3	3	0	0	0

Example 22. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	3
2	2	3	0	3
3	3	0	0	0

Example 23. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	0
2	2	2	0	2
3	3	0	1	0

Example 24. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	0
2	2	2	0	2
3	3	0	3	0

Example 25. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	0
2	2	2	0	2
3	3	1	1	0

Example 26. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	0
2	2	2	0	2
3	3	1	3	0

Example 27. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	1
2	2	0	0	0
3	3	2	2	0

Example 28. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	1
2	2	0	0	3
3	3	0	0	0

Example 29. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	1
2	2	2	0	0
3	3	2	0	0

Example 30. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	1
2	2	2	0	0
3	3	2	2	0

Example 31. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	1
2	2	2	0	0
3	3	3	0	0

Example 32. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	1
2	2	2	0	0
3	3	3	2	0

Example 33. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	1
2	2	2	0	2
3	3	3	3	0

Example 34. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	1
2	2	2	0	3
3	3	3	0	0

Example 35. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	1
2	2	3	0	0
3	3	2	0	0

Example 36. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	1
2	2	3	0	0
3	3	3	0	0

Example 37. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	1
2	2	3	0	3
3	3	0	0	0

Example 38. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	1
2	2	3	0	3
3	3	3	0	0

Example 39. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	3
2	2	0	0	0
3	3	0	3	0

Example 40. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	3
2	2	2	0	2
3	3	0	3	0

Example 41. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	2	0
2	2	0	0	0
3	3	0	2	0

Example 42. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	2	0
2	2	0	0	0
3	3	2	2	0

Example 43. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	2	1
2	2	0	0	2
3	3	3	3	0

Example 44. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as shown in

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	2	2
2	2	0	0	0
3	3	2	2	0

Example 45. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	2	2
2	2	0	0	2
3	3	3	3	0

Example 46. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	2	2
2	2	0	0	3
3	3	0	0	0

Example 47. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	2	3
2	2	0	0	0
3	3	0	0	0

Example 48. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	3	0
2	2	2	0	2
3	3	0	1	0

Example 49. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	3	0
2	2	2	0	2
3	3	0	3	0

Example 50. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	3	2
2	2	0	0	3
3	3	0	0	0

Example 51. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	3	3
2	2	0	0	0
3	3	0	0	0

Example 52. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	3	3
2	2	0	0	0
3	3	0	2	0

Example 53. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	3	3
2	2	0	0	0
3	3	0	3	0

Example 54. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	3	3
2	2	0	0	3
3	3	0	0	0

Example 55. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	3	3
2	2	2	0	2
3	3	0	3	0

Example 56. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a ARZ-algebra as follow:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	3	3
2	2	3	0	3
3	3	0	0	0

Chapter

Six

**Conclusion and
future works**

Chapter six

Conclusions and Future Work

6.1 Conclusions

This chapter some important conclusions have presented with some suggestions for future work.

1. Proposing ARZ-algebra where ARZ-algebra is square matrix satisfy six condition also two types of algebra are fuzzy and ordinary.
2. Proposing some definitions such as subalgebra ,ARZ-ideal ,quotient ARZ-algebra , homeomorphism ,commutative and implicative.
3. Converting ARZ-algebra into binary block code by ARZ-function .
4. Using biometric data such as face ,fingerprint ,hand ,and iris and other image .
5. Generating key by ARZ-algebra with Random key .
6. Encryption data (image, text) by using RC6 block cipher.
7. Decrypting ciphertext by using RC6 block cipher.
8. Applying some measures to compute accuracy of proposed method .

6.2 Future Work

1. Creating new algebra by ARZ-algebra.
2. Studying translation fuzzy ARZ-ideal
3. Studying multiplication fuzzy ARZ-ideal
4. Studying generalized fuzzy ARZ-ideal
5. Studying Cubic fuzzy ARZ-ideal
6. Studying interval-valued fuzzy ARZ-ideal
7. Studying anti-fuzzy ARZ-ideal
8. Encryption by another block cipher such as AES or DES.
9. Creating key by chaotic map.
10. Studying other mathematical properties of these species.

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الخلاصة

يعتبر الجبر معلما هاما في الرياضيات. غالبًا ما يجد الطلاب هذا الموضوع معقدًا. لكنها في الواقع واحدة من أكثر موضوعات الرياضيات إثارة للاهتمام ، ويمكن أن تساعد الممارسة المنتظمة لموضوعات الجبر الطلاب على تطوير مهاراتهم المنطقية والاستدلالية.

تشتمل الطريقة المقترحة على ARZ-algebra و fuzzy ARZ-algebra و ARZ-binary block code وتطبيق ARZ-algebra في خوارزمية التشفير وهي RC6.

عرفنا ARZ- algebra وتم برهان بعض خصائصه. تم تعريف مفاهيم التالية وهي quotient ARZ-Algebras و ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra و subalgebra, ideal و homomorphism و several theorems وتم ذكر الخصائص وإثباتها.

كذلك عرفنا fuzzy ARZ-ideal و ideal و subalgebra و homomorphism و الضرب الديكارتي. وايضا تم اثبات بعض الخواص والنظريات المهمة لهذا النوع من الجبر.

يتم إنشاء كود كتلة ARZ الثنائي بناءً على ARZ-algebra وهو تعميم لـ BCC-algebra. يتم تعريف دالة ذات قيمة ARZ لتشكيل هذا الرمز. في حالات مختلفة من جبر ARZ ، أي commutative و implicative و not commutative and implicative و not commutative and implicative و not implicative و commutative و not implicative ، اذا كان ARZ-code موجود. ARZ-code V هو مجموعة فرعية من كود الكتلة الثنائية العالمية. على العكس من ذلك ، يمكن استخدام كود ARZ لاستعادة ARZ الجبر. تم إثبات هذه النتائج رياضيا. يتم تقديم بعض الأمثلة لشرح هذه النتائج. يعتبر إنشاء كود ARZ بمثابة رؤية جديدة للاتصالات.

انتشرت المعلومات الرقمية في جميع أنحاء العالم ؛ تتطلب هذه المعلومات الرقمية الحماية من الأنشطة الخبيثة عند إرسالها من جهاز إلى آخر عبر الشبكة اللاسلكية ، لذلك استخدمنا خوارزميات التشفير لحفظ هذه المعلومات. Rivest Cipher 6 (RC6) هي عبارة عن خوارزمية تشفير تعتمد على تقسيم البيانات السرية الى حزم ويتم انشاء المفتاح الخاص بالتشفير بواسطة ARZ-algebra.

RC6 هو تحسينات على RC5. وكذلك هذه الخوارزمية تلبى متطلبات خوارزمية AES.

قواعد البيانات المستخدمة هي ORL و CMU و MMI و HZFD و Casei iris وبصمة الإصبع والوجه 94.

لتقدير دقة بيانات التشفير وفك التشفير ، تم استخدام بعض الاختبارات مثل PSNR و SNR و MSE و RMSE.

البرنامج المستخدم هو MATLAB R2020a ومواصفات الكمبيوتر المحمول Hp و Intel RAM 4GB و core i5.

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ARZ-algebra لتطبيق مخطط التشفير

رسالة مقدمة الى

مجلس كلية التربية للبنات/ جامعة الكوفة كجزء من متطلبات نيل درجة الدكتوراه في
الرياضيات من قبل الطالبة :

زينب راضي موسى

بإشراف

أ.د. أريج توفيق حميد

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2022 م

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